

Accelerating and upscaling transformational adaptation in
Europe: demonstration of water-related innovation
packages

Intermediary Monitoring Report

Deliverable 5.8

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Author(s)	Egaleo: Stelios Karozis, Dimitris Tzempelikos; Galicja: Amaya Soto, Lucia Fraga, Andrea Ogando Vidal, Carlos Rodriguez, Jose Guitian Bermejo, Silvia Torres, Silvia Piedracoba, Ignacio Gonzalez Lappeenranta: Sanna Varis, Liulu Du-Ikonen, Mariiag Zhaurova, Risto Soukka, Mika Luoranen, Tuomas Sihvonen, Satu-Pia Reinikainen; Oristano: Manuela Puddu, Francesca Etzi; West Country Region: Giles Rickard, Nicola Rogers, Zoe Smith.
Primary Contact and Email	Jan Cools, jan.cools@uantwerpen.be Hnátková Tereza, hnatkovat@fzp.czu.cz
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LIST OF ACRONYMS

AP	Action Plan
AWAR	Awareness-raising modules
BNG	Biodiversity Net Gain
CAF/CAE	Citizen app
CEI	Choice experiment
CCA	Climate change adaptation
CC	Climate Change
CCISC	Climate Change Impacts Study Committee
CETMAR	Technological Centre of the Sea
CIH	Climate innovation hub
CIL	Community Infrastructure Levy
COAST	Coastal Contract
CoM	Covenant of Mayors for Climate and Energy
COTS	Commercial off-the-shelf
CS	Citizen scientists
DEFRA	UK Department for Environment, Farming and Rural Affairs
DSI	Demand analysis for social services and infrastructures
EEA	European Environment Agency
ELMS	Environmental Land Management Scheme
ERDF	European Regional Development Fund
ESNACC	Elements for a National Adaptation Strategy to Climate Change
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
GIS	Geographic Information Systems
GHG	Greenhouse gases
HAB	Harmful Algal Bloom
ICW	Integrated Constructed Wetlands
INTERM	Intertidal Monitoring
IoT	Internet of Things
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
ISPRA	Institute for Environmental Protection and Research
KCS	Key community system

KPI	Key performance indicator
LWO	Local Wetland Observatory
MASE	Ministry for the Environment and Energy Security
MOE	Municipality of Egaleo
MoEE	Greek Ministry of Environment and Energy
MRM	Mussel Raft Monitoring
MRV	Monitoring, Reporting and Verification
NAP	National adaptation plan
NAS	National Adaptation Strategy
NBS	Nature-based Solution
NCM	Natural Capital Marketplace
NCCAC	National Climate Change Adaptation Committee
NCSRDR	National Centre For Scientific Research Demokritos
NN	Nutrient Neutrality
OECC	Spanish Climate Change Office
PNACC	Spanish National Adaptation Plan to Climate Change
RAAP	Regional Adaptation Action Plans
RASCC	Regional Adaptation Strategy to Climate Change
RI	Resilience Index
SAC	Special Area of Conservation
SCS	Smart Climate Stations
STH	Stakeholders
SuDS	Sustainable Drainage System
SWM	Storm water modular system
SWMM	Storm water monitoring
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
URB	Urban run-off system
UVIGO	University of Vigo
WRT	Westcountry Rivers Trust

TABLE OF CONTENTS

LIST OF ACRONYMS.....	3
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY.....	7
1.0 MUNICIPALITY OF EGALEO – ECOSYSTEM OF SOLUTIONS	9
1.1.CONTEXT.....	9
Infographic.....	9
Geographical description	10
Climate vulnerability, impacts and challenges.....	10
Sectors (KCS) impacted.....	11
Legislative background	11
Adaptation governance at the national level.....	11
Relevant national Greek policies.....	12
Adaptation governance at the regional level.....	12
Adaptation governance at the local level	12
1.2. DESCRIPTION OF SOLUTIONS IN TRANSFORMAR.....	13
Description of the solutions	13
Description the expected innovation	15
1.3. EXPECTED IMPACTS	16
Overview of the expected impacts	16
Dominant Indicators.....	17
Baseline data	17
Approach to monitor impacts.....	17
Availability and access of monitored data.....	17
1.4. WORK IN THE UPCOMING MONTHS.....	18
1.5. ANNEX – KPI USED BY MOE PER SOLUTION	19
2.0. GALICIA – MRM/IR/INTERM.....	1
2.1. CONTEXT	2
Infographic.....	2
Background & objectives.....	3
Objectives	3
Geographical description	4
Climate vulnerability, impacts and challenges.....	5
Legislative background	7
Adaptation Governance at the National Level.....	7
Relevant National Spanish Policies.....	7
Adaptation Governance at the Regional Level.....	7
Adaptation Governance at the Local Level.....	8
Measuring Risks and Vulnerabilities to Climate Change	8
Monitoring implementation	8

Building capacity and disseminating knowledge	8
2.2. DESCRIPTION OF SOLUTIONS IN TRANSFORMAR	9
Resilience Index (RI).....	9
Intertidal Monitoring – INTERM	11
Mussel Raft Monitoring - MRM.....	13
Expected Innovations	15
RESILIENCE INDEX (RI).....	15
INTERTIDAL MONITORING - INTERM.....	16
MUSSEL RAFT MONITORING - MRM.....	17
2.3. EXPECTED IMPACTS.....	18
Overview of the expected impacts	18
Project impact indicators, approach of monitoring	18
Baseline data	25
Availability and access of monitored data.....	26
2.4. CONCLUSIONS.....	27
2.5. REFERENCES	28
3.0. LAPPEENRANTA – DEVELOPING STORMWATER MANAGEMENT AND MONITORING	30
3.1. CONTEXT.....	31
Infographic.....	31
Objectives	31
Geographical description	32
Climate vulnerability, impacts and challenges.....	33
State-of-the-art on adaptation in the demonstrator	35
3.2. DESCRIPTION OF SOLUTIONS IN TRANSFORMAR	38
URB (NBS)	38
SWMM (digital solution)	40
CAF (Citizen app)	42
CEI (Choice experiment)	43
Description of the expected innovations.....	44
3.3.EXPECTED IMPACTS	45
Overview of the expected impacts	45
Selected indicators.....	45
Baseline data	49
Approach to monitor impacts	51
Availability and access of monitored data.....	53
Upscaling and acceleration of the solutions	53
3.4. CONCLUSIONS.....	54
4.0. ORISTANO – COAST AND SMART GATE	55
4.1. CONTEXT.....	57
Infographic.....	57
Objectives	57
Geographical description	58

Climate vulnerability, impacts and challenges.....	61
State-of-the-art on adaptation in the demonstrator.....	63
4.2. DESCRIPTION OF SOLUTIONS IN TRANSFORMAR.....	66
The Coastal Contract.....	66
The Smart Gate and Nature-Based Solution	67
Description the expected innovation	76
4.3. EXPECTED IMPACTS.....	76
Overview of the expected impacts and related indicators.....	76
Approach to monitor impacts.....	87
Availability and access of monitored data.....	88
4.4. CONCLUSIONS.....	88
4.5. BIBLIOGRAPHY	89
5.0 WESTCOUNTRY REGION: IMPROVING THE AGRICULTURAL-RIPARIAN INTERFACE IN NUTRIENT SENSITIVE CATCHMENTS IN SOUTH WEST ENGLAND	91
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY.....	91
5.1. CONTEXT	92
Infographic.....	92
Objectives	92
Geography of the Westcountry.....	93
Climate vulnerability, impacts and challenges.....	94
Adaptation within the demonstrator.....	98
5.2. DESCRIPTION OF SOLUTIONS IN TRANSFORMAR	99
Overview of the solutions.....	99
Description of the expected innovation	102
5.3. EXPECTED IMPACTS.....	109
Overview of the expected impacts	109
Selected indicators.....	113
Baseline data	115
Approach to monitor impacts.....	117
Availability and access of monitored data.....	117
5.4. CONCLUSIONS.....	118
5.5. REFERENCES	118

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The main goal of this report (D5.8. Intermediary Monitoring Report) is to provide a comprehensive overview of the solutions implemented in TransformAr demonstrators, and in particular highlighting the approaches to assess their effectiveness on region-specific climate change impacts based on data and metrics proposed.

Each section of the report is dedicated to a specific demonstrator, providing details on its context, innovative solutions implemented, and expected impacts. To assess and quantify these foreseen impacts by the end of the TransformAr project, the respective demonstrators have identified relevant indicators. In addition, the report includes information on existing baseline data and the approach that will be taken for monitoring impact until the end of the project and beyond.

This work presented in D5.8. consists of monitoring advances in WP4: 'Actionable adaptive solutions implementation' for each category of solutions, and nature-based and technological and digital solutions in particular. The aim of this monitoring process is to track the environmental impact of tested solutions, and to recognise overall effectiveness of the application for transformational adaptation in the specific context of each demonstrator.

In this report, we present the progress of the Municipality of Egaleo (Greece), Galicia (Spain), Lappeenranta (Finland), Oristano (Italy) and the Westcountry Region (UK). Required data from demonstration localities are provided by each demonstrator and gathered for detailed analysis. The analyses are focused on parameters monitored and on significant parameters chosen based on literature and previous existing data. A final monitoring report will be delivered at the end of the project at M48.

1.0 Municipality of Egaleo – Ecosystem of solutions

Executive summary

The Municipality of Egaleo (MOE) will install smart climate stations (SCS) at key municipal buildings to acquire a view of the microclimatic conditions. A citizen’s app (CAE) will allow inhabitants to participate in the debate around Climate Change (CC), the changes of the microclimate and potential solutions. Awareness-raising modules (AWAR) will be designed, especially for young people and school pupils to promote climate awareness. In addition, a climate innovation hub (CIH) will be installed to promote green and climate friendly entrepreneurship. A demand analysis for social services and infrastructures (DSI) will be conducted. The ecosystem is depicted in Figure 1.

1.1.Context

Infographic

SCS - Smart Climate Stations | **CAE** - Citizen App | **AWAR** - Awareness-raising | **CIH** - Climate Innovation Hub
DSI - Social services/infrastructures

Figure 1: Ecosystem of MOE’s solution in TransformAr project

Geographical description

The municipality of Egaleo (MOE), Greece (37.9924° N, 23.6781° E) is situated at the west region of the urban planning complex of the region of Attica and has been built at both sides of the ancient road «Iera Odos». It is approximately 4km away from Athens. The borders of Egaleo can be seen in Figure 2 below. The population of the city is around 120.000. The city is exposed to heat waves (expected to increase with CC), extreme precipitations, thunderstorms, and flooding events.

Figure 2: Egaleo borders

Climate vulnerability, impacts and challenges

MOE, being part of the Western Region of Attika in Greece, belongs to the wider Mediterranean biogeographical region. As thoroughly assessed earlier on, Egaleo is at great risk of **drought and wildfires fires of the «Baroutadiko Grove»**. Furthermore, **heatwaves** also pose a dire heat stress danger to elder citizens, vulnerable groups and to households that cannot afford adequate cooling, which also stresses the issue of energy demands of cooling. Among the major natural risks that are threatening Egaleo are fires caused by the severe temperatures and the dryness of the vegetation during summertime.

Another potential natural risk for Egaleo is **flooding** from urban flash floods, which is due to the insufficient flood risk management systems. Egaleo is located near Kifissos river, which has a high risk of flooding during mid-autumn-winter session, causing massive damage to the area. Severe floods with peoples deaths occurred in 1934 in 1954 and in 1997 (Egaleo Book, 2023)

There has been a series of wildfires roaming throughout summertime in Greece. Egaleo has not experienced a direct episode of fire in Baroutadiko Grove, although each summer temperatures have been reaching up to 45°C, putting the municipality in an alarming state.

Stoyanous & Bilinis (2016) presented the issues that Egaleo is facing, increasing the territory's vulnerability from a climate perspective, including:

- Slow population growth rate, high unemployment rate and the prevalence of vulnerable groups (migrants, offenders). These groups often lack the resources to protect themselves against severe climate effects and the slower economic growth of Egaleo makes it difficult with keeping up with their support.
- Infrastructures, mostly the inefficient street planning, the lack of public spaces and parking lots. That leads to surplus people activity in public spaces and increased traffic volume that can cause amplified harm to the environment of the area.
- Direct environmental issues caused by the industrial activity in Eleonas and Yula areas.
- Increasing temperature in Egaleo during summertime is evidence for its citizens to realize the existence and impact that climate change yields. This could urge them to become more aware about their living habits and start changing their lifestyle to an eco-friendlier one (e.g. start using public transportation more, reduce in-house electricity usage, not litter the streets).

Sectors (KCS) impacted

Three KCS where the MOE demonstrator will be implementing solutions to adapt the impacts of climate change include **health**, **infrastructures**, and **urban planning**, described in more detail below:

- **Health:** Rapid urbanization has led to a sharp increase in emissions of CO₂, NO_x and other pollutants, adding to the increasing intensity of heatwaves, significantly affecting the health of citizens. Green areas are extremely limited, leading to artificial means. Even if socially vulnerable groups amount to 10% of the population of the Municipality, this remains a huge problem. Climate change is expected to increase these groups and negatively affect their living conditions.
- **Infrastructures:** Building and infrastructures are not climate-proof. Thunderstorms and heatwaves cannot be dealt with the existing infrastructure, degraded each year.
- **Urban planning:** Climate change also reinforces the urban heat island phenomenon in Egaleo, leading to an increase in energy consumption and carbon footprint; and causing faster degradation of asphalt, tarmac, concrete and another hard surfacing with more frequent needs for maintenance works. The phenomenon thus leads to a reduction in the absorption of rainwater, which overcomes stormwater systems and increases flood risks. Climate change combined with rapid urbanization has created the need for innovative and sustainable urban planning.

Legislative background

Adaptation governance at the national level

The [Greek National Adaptation Strategy \(NAS\)](#) was adopted in 2016, which the Parliament endorsed with the Law 4414/2016. The NAS outlines main objectives, guidance and tools to support the implementation of adaptation policies and actions, and will be reviewed in 2026 (Ministry of Environment and Energy, 2016; OECD, 2020).

As listed by the OECD (2020), the principal objectives of the Greek NAS are to:

- 1) establish and enhance decision-making procedures;

- 2) link adaptation with sustainable growth through implementation of regional/local action plans;
- 3) promote adaptation in all economic sectors, especially the most vulnerable;
- 4) create a monitoring, evaluation and updating mechanism; and
- 5) build capacity and raise awareness.

The [National Climate Change Adaptation Committee \(NCCAC\)](#) advises the Ministry of Environment and Energy (MoEE) and drives the implementation, the development of the NAS and supports adaptation policies. The NCCAC consists of members various levels of government, industry, academia and civil society.

Relevant national Greek policies

[Law 4759/2020 on the Modernisation of Spatial and Urban Planning Legislation and other provisions](#): This document amends previous legislation and notably amends spatial planning with regard to renewable energy projects.

[Greece's recovery and resilience plan](#): Greece has approved a €30.5 billion recovery and resilience plan, consisting of – as [listed by the Grantham institute](#) - “€17.8 billion in grants and €12.7 billion in loans. 37.5% of the plan’s total allocation for reforms and investments supports climate objectives, including: electricity infrastructure, energy efficiency in residential buildings (targeting renovating more than 100,000 residences, including low-income households, to increase energy efficiency) and sustainable mobility.”

Adaptation governance at the regional level

Instead of developing a national action plan, [law 4414/2016](#) sees that the 13 administrative regions of Greece will develop **Regional Adaptation Action Plans (RAAPs)** that will implement the NAS in 7-year cycles (at the time of publishing this report, these are still under development). Quality is ensured for the RAAPs through technical specifications listed in the NAS. To make sure that the RAAPs are compliant with the technical specifications set out in the NAS, the MoEE reviews them before endorsement. If the MoEE identifies that further national action is required, this will be taken up at higher levels. This bottom-up approach accounts for regional circumstances but this may also mean that national action can be delayed. The RAAPs are also sought to inform the mainstreaming of adaptation (for example in disaster risk management plans). The RAAP is also open to public consultation (by members of regional municipalities and regional representatives of governmental authorities, regional stakeholders as well as citizens’ representatives).

Adaptation governance at the local level

The draft of the NAS was open to public consultation before being finalised (by members of the academic community, various ministries, the [Hellenic National Meteorological Service](#) and civil society). Implementation of adaptation actions continuous on a multi-sector level.

[Measuring risks and vulnerabilities to climate change](#)

The [Hellenic National Meteorological Service](#), the [Ministry of Rural Development and Food](#), the [Institute of Mediterranean Forest Ecosystems and Forest Products Technology](#), the [National Observatory of Athens](#), the [Hellenic National Platform for Disaster Risk Reduction](#) (coordinated by the General Secretariat for Civil Protection) and a number of national research centres are involved in climate observation in Greece. The NAS is developed based on a vulnerability assessment conducted by the Climate Change Impacts Study Committee (CCISC) in 2011 that was developed based on simulations of projected future climate change impacts. The NAS contains adaptation actions per sector. It is expected that the RAAPs identify any additional regional and sectoral needs.

Monitoring implementation

Continuous monitoring of the effectiveness of implemented regional adaptation actions is expected through each RAAP, while the Central Union of Greek Municipalities and the Union of Greek Regions will respond to the NCCAC, which has the principal responsibility to monitor national climate change adaptation progress. Each RAAP will develop an indicator-based monitoring and evaluation system to allow for this continuous monitoring system to take place (OECD, 2020).

The NAS and RAAPs will be evaluated and revised every decade (at least). The NCCAC will also monitor and evaluate the NAP provide policy recommendations, as well as legislative and other possible measures and actions. Stakeholders will be engaged to develop, monitor, evaluate and review the NAS and RAAPs.⁶

Building capacity and disseminating knowledge

The adaptation governance in Greece can be considered to represent a bottom-up approach (EC, 2018) – where regions are responsible for the vulnerability assessments, monitoring, in addition to policy development and funding acquisition. Data on adaptation is currently not publicly available, and funding is currently sought by the MoEE to develop a National Adaptation Knowledge Hub (building on the experience of France and Spain), in addition to increasing capacity building and training programmes that would be accessible to interested stakeholders. Such platforms could boost collaboration between regions and relevant target groups.

Thanks to an eight-year long EU LIFE project entitled [AdaptInGR](#): Boosting the Implementation of Adaptation Policy across Greece, MoEE sought to improve administrative and financial capacity in response to climate change adaptation. AdaptInGR will contribute to the development of a monitoring and evaluation framework, among other tasks. The MoEE and National Centre for Environment and Sustainable Development will take over the work of the project upon its completion (including training, monitoring and information-sharing responsibilities).

1.2. Description of solutions in TransformAr

Description of the solutions

In TransformAr project MOE will build a series of solutions that work together complementary towards climate awareness and adaptation of MOE and its citizens (see *Figure 3*). MOE solutions comprise of data collection from various sources, analysis and post-processing of the data and feedback the outcomes to the citizens and promote climate awareness or utilize them for evidence informed climate adaptation policy suggestions at local municipality level. The *Table 1* presents each solution of TransformAr for MOE.

Table 1: Description of MOE solution within TransformAr project

Solution	Description
<i>Smart Climate Station - SCS</i>	MOE focuses on the installation of 21 Smart Climate Stations (SCS) around key areas of the city. The purpose of the SCSs is to gather real-time data regarding the micro-climate of the city, supporting the public administration office to ready the citizens in case of climate emergencies. After careful consideration and design, the key areas have been identifies and the SCSs will begin their operation during the timeline of this demo. SCS will register Temperature, Relative Humidity, Atmospheric Pressure, CO2 (ppm), PM 2.5 /10 (ppm), Wind speed and Rainfall.
<i>Demand Social Analysis - DSI</i>	MOE provides a series of social/health services to the citizens. Due to climate change impact, the demand for such services, it is expected to

	changed. To prepare to supply the services without interruption and meet the future demand, a demand analysis for social services/infrastructures will be performed. The analysis will provide the data to plan an adaptation strategy by taking into account the supply and demand of social services of the future.
<i>Citizen App – CAE</i>	MOE will develop a mobile app for gathering and distributed information; (1) it will used to crowdsource data about climate awareness of citizens of MOE via questionnaire, (2) to disseminate TransformAr’s MOE solution to the public and (3) to provide notifications for climate related events
<i>Awareness module – AWAR</i>	MOE will develop and test a curriculum of 45 min for pupils between 16-18 years old related to climate change understanding and climate awareness
<i>Climate Innovation Hub – CIH</i>	MOE will upgrade a multi-purpose facility to Climate Innovation Hub by (a) create a permanent exhibition about climate change and TransformAr solutions of MOE, (b) demonstrate live the data streaming from SCS and the post-processing indicators and (c) organizing a series of events for promoting the climate innovation (e.g. datathons), thus, providing access to the MOE’s data and asking for innovative solutions for MOE’s climate related problems.

The design and development of the MOE’s ecosystem of solutions, is using SCS, CAE and DSI as data sources for weather, environmental, demographic and modelling result and AWAR, CAE and CIH as dissemination and communication frontends for the citizens of MOE. The management and analysis of the various types of dataset is accomplished with the support of NCSR.D. The development of every solution is planned to have been fully deployed until 9/2024 with monitoring of impacts to be continued until the end of the project and beyond (see *Table 2*).

Table 2: Timeline of implementation of MOE solutions

Solution	Timeline
SCS	10/2023 - Acquisition of Commercial and Custom SCSs 11/2023 - Installation of SCSs in the pre-determined locations 12/2023 - Demo use of the SCSs
DSI	9/2023 – Finalizing of mapping infrastructure and services 12/2023 – Start analysis (downscale E3M dataset for Attica) 9/2024 – Finish analysis
CAE	6/2023 – Contract signed with subcontractor 11/2023 – Version Alpha of the app
AWAR	3/2023 – Curriculum for school developed 6/2023 – Presentation to MOE pupils 10/2023 – Planning event for 2024
CIH	6/2022 – Developed concept

10/2022 – Performed awareness workshop to local stakeholder

10/2023 - Planning event for 2024 and disseminate results of TransformAr of MOE

Weather and environmental data are used by NCSRd to be fused with daily weather forecast and produce a high-resolution weather forecast for the region of MOE. In addition, NCSRd will provide the data management techniques to clean, process and visualize the environmental data. DSI analysis will utilize the infrastructure and services data of MOE and the statistical methods NCSRd in order to take the results of E3M socio-economic model and downscale the information to the municipality level.

The post-processed information, alongside the results of crowdsourced data (questionnaires) and demand analysis will be disseminate via CAE directly to MOE citizens, part will be used in the climate awareness in pupils (AWAR) and the MOE TransformAr dataset will available in CIH alongside the permanent climate exhibition and live data streaming.

Figure 3 illustrates the coupling of MOE solutions and the flow of information from data sources to communication channels.

Figure 3: Illustration of MOE solution working complementary to each other

Description the expected innovation

The expected innovation of MOE's solutions can be categorized in three groups; (a) the streaming dataset comprised of different types, formats and resolution (CAE, SCS, DSI, post-processed information), unique for a municipality, (b) the fusion and use of the data for evidence-informed policy suggestions, alongside raising awareness at citizen (CAE, AWAR) level and promote innovation (CIH) and (c) the replicability and transferability of the MOE's ecosystem of solutions, as the main concept (Data, Analysis, Act (see

Figure 1)) can be followed with different component and under the same scope.

1.3. Expected impacts

Overview of the expected impacts

The expected impacts per solution can be found in *Table 3*. The impacts are either direct, thus, they deriving directly from the solution, or indirect, thus, they support the impacts of other solutions or long-term actions beyond TransformAr lifetime and scope.

Table 3: Description of expected impacts per solution

Solutio n	Expected impact
SCS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> (a) The data will provide a detailed dataset for weather and environmental conditions at MOE that will be visualized in Citizen Application Engagement (CAE) solution and disseminate part of the result to the citizens of MOE towards climate awareness in a large (municipality) level. (b) The data will be used by the NCSR (technical partner of MOE) to support the climate and environmental research of the organization and provide back to MOE a localized and high-resolution weather forecast of 120 hours for the area of MOE. The forecast data will be used directly as an alarm system to inform the relevant Municipality Departments (Civil Protection, Municipal Police) and other First-Responders when abnormal temperature levels or precipitation levels are noted, helping to prevent casualties and loss of musicality social services. (c) Beyond the MOE TransformAr solution, the SCS data collection will be used to monitor the effectiveness of different actions and measures implemented in MOE by comparison the measurement and relevant indicators before and after the implementation, thus, helping in quantify policy suggestion and making.
DSI	Forecasting the changes of demand for social services due to climate change, will enable the MOE to plan how the supply of social services will be maintain by meeting the demand and adapt on the new climate conditions and extreme events, such as more intense and frequent heatwaves.
CAE	As CAE provides a two-way channel of communication between MOE and citizens, it is expected to impact not only the citizen understanding of climate change, but also to provide a way to MOE to monitoring the impact of other TransformAr solution either directly (questionnaires with direct reference to specific solutions) or indirectly (overall quantification of climate awareness).
AWAR	AWAR is expected to impacted the climate change understanding of young people and try to clear misconceptions of what is climate change, what are the impacts, how it can be tackled etc. As such, it is aspired to create a more climate awared generation that pursuit for mitigation and adaptation through the municipality scale and/or social transformation.

CIH

CIH consist of (i) a static climate exhibition that is expected present the climate actions of MOE to the public; (ii) a dynamic part of livestreaming and visualization of the different types of data that are gathered and processed at MOE and both it is expected to impact people visiting the exhibition by raising the climate awareness. In addition, the availability of the dataset to SMEs, groups and teams via events (e.g. datathons) is expected to promote innovation and solutions for climate related problems that MOE has or will have in the future.

Dominant Indicators

For quantify the expected impacts of the TransformAr solutions in MOE, a series of Key Performance indicators (KPI) were selected and can be found in 1.5. ANNEX – KPI used by MOE per **solution**. The data to assess the KPIs will be based on information gathered via the data source solution (SCS, CAE, DSI) and data available to MOE via open databases national or international. As it was mentioned, the main scope of MOE solutions in to raise awareness to citizens and informed how to react in a rare climate driven even, thus, enhance behavioral change. Indicators that will measure the direct impacts of the solutions are:

- the analysis of questionnaires from CAE,
- the virtual visitors of CAE,
- the visitors of CIH exhibition,
- the number of participants in various events of AWAR and CIH

At the same time, the data collected can support the policy actions of MOE by evidence-informed decisions at the local level. As such, the impact KPIs can indirectly be assessed in long-term and they are mainly based on how the status of living and health and social indicators are changing.

Baseline data

The data to assess the direct impacts of MOE's solutions are coming from collections of data of measures people that attended events or the post-processing of the questionnaires. In order to see the effectiveness, a first batch of questionnaires have been already collected (early 2022) that will work as the baseline of climate understanding of citizens of MOE. In addition, questionnaires before events and after will be used, to assess the immediate quality of different actions and in average the change of climate awareness of MOE citizens.

Approach to monitor impacts

For the direct information and impacts of the solutions, the monitoring will be through the CAE and automatic calculation of indicators that can be found in 1.5. ANNEX – KPI used by MOE per **solution**

Availability and access of monitored data

All the data will be stored in a server at MOE premises. NCSR D will be gathering a copy of all data to perform analysis, post-processing and visualisation. The NCSR D outcomes will be forwarded to MOE server, for storing and they will be also stored at NCSR D premises alongside the original data. MOE and NCSR D server will be a copy of each other, thus, securing the availability and robustness of MOE dataset. All data or part of dataset will be available via events and upon submission of interest for specific scope and purpose.

Specifically for the indicators data of TransformAr solutions, they will available via CIH and CAE, and potentially to other outcomes of TransformAr project (e.g. TADA - https://mssg.ipta.demokritos.gr/transformar_tools_repo/)

1.4. Work in the upcoming months

In the upcoming months the MOE will use the monitoring data, conduct simulations, on the status of the environment, design scenarios of Climate Change contribution, assess impacts and provide mitigation measures, together with a policy plan for 2030

1.5. ANNEX – KPI used by MOE per solution

To evaluate the effectiveness and outreach of the climate adaptation solutions implemented in the Municipality of Egaleo, a dedicated set of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) was developed. These indicators were selected to reflect both the immediate outputs and long-term impacts of each solution under the TransformAr framework.

The KPIs are directly connected to the data gathered from smart climate stations (SCS), citizen engagement via the app (CAE), social demand analysis (DSI), awareness-raising modules (AWAR), and the climate innovation hub (CIH). They allow the municipality and its partners to monitor technical performance, behavior change, community participation, and alignment with policy planning needs.

Each KPI has been designed to:

- Reflect the specific context and vulnerabilities of Egaleo,
- Capture cross-cutting impacts (health, infrastructure, environment, economy),
- Enable tracking of solution scalability and replicability,
- Support data-informed decision-making processes.

These KPIs are grouped by solution type and include both quantitative metrics (e.g. real-time data accuracy, participation rates) and qualitative outcomes (e.g. increased climate literacy, policy integration). Baseline data collected since 2022 provides a reference point for measuring progress throughout and beyond the TransformAr project timeline.

Moreover, the KPI system contributes input data to the TransformAr Avoided Damages Application, allowing estimation of long-term socio-economic benefits derived from implemented adaptation measures. Selected indicators are also expected to feed into WP6 methodologies for cost-benefit assessment and decision-support models, ensuring coherence across evaluation, planning, and upscaling.

The indicators should serve both formative and summative purposes — supporting adaptive management during implementation and enabling ex post assessment of project outcomes.

The KPI system includes:

- Metrics capturing citizen engagement and behavioral change (e.g. app usage frequency, engagement rates in participatory events),
- Environmental performance indicators (e.g. urban heat mitigation, air quality from smart climate stations),
- Institutional outcomes (e.g. integration of data into municipal planning via CIH), and

- Synergy indicators (e.g. co-benefits across green infrastructure and community innovation).

Each indicator is grounded in a robust data collection protocol with source identification (SCS, CAE, DSI), frequency of measurement, and target values where applicable. Additional attention was given to triangulation of data (e.g. cross-verification between app analytics and on-the-ground surveys), in line with WP5's multi-source evaluation methodology.

Solution	Expected impact	Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)	Source/Measurement Approach
Smart Climate Stations (SCS)	The use of the SCS network will increase the knowledge and quantify the local climatic conditions. Data will be used for planning adaptation solutions.	Number of SCS installed in key municipal locations	Station deployment tracking
	Increase climate change awareness both for policy makers and citizens.	Real-time microclimate data accuracy	Data comparison with baseline climate models
	Increase adaptive capability of MOE	Percentage of data integrated into municipal decision-making	
Citizen App (CAE)	Increase citizen engagement and awareness	Number of registered users and active participants	App analytics tracking
	Increase citizen engagement and awareness	Public engagement through app feedback and surveys	
Awareness-Raising Modules (AWAR)	Increasing students' awareness is expected to have a dramatic positive effect in the long term, leading to an increase in proactive citizens focused on climate adaptation.	Number of students trained through awareness sessions	Attendance records
	Increasing students' awareness is expected to have a dramatic positive effect in the long term, leading to an increase in proactive citizens focused on climate adaptation.	Increase in climate literacy among students (measured via pre/post surveys)	Survey-based impact assessment

	Increase the hands-on experience of students to understand and analyse climatic data, as well as increase their understanding of the need for actionable solutions.	Number of workshops conducted	
Climate Innovation Hub (CIH)	Increase the collaboration with other EU projects and initiatives that take place in the same demonstration area.	Number of climate-related projects initiated	Event participation tracking
	Increase climate change and adaptation awareness.	Public attendance in innovation events (e.g., datathons, hackathons)	
Demand Analysis for Social Services (DSI)	Understand the effect of climate change on Social Services and their needs for adaptation.	Number of social services evaluated for climate resilience	Social services data analysis
	Short and long-term planning or adapting Social Services to the climate change.	Forecast accuracy of demand changes due to climate impacts	Municipality action plan integration
	Evaluate the effectiveness of TransformAr as a project to identify and promote actionable solutions for climate-proofing Social Services.	Percentage of recommendations adopted by local policymakers	

KPI table note : Each KPI in the updated table is linked to specific TransformAr solutions (SCS, CAE, DSI, AWAR, CIH) and describes measurable outputs relevant to both short-term awareness impacts and long-term policy relevance. Indicators have been aligned with data flows and monitoring timelines, including citizen participation rates, behavioral survey results, and environmental measurements for local policy design. These KPIs were selected to ensure replicability and scalability across other Mediterranean urban areas.

2.0. Galicia – MRM/IR/INTERM

Executive summary

The current report outlines the context and the ongoing solutions within one of the 6 demonstrators of the TransformAr project, the Galician demonstrator. Additionally, it addresses the expected impact, impact indicators, and their monitoring procedures.

The Galician demonstrator focuses on **adapting shellfish aquaculture and harvesting to the challenges posed by climate change**. The activity has been selected due to its significant role in the regional economy and its susceptibility to climate change, as outlined in the Galician Climate Change Strategy 2050 and in the Integrated Regional Plan for Energy and Climate (2019-2023).

Mussel aquaculture, accounting for approximately 40% of the European aquaculture production, is a vital sector employing nearly 4,000 individuals in the region. Similarly, **clam culture farms and shellfish harvesting** along coastal land concessions and intertidal sandbanks, directly employ around 4,300 people, with approximately 90% being self-employed women.

Key climate-related threats affecting shellfish aquaculture include the potential intensification of extreme weather events, unpredictable fluctuations in mussel seed availability, and the expected increase in harmful algal blooms and acidification. Also, changes in coastal oceanographic and hydrological factors will alter the sedimentary composition of shellfish banks, impacting shellfish productivity and mortality. In extreme cases, this could result in the loss of these habitats.

Within TransformAr, three solutions are tested to comprehensively grasp the nature of these changes and bolster adaptation to climate change:

- **Resilience Index (RI)** for the Galician mussel aquaculture. Developed by UVIGO-REDE, provides insight into operational risks scenarios caused by the effects of climate change and identifies the resilience factors available for adaptation. This index is built through the gathering of context information and consultation with experts and stakeholders on the one hand, and modelling of data on the other hand. This knowledge empowers practitioners and policymakers to informed decision-making and define efficient strategies for enhancing the operational resilience of the Galician mussel aquaculture.
- **Intertidal Monitoring (INTERM)**: The sedimentological knowledge increase and the application of an up-to-date morphodynamic model by UVIGO-GEOMA, enhances our understanding of the intertidal sandbank response to climate change. It provides valuable insight for adapting production in the face of changing environmental conditions.
- **Mussel Raft Monitoring (MRM)**: CETMAR has pioneered the digitalization of mussel rafts to enable real-time production monitoring. This tool's design and implementation has been carried out in close collaboration with mussel production stakeholders, adapting to their needs. It focuses on the collection of extensive real-time data from mussel rafts to optimise the management of mussel production, particularly in response to climate-related challenges.

The **innovation** of these solutions lies in the development and application of digital and technological solutions to be provided to the shellfish aquaculture and harvesting sector in Galicia. These solutions aim to provide real-time data, improve understanding of environmental responses, and enhance the efficiency and resilience of these industries to better adapt to climate change. **The main impacts will be** the improved understanding of the problematic, the awareness about climate change effects on the sector and the satisfaction of the solutions contribution, at the two key community systems involved: the clam sector and the mussel industry. This will be **assessed** mainly with indicators informing on the performance of the solutions and the participation, perception, involvement, and interest of key sectoral stakeholders.

2.1. Context

Infographic

Preliminary Infographic that we'll be improved for communication and transference purposes in 2024.

Figure 1. Visual scheme of the Galician demonstrator and the solutions being tested

Background & objectives

Galicia is one of the most significant fishing regions within the European Union. Within Galician fisheries, mussel and clam aquaculture systems play a vital role in the regional economy, influencing a wide range of activities including the processing and commercialization sector, the canning industry, shipbuilding, and tourism. Tourists partake in various activities such as dining on seafood, participating in gastronomic tours, and paying for boat trips and fishing excursions.

Marine aquaculture and shellfish harvesting occur in coastal facilities on land or in marine areas considered as inland waters, known as "Rías". On the one hand, the mussel aquaculture sector directly employs over 4,000 individuals in the region. This industry faces climate-related threats such as adverse impacts from extreme weather events on mussel raft structures, the availability of mussel seeds, and harmful algal blooms. On the other hand, clam farming takes place in the coastal sandbanks (numbering more than 600), with shellfish harvesting on foot involving approximately 3,500 self-employed individuals collecting bivalves and polychaetes on beaches and intertidal sandbanks. Notably, 90% of these harvesters are women. Because of Climate Change, coastal oceanographic and hydrological conditions are expected to alter the sediment characteristics of shellfish banks, reducing shellfish productivity and increasing mortality. In extreme cases, this could lead to the loss of these habitats.

To confront these challenges, communities find it challenging to understand what currently exists, what is required and what is feasible in terms of adapting to CC. In numerous workshops and sector meetings, it has been asserted that timely and open data communication is essential for informed and efficient decision-making. This, in turn, boosts project feasibility and shapes citizen behaviour. Embracing digital and technological innovations, alongside streamlined management systems, could yield swifter, more efficient responses to extreme events. This, in essence, could mitigate climate-related damage, all while taking budgetary limitations into careful consideration.

Objectives

The objective of the Galician demonstrator is to drive a region-specific adaptive transformational adaptation process for the clam and mussel sectors, responding to the prevailing multi-sectoral climate risks. The table 1 correlates the solutions developed by the Galicia demonstrator with the specific objectives they contribute to.

Table 4. Specific objectives in relation to solutions demonstrated

Specific objectives	MRM	RI	INTERM
Improve the understanding of the regional oceanographic environment and test tools that will contribute to the effective use of this information.	X		X
Engage with stakeholders and increase the awareness and the perception of risks to address territorial vulnerabilities linked to CC.	X	X	X

Facilitate the integration of Internet of Things and Artificial Intelligence to bring digitalisation and automation strategies to the shellfish sector.	X		
Provide policymakers with decision-making support tools to define actions and a roadmap for enhancing resilience.		X	X
Showcase the efficacy of solutions in bolstering resilience within the mussel and clam sector in Galicia and ascertain their potential for replication.	X	X	X
Derive a set of recommendations and measures including an appealing document, by using the tools delivered.	X	X	X

Geographical description

Deliverable 1.2 of the TransformAr project provides a detailed and comprehensive explanation of the geographical characteristics of Galicia. This section offers only a summary to contextualise the demonstrator and the solutions.

Galicia (6.4 - 9.6°W, 41.5 - 44.2°N) is located in the North Atlantic region, in the Northwest quarter of Spain. The region covers 29,576 km², representing 5.8% of Spanish territory, with a coast line of 1,659 km (32.8% of the Spanish coastline). The intricate Atlantic coast of Galicia is mainly characterised by the presence of multiple coastal inlets known as Rías. Their geomorphology and circulation favour the efficient use of the nutrients transported by the upwelling process in spring and summer, and provide protection against autumn and winter storms, conditions that make Galicia an exceptional site for the mussel aquaculture on hanging ropes and bivalve extraction in sandbanks. In particular, the Ria de Arousa, the largest bay inlet in the southwest coast, appears as the most productive area with 70% of the mussel rafts and 50% clam sales ((Xunta de Galicia, 2021a).

Galicia is located in the transition from the temperate to the subpolar regimes of the North Atlantic, which, among other factors, makes it particularly sensitive to the predicted CC. Its consequences in the regional oceanography systems and the consequent socio economic impact remains under evaluation.

The territory of Galicia is home to 56 types of habitats of community interest, with 10 of them being considered as priorities. According to the data extracted from the “Master Plan of the Natura 2000 Network” prepared in 2012 by the regional government Xunta de Galicia (Ramil-Rego et al., 2012), 12.7% of the territory of Galicia is considered a Site of Community Interest (SCI) and 3.4% corresponds to Areas of Special Protection for Birds (SPAs), which are usually part of SCIs. Galicia’s regional population includes some 2.7 million people. The region has developed a Galician Climate Change Strategy 2050, and an Integrated Regional Plan for Energy and Climate for the period 2019-2023 which is meant to guide the implementation of the strategy.

Figure 2. Study area – Ria de Arousa – Galicia -Spain

Climate vulnerability, impacts and challenges

According to the European Environment Agency (EEA, 2017a), the region of Galicia is at risk of more frequent and intense winter storms that will lead to an increasing risk of coastal infrastructure damage and heavy precipitation events, which in conjunction with sea level rise, could lead to more intense riverine and coastal floods. Recent research have shown how variations in regional oceanographic conditions (e.g. increase in temperature, changes in upwelling-favourable coastal winds and precipitation regimes), the alteration of nutrient fertilisation patterns (Sousa et al., 2020, FuentesSantos et al., 2021), presence of invasive species or new pathogens, as well as potential increase in harmful algal bloom (HAB) episodes (Álvarez-Salgado et al.; 2008, Pérez et al., 2010), can pose threats to which the aquaculture sector needs to adapt (Cramp et al., 2021).

Galicia faced a series of severe weather events in the past, including storms, droughts, wildfire and heatwaves. For example, in 2003 the temperatures in Galicia exceeded the 95th percentile of the maximum temperature, which impacted the mortality in the region; In 2002-2003 and 2013-2014, storm events significantly eroded beaches along the cost causing damage to infrastructures such as ports, ships, mussel rafts, and generated the inability to work at sea (small-scale fisheries, mussel aquaculture, shellfish harvesting activities). The region also witnessed one of its worst droughts in the last hundred years in 2016-2017 (Khamis et al., 2022), with an overall decrease in rainfall by about 500 mm, magnifying a series of wildfires that destroyed a total of 43,000 hectares, with consequences in soil erosion and sediment contribution to the Rías through the river discharge.

During the years 2002 and 2023, nineteen bilateral meetings and two workshops were held with key actors to discuss the adaptation of the Galician clam and mussel sector to climate change (CC), as part of the TransformAr activity “Development of a shared vision for a future resilient to climate change”. These sessions substantiated that the local stakeholders' perception of climate change hazards aligns with scientific observations and recent observed events. In order of importance, they selected as main hazards fluctuations in salinity and river discharge, followed by the consistent rise in sea surface temperatures, changes in wind patterns and upwelling, and an escalation in the frequency and intensity of extreme winter events (e.g., waves and storms). Participants highlighted habitat alteration, the introduction of invasive species or alterations in existing populations, and erosion or modification of sedimentary banks as the principal risks directly associated with CC.

The impact of the above-mentioned risks could lead to higher pressure on the supply chain and the work culture (alterations in concessions, employment, social stress...). Adequate and economically viable adaptation measures are therefore needed to face these diverse challenges and increase the resilience of the sector. To face this demanding task, it is crucial to obtain longer data series and their analysis to support decision-making, propose tailor made strategies and apply specific adaptation actions suitable to the sector. Figure 2 summarises the hazards, exposure, vulnerability and risks to which the territory/sector is exposed to considering the results of the workshops.

Figure 3. Hazards, exposure, vulnerability and risks to which the Galician mussel-clam sector is exposed

Legislative background

The Spanish Policy and Institutional Framework on Climate Change Adaptation

Adaptation Governance at the National Level

The first Spanish [National Climate Change Adaptation Plan](#) (PNACC) was adopted in 2006 and was in force until 2020. The current PNACC is in force from 2021 to 2030 and is implemented through a series of work programmes targeted to priority areas. The PNACC is the Spanish public administration's [reference framework](#) to address adaptation through action and tools for assessment in the sectors known to be most affected, including the water management sector, agriculture, forests, biodiversity, coasts, health and tourism.

Spain's national energy policies underline the importance of climate resilience. For instance, the [2020 National Energy and Climate Plan](#) highlights the need for resilience and CC adaptation in sectors such as water, transport infrastructure, forestry, and coastal and marine environments (IEA, 2021).

The Spanish Climate Change Office (OECC) – part of the Ministry for the Ecological Transition – oversees policymaking on adaptation. The National Climate Council makes recommendations, while the Coordination Commission of Climate Change Policies adopts adaptation plans and reports and coordinates action between national, regional and local levels. The PNACC was adopted after public consultation with public administration, civil society and interested sectors and parties.

Relevant National Spanish Policies

Five national policies address CC issues that are worth mentioning in the context of this project:

1. [Law 2/2013 on the protection and sustainable use of coastal areas](#):
2. [Royal Decree 903/2010, on the Assessment and Management of Flood Risk](#):
3. [Royal Decree No. 19/2016 - Flood risk management plan of the Galicia-Costa Hydrographic Demarcation](#):
4. [Royal Decree No. 425/2016 - Regulatory basis for the granting of subsidies from the General State Administration to Agrarian Insurance](#):
5. [Royal Decree 690/2021 regulating the Ecological Restoration and Resilience Fund](#):

Overall, these policies aim at protecting coastal areas, incorporating regulations to address CC effects by promoting their preservation and restoration. They also allow project cancellation in the case of risks of sea level rise and mandates the Ministry of Agriculture, Food and Environment to develop a coastal adaptation strategy. Moreover, multi-sectoral coordination and public participation is emphasised, aligning with existing regulations on civil protection. Lastly, the basis for granting subsidies for agrarian insurances are established, contributing to farmers' premium payments. In summary, these laws and regulations create the framework to develop actions on climate change mitigation and adaptation in coastal areas, enhancing climate resilience.

Adaptation Governance at the Regional Level

Every region in Spain, except for Asturias and Rioja, have adopted regional action plans or adaptation strategies, which covers 97 % of the Spanish population (EC, 2018). To date, 1922 municipalities are signatories to the [Covenant of Mayors for Climate and Energy](#).

Adaptation Governance at the Local Level

Several stakeholders support the actions outlined in Spain's national climate and energy plans. Locally, the Spanish Cities Network for Climate, which is a voluntary association of municipalities, supports climate action development and promotion through the establishment of adaptation strategies and plans. At the same time, the OECC co-authored guidelines for preparing local CC adaptation plans prepared in 2015 (IEA, 2021).

Measuring Risks and Vulnerabilities to Climate Change

The measurement and analysis of atmospheric climate data is undertaken by the [Spanish Meteorological Agency](#) - AEMET, which follows the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) scenarios (latest AR5 scenarios). Together with Portugal, Spain also addresses transboundary risks and vulnerabilities surrounding issues of biodiversity, marine ecosystems and forestry that affect both countries. A project entitled "[Climate Change on the Spanish Coast](#)" - C3E, was coordinated by the University of Cantabria, on behalf of the OECC, and developed databases and tools to assess vulnerabilities and impacts, and eventually identify adaptation measures in coastal areas. The [Centro de Estudios y Experimentación de Obras Públicas](#) - CEDEX, has also carried out scenarios to monitor the impact of CC on water resources and droughts in Spain.

Monitoring implementation

Several monitoring reports tracked and evaluated the first PNACC. For instance, every three years a report is published by the OECC to assess its implementation. The contents of these reports include focus on the work done on adaptation in various sectors, as well as regions through factsheets and checklists.

In Galicia there is a Strategy for CC and energy 2050 and the Integrated Regional Plan for Energy and Climate (2019-2023). Galicia also integrates the Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change of the European Commission from September 2022.

Building capacity and disseminating knowledge

The [AdapteCCa](#) adaptation platform is a tool developed by the OECC to facilitate knowledge exchange for experts, institutions and interested parties on the impacts and vulnerabilities of CC and adaptation. Workshops are also organised by the OECC and the national centre for environmental education - CENEAM, to gather researchers, policymakers, as well as civil society to develop solutions for CC adaptation. The [CLIVAR-Spain scientific committee](#) publishes assessment reports that list Spanish research groups involved in monitoring and measuring CC impact and adaptation in Spain¹

At this point, it should be mentioned the [Xunta de Galicia Coastal Observatory](#)², which is understood as a strength in the context of CC. For more than a decade, it has offered ocean-meteorological information on the Galician coast, being very useful for research, decision-making by administrations,

¹ See the [Spanish fiche for the EU adaptation preparedness scoreboard](#) and the [Climate ADAPT portal](#) for further details.

²For more information see: <https://marnaraia.org/>

and the development of ecosystem services related to the blue economy and coastal protection, including CC indicators.

2.2. Description of solutions in TransformAr

Resilience Index (RI)

The REDE research group at the University of Vigo is **undertaking the development of a mathematical model, the Operational Resilience Index (RI), for the mussel farming sector** that aims to nudge stakeholders' behavioural change. This index (framed within the project's governance solutions) provides stakeholders (STK) and policymakers with a comprehensive assessment tool and a decision-making assistance instrument that will allow them, on one hand, to identify strategic focal points for adapting the mussel farming production operations to the effects caused by CC and, on the other, to establish which measures can have the greatest impact on reducing the risk of business interruption.

As illustrated in figure 4, the development of the Operational RI employs a hybrid methodology that integrates climate data and scenarios with input from experts and STH. This process unfolds across three different phases, of which the first one and part of the second one have been implemented to date:

1) Identification of relevant experts and STH, followed by the **collection of three sets of variables** to be used throughout the index construction: (i) data about the aquaculture processes, (ii) climatic variables that could affect those processes and their projections and (iii) the available resilience factors with the potential to moderate the impact of the selected climate elements on critical processes.

2) During the second phase, the Delphi methodology was employed to engage experts and STH in a participatory and consensus-building process. As a result, vulnerabilities, risks and resilience factors within the mussel aquaculture production have been prioritized. The participants in both Delphies possess expertise related to mussel aquaculture, climate change, and/or resilience. Furthermore, the quintuple helix (Carayannis et al., 2012) has been represented in the expert panels, encompassing Administration, Academia, Productive sector, Environmental organizations and Society. A total of 23 experts took part in the first Delphi (July 2023), while 20 experts participated in the second one (October 2023). The outcomes facilitated the identification of priority risk scenarios and resilience gaps, respectively.

As a final step of the second phase, a questionnaire will be designed and distributed to STH to **assess the key resilience factors**, that is, the adaptive capacities of the sector.

3) The final phase will encompass the definition of the mathematical model (fed with the variables identified in phase 2 and the values from the capacities questionnaire) and **the calculation of RI scores**. Finally, **the definition of proposals for improving adaptation** will be discussed with STH in order to define a strategic roadmap.

Figure 4. Methodological design for the Operational Resilience Index

The RI represents a tool for evaluating the level of adaptability in the operations of the mussel production process. Figure 5 shows a draft of how the final result will be represented after calculation of the synthetic index of the resilience factor (the figures are fictitious until the final results by March 2024).

We chose to design a composite index with indicators (synthetic index) because **such a tool simplifies the communication, turning complex information into understandable metrics**, more accessible to a wider audience. Therefore, the RI evaluation will encompass an overall score and a detailed breakdown across five dimensions: Governance, R+D+I, Collaboration, Risk Management, and Operational Environment. Additionally, each dimension is further dissected into four factors, totalling 20 resilience factors.

The dashboard of final scores combines multiple dimensions and factors into a single global metric. It takes into account multiple factors providing a more nuanced understanding of the overall state of the sector. It considers the interaction between the impact level of different risk scenarios and the ability of the identified resilience factors to adapt to their effects. In addition, the index assigns different weights to resilience factors based on the relative importance that experts attribute to each risk scenario. This weighting allows a more nuanced and realistic reflection of the importance of each element in influencing the overall index.

The results emerging from the index will provide specific insights that will allow the formulation of actions and a roadmap for enhancing resilience.

Figure 4. Draft presentation of the results of the synthetic Resilience Index (the numbers are fictitious until final calculation).

Intertidal Monitoring – INTERM

The GEOMA Research group from the University of Vigo implements a **sedimentological monitoring of sandbanks at specific locations of clam exploitation** with the aim to improve the knowledge of the sediment dynamics, the stability of the ecosystem substratum, and its response to the predicted Climate Change outcome. An updated understanding will improve STH and policymakers basis for adequate adaptation solutions, efficient management currently hindered by the lack of information.

This solution directly responds to two aspects in the nature of the sandbanks substrate understanding:

1. The **sedimentological context** of the Galician intertidal sandbanks, specifically what drives their morphology and how their sediments seasonally behave, and the potential relationship with changes in shellfish productivity.
2. **Consequences of the Climate Change** on the Galician sandbanks terrain. Although we know that environmental variations alter the morphology and composition of the intertidal sediments (e.g. Friederichs 2011) potentially altering the ecosystem, few studies have undertaken this issue at the regional level.

Within this context, selection of study-case locations was performed after discussion with local shellfishers and scientific community involved, trying to respond to the observed variable historical productivity of commercial clams and arising sedimentological concerns. To fit our evaluation in the time frame of the project, the "space for time" hypothesis has been assumed, selecting three areas on the south margin of the Ría de Arousa, with different geological configuration and levels of shellfish productivity.

The INTERM solution has a threefold mission:

1. **Intertidal Monitoring:** Based on previous and ongoing STH efforts currently used for sediment management strategies, a systematic monitoring has been carried out to obtain seasonally updated datasets along the duration of the project. Starting in month 13 (October 2022), sediment properties (grain size distribution, organic matter content, geochemical composition, etc.), terrain elevation datasets and oceanographic parameters influencing the area dynamics are being surveyed.
2. **Morphodynamic Modelling:** A model set up is being configured and validated on the DELFT3D package (Deltares, The Netherlands) for a regional level domain where the tide is the main hydrodynamic factor. Sediment transport under different bathymetric conditions, tidal currents, and river discharge variations are evaluated using the modules FLOW and MOR. An orthogonal grid is established and refined towards the selected intertidal sandbanks, incorporating external datasets for deep bathymetry, but obtained higher resolution depth and sediment composition for the selected shallow sandbanks. Simulations depend on the boundary conditions defined for tide, river and water surface. Currently, the model set-up needs to be validated, contrasting the results with ongoing monitored and public stations data, to allow the exploration of regional CC scenarios with variable hydrodynamic conditions. We expect to describe whether the selected sandbanks lose or gain sediment, as well as their sediment texture variations, that might avoid some species growth.
3. **Knowledge transfer:** The compiled information, including the generated datasets and predicted scenarios, will be analysed and processed to finally return to the clam sector in a way that will contribute to improve the sandbank monitoring guidelines, and to be the basis to co-create and purpose management strategies of harvested sandbanks against the CC. The planning, methodology and lessons learnt of the process will be available to guide similar processes in equivalent areas.

Figure 5. INTERM strategy scheme.

Mussel Raft Monitoring - MRM

The Technological Centre of the Sea – CETMAR, is carrying out the development of a **pilot case of digitalization of the mussel aquaculture**. The conditions of the marine environment and the production are being monitored in active mussels' farms, for the improvement of the exploitations management, **with the support and collaboration of its owners**.

The first comprehensive monitoring of a mussel raft in the Galician rías was conducted at the physical variables level in the framework of the ESSMA project (Ecological Sustainability of Suspended Mussel Aquaculture), funded by the Spanish Ministry of Science and Innovation (Aguiar et al., 2015). This study suggested that it was necessary a revision of the ecological concepts, such as food depletion and/or reduction in water flow, based on idealized linear flows through the rafts. This included the consideration of the "clearance" area, defined as the area affected by non-linear effects produced by the raft itself and its surrounding rafts. These conclusions were supported by the results obtained through a near real-time monitoring of a raft, during more than a year and a half, in the Lorbé polygon of the Ría de Ares and Betanzos (NW Galicia, Spain). The digitalization in this case involved the installation of four currentmeters and four turbidimeters/fluorometers placed on each side of the raft that recorded data in a self-contained way. Simultaneously, the position and orientation of the raft were also recorded in real time. The autonomy of this raft was limited by energy requirements because most of the equipment had batteries not powered by solar panels. This intricates recurrent battery changes and, consequently, numerous visits to the raft.

In this case, the solution developed in TransformAr includes the **monitoring of environmental, and production parameters** (currently in two mussel-rafts), **based on the implementation of IoT solutions powered by solar energy**. Besides, the remote visualisation of the data on an internet-based platform is also being developed, presenting the information for production management.

A key aspect is the reception and feedback from workers in the sector, paying attention to their opinions and suggestions for improvement or adaptation of the installation to their interests.

Figure 6 explains the logic and the sequence of the data gathered from the moment that the sensor captures them to the visualisation on the dashboard.

Figure 6. MRM flowchart

Next, it is shown the degree of execution of this solution in three phases as well as the time frame:

- **The first phase** consists of a **system that monitors the basic parameters** and can validate the installation and the developments created expressly for its use on rafts. For this purpose, an **IN-SITU data storage installation was designed and installed in a raft to be tested** for a few months and make the necessary modifications to improve its robustness.

At the same time, a **first analysis of the data** was carried out in order to optimize criteria in terms of storage capacity and frequency of data acquisition.

With all the lessons learned from the first phase, a new design of the installation architecture was made **to adapt it to a real-time data collection system**.
- **The second phase** develops the **communication protocols and the improvements** to be able to perform data acquisition autonomously and send the measurements to ground stations for further analysis. In addition to the oceanographic monitoring sensors, other meteorological sensors were added to complement and improve the sampling capability of the system installed in two mussel rafts.

Data analysis procedures are being improved as well as the characteristics of the huge amount of data received in real time.

The designed installation is feasible for the available infrastructure and resistant to the adverse conditions of the marine environment and has a high degree of autonomy, both in terms of energy and in the measurement and telematic transmission of monitored data, as well as having systems for detecting possible failures.
- **The third phase**, implemented in 2024, **will improve the data analysis systems and the necessary implementations to visualise the data in a user-friendly web platform**. This dashboard will show real time data, as well as all the data history of the variables that are being collected. It is intended

that data access and the visualisation are affordable for STH and useful in decision-making for more effective and sustainable management of resources.

To assess the feasibility of digitalization in the sector, the technical and economic aspects are analysed, as well as the impact of the implemented solutions, facilitating and promoting their replication and scalability in the sector. Although it is too early to be able to evaluate the actions or changes that can be carried out by workers in the sector after analysing the data provided, we already can assert that the information collected is interesting and adds value to the sector and their workers. By incorporating IoT technology into mussel raft monitoring, the shellfish industry can adapt to and mitigate the challenges presented by a changing climate while maintaining sustainable and profitable operations.

This effort contributes to the achievement of several objectives defined at National and Regional Climate Change Adaptation Plans. Specifically, it is aligned with the Integrated Regional Plan for Energy and Climate (2019-2023) for the development and implementation of the Galician Strategy for Climate Change and Energy 2050 in the lines of action: 11 - Consolidate an observation network as an instrument to improve monitoring, 14 - Promote the conservation and efficient use of natural resources, and 18 - Consolidate sustainable management of fishing and aquaculture that minimises the impacts of CC and guarantees the current positioning of the sector in the long term.

Expected Innovations

Each of the three solutions presented in point 3.1 is expected to generate new information for the demonstrator that will be transfer to a broader audience. In general terms it is expected that the demonstrator innovates on monitoring, technical and social aspects. Table 2 illustrates which solution results in the desired innovation field.

Table 5. Expected innovations.

Innovation	MRM	INTERM	RI
Innovation on monitoring	x	x	
Technical innovation	x	x	x
Awareness in climate change			x

RESILIENCE INDEX (RI)

The novelty of the RI in the Galicia demonstrator and its recognition in noteworthy publications and reports highlights its robustness and applicability. The RI development methodology and validation was documented by REDE research group in a 2021 publication in the Marine Policy journal (León-Mateos et al., 2021). Furthermore, this paper was cited in the Working Group II Sixth Assessment Report for the IPCC. **The RI first application took place in the A Coruña Port, Galicia (Spain).** However, the methodology used to create this synthetic index can be transferred to other sectors and regions. It is worth noting that such a decision-making **tool has never been implemented in the key community system (KCS) of the mussel aquaculture and it is unknown for actors involved in it.**

The innovative value of the RI solution in TransformAr is represented by the following factors:

- a) **Decision-Making assistance instrument.** The RI will play a crucial role in providing STH, managers, and policymakers with accessible and understandable information derived from diverse scientific fields not interconnected before. The main innovative factor involves the gathering of both quantitative and qualitative data belonging to different areas and transforming it into simple and easily interpretable metrics with a format that is user-friendly and enables informed and forward-looking decisions on where to concentrate their efforts.
- b) **Holistic assessment.** To maintain uninterrupted aquaculture operations and even foster the sector to grow as climate change becomes more apparent, holistic approaches to addressing climate change impacts are needed (Maulu et al., 2021). The RI will bridge that gap by providing a broad view on the level of adaptive capacity of mussel aquaculture by interconnecting risks, vulnerabilities, resilience factors, and actionable recommendations in the benefit of an informed decision-making.
- c) **Interdisciplinary approach.** To move forward long-term responses, incorporate governance initiatives that take into account different needs of STH, users, and culture ecosystems as a whole are required (Reid et al., 2019). Current tools for measuring resilience are often constrained, tend to adopt a partial perspective, biased toward environmental dimensions or neglect social and economic aspects (Maulu et al., 2021). The comprehensive involvement of all STH in formulating the index will mitigate the biases commonly associated with indicators that rely solely on the viewpoints of select parties.
- d) **Stakeholder engagement and dissemination.** The RI development involves active stakeholder participation not only in formulating the index but also in decision-making for strategic actions to enhance the sector's adaptive capacity. According to Engle & van Senten (2022) successful engagement through participatory approaches, including policy-makers, producers, local citizens, and other STH, is preferable over command-and-control methods. Responsible and sustainable aquaculture, guided by science-based regulations applied efficiently, holds the promise of improving community resilience.

INTERTIDAL MONITORING - INTERM

Whether the sediment data integration of the selected shellfish sandbanks relies on historical data collected by local fishermen's guilds and scientific or government institutions, the INTERM involves surveying at a temporal and regional scale never performed before in the region. The innovation of the INTERM can be then outlined in the following items:

- a) **Scientific / Monitoring Innovation.** Multiple efforts have recently been made to control and manage the intertidal sandbanks, however, in the recent years, there is a clear decrease in shellfish productivity (www.pescadegalicial.gal) which causes have not yet been identified. At a regional level, some studies have explored how climate affect the biophysical conditions for bivalve development, such as temperature and salinity (e.g. Des et al., 2021; Dominguez et al., 2021), however few work has been done regarding the ecosystem suspended sediment dynamics and substrate stability, which can be altered among other causes, due to variable climate dynamics. The INTERM solution aims to innovate in the direction to fill this lack of knowledge, exploring both the present day sediment dynamics by intertidal monitoring, and future response, by morphodynamic simulations.
- b) **Technical innovation in the evaluation of CC effects.** As an innovative technical solution, INTERM evaluates the CC affectation to the regional coast and marine environments of Galicia by the use of the state-of-the-art DELFT3D model package on its recently updated Flexible version. The evaluation of the sediment transport and morphodynamic evolution at this estuarine domain, and its consequences on bivalve ecosystems sustainability, through the MOR module of DELFT3D has

never been done. Additionally, no morphodynamic simulations were previously applied to the selected intertidal sandbanks, which are the most productive of Galicia, to study their morphological evolution climatic variable conditions. Therefore, the fine-tuning of the model for the confined coastal zone with irregular coastline and valuing sediment transport for changing hydrodynamic conditions represents an important innovation of the INTERM solution.

- c) **Innovation in science-society interactions and strategies:** INTERM will make an effort to improve shellfish harvesters' confidence in science and researchers as allies in the management of the banks, aiming to innovate following recent RRI guidelines contrasting traditional scientific work. For this, within the framework of the project, we aim to make the monitoring effort **profitable** by coordinating the efforts with the interests of the fishermen's associations in the measurement of mandatory indicators for the resource management plans.
- d) Additionally, in this context of up-to-date research directions, the monitoring of sandbanks has been designed keeping in mind that long time series of data cannot be supported by research projects with a fixed duration and will eventually have to be left to the fishermen's associations. Therefore, **methods** used in the project have been **adapted to facilitate continuation of sampling strategies**, replications, and main analysis, to those existing in these organisations, once the project ends.

MUSSEL RAFT MONITORING - MRM

CETMAR has extensive experience over the past 15 years in real-time monitoring of oceanographic and meteorological variables within the framework of the transborder RAIA Observatory. However, **monitoring a functioning mussel raft, represents a significant and pioneering leap**, involving the adaptation of digital measurement systems without disrupting the work of the mussel producers.

The digitalization of a mussel raft requires a different approach compared with traditional in-situ monitoring. The following aspects are being innovative in the mussel sector Galician industry:

- a) **Real-time Data Collection of environmental variables** through IoT systems that transmit data to a centralised platform. This enables immediate data analysis, offering timely insights into changing environmental conditions.
- b) **Remote Monitoring** reduces physical presence and helps ensuring the safety of personnel.
- c) **Data Analysis and Predictive Modelling.** Machine learning and data analytics help in identifying patterns and trends related to CC impacts on mussel farming. This information can be used for making informed decisions and the formulation of adaptive strategies.
- d) **Alerts and Notifications** when certain parameters reach critical levels. For instance, if water temperature exceeds a certain threshold, the mussel raft operators receive an alert, enabling immediate protective actions.
- e) **Historical Data Storage** that allows the creation of valuable long-term CC impact records for scientific research and policy development related to CC and its effects on mussel farming.
- f) **Energy Efficiency**, using low-power sensors and communication technologies. This ensures that monitoring operations do not place an excessive burden on power resources. Ongoing efforts are directed towards mitigating the effects of reduced solar radiation in Galicia during the autumn and winter seasons.
- g) **No interference in daily workers' tasks:** the installation has been designed to be integrated into the available infrastructure.

2.3. Expected impacts

Overview of the expected impacts

The overall impact is to **empower the sector with real-time data and predictive capabilities, improving operational efficiency and supporting sustainable and adaptive management practices to face the environmental changing conditions due CC.**

It is expected that the users will find the monitoring of their production activities more manageable and adaptable to the changing environmental conditions. This, in turn, may enable them to better plan their work and have a positive impact on their working conditions and safety.

The solutions that are being developed, are understood as a trial to study the feasibility of the digitalization of the sectors for a better adaptation to CC. Thus, the effectiveness of these tools will be gauged by the extent to which they are embraced and how satisfied users, including producers and scientists, are with them.

Furthermore, the aim of the demonstrator is that the insights derived from these tools facilitate STH and policymakers to identify strategic focal points for adapting to CC effects and make well-informed decisions to enhance the operational resilience of Galician mussel and clam aquaculture.

Table 6. Expected impacts of the solutions.

Expected impact	RI	INTERM	MRM
Knowledge increase and transfer about regional oceanographic environment	X	X	X
Availability of technically viable and effective digital-technological tools to address territorial vulnerabilities linked to CC.		X	X
Availability of decision-making support tools to define actions and a roadmap for enhancing resilience.	X		
Awareness rising and better perception of CC risks affecting the sector	X	X	X
Social acceptance and interest in replicating the solutions or any of the components developed	X	X	X
Governance and management measures	X	X	X

Project impact indicators, approach of monitoring

Prior to obtaining impact results, it is imperative to first gather data on the implementation of the solutions, such as identifying suitable data collection areas, securing producer agreements, installing sensors, ensuring sensor functionality, and the type of information obtained.

Then, the expected impacts of the solutions will be measured through the impact indicators as described in the Table 4. In this table, several columns have also been added to clearly display the baseline, the expected outcomes at the end of the project, the current situation, and the approach to monitoring indicators per impact (the type and format of verification sources). The table could be enhanced by providing more information for the next monitoring report.

The impact of these solutions will be closely monitored in accordance with project guidelines and, where feasible, aligned with other demonstrators. Overall, the increase in knowledge impact through the course of the project is measured by comparison between the obtained measurements from monitoring surveys and sensors and baseline existing data. It is assessed mostly based on user satisfaction (producers and scientists), technical and economic viability, awareness and behavioural change, and the potential for replication. The monitoring of these indicators is approached through workshops, meetings, testimonies of key informants, surveys and questionnaires. Reports of the involvement of the STH and communication and transfer activities will serve as verification sources, together with information about the data publication records and web/visor visualisations.

Table 7. Indicators to measure the expected impacts, linked to the baseline, the expected outcomes, the current situation, and the monitoring approach.

Expected impact	Indicators	Solution	Approach	Baseline	Achieved	Expected
Knowledge increase and transfer	Generation and dissemination of new outputs of knowledge related to CC management.	RI	Data publication records/report, web/visor views (Google analytics records), survey of STK using data.	-	2 outputs identified and distributed among STK: - 70 climate risk scenarios for the mussel aquaculture - 20 resilience factors, useful for facing the effects of climate change on mussel aquaculture	2
	Accessible and real time information on the effects of changing local environmental conditions on a real mussel raft (at high frequency)	MRM	Log of communication and transfer events, report of transfer workshops, minutes of meetings with 5 helix and bilateral meetings.	0	No data available yet	Access to the digital dashboard: 1 entry each 15 days
	Number of STH or institutions using data	INTE RM MRM		-	No data available yet	90% of engaged STK
	Km ² emerged topography (by foot)	INTE	0	0.36 Km ²		

		RM					
	Km ² submerged bathymetry	INTERM		0	2.78 km ²	7 km ²	
	Sediment Samples per Sandbank (by foot)	INTERM		4-5 sandbank/year	6-12 samples/ sandbank/ season (2023)		
	Current flow/ turbidity survey	INTERM		0	1 per sandbank	1	
	Nº Sandbanks with sediment dynamics experiments	INTERM		0		1 per sandbank	
	N of publications / new outputs of knowledge related to CC adaptation in the shellfish sector	All		-	-	4	
	N of transfer events / meetings	All		0	-	6	
	Engagement or participation in WS and transfer initiatives	All		-	-	-	
Technically viable and effective digital-tech. tools	Sandbanks completely monitored (1 year)	INTERM	Measurements (comparison before and after)	0	2	3	
	Increase in the Technology Readiness Level (TRL) scale in the mussel sector (digitalisation and automation)	MRM	Report/video of the solution	TRL4 Validated under laboratory-scientific conditions	-	TRL6 Demonstrated in relevant env. (beginning	

						TRL7 System prototype demonstration in operational env.)
	Availability of technically viable and effective digital-technological tools	INTERM MRM	Reports, videos and links to the dashboard	-	-	2 new solutions
Awareness rising and better perception of CC	Perception improvement about the need of a decision-making assistance tool for CC adaptation	RI	Reports of the workshops, testimonies, key informants and surveys pre- and post-implementation	-	-	Positive answer to the survey
	Increase in the awareness about the risk affecting shellfish culture and the availability of adaptation measures	All		-	-	80% of the STK engaged
Social acceptance and interest in replication	Expensive commercial sensors replacement with COTS	MRM	Report, STK survey	-	-	-
	Interest in replicating the solution or any of the components developed	MRM	Expressions of interest for replication or install sensors (Emails, official request forms, meeting minutes)	0	-	3 solutions
	Participatory engagement	All	Reports, participation lists	-	72 (from 43 organisations)	80 actors 20 Fishers

					24 Fishers and shelfishers 9 Policy makers 14 Scientific orgs. 9 socio-env. orgs. 18 sectoral orgs.	shelfishers 20 Policy makers
	Number of collaborative initiatives created	RI	Workshops and report on the lines of action defined collaboratively by stakeholders with the help of the results of the resilience index	0	-	15 initiatives
	Change in the long-term behavioural trends of STH in decision and policy making	RI		-	-	Positive answer to the survey
	Interest and content with the provided data	INTE RM MRM	Entries in the dashboard, satisfaction surveys	-	-	80% of the Fishers shelfishers
Governance and mgmt. measures	Number of mussel aquaculture STH participating in decision-making processes	RI	Participation records during consultation processes in the RI development, stakeholder feedback	-	In progress - 23 agents participated in two consultations (Delphi) - 10 experts in the validation of technical data (climatic variables and projections, processes, and	40 agents

					resilience factors)	
	Number of innovation helixes represented. (According to the quintuple innovation helix framework)	RI	Participation records during consultation processes in the RI development	-	5 helix	5 helix
	Actions and a roadmap defined for enhancing resilience.	RI	Report	No data available for this sector	-	1 roadmap
	Creation of a resilience assessment of the mussel sector	RI	Performance rating of the mussel sector in certain critical areas.		-	RI
	Roadmap with consensus and validated solutions	All	Report	0	Roadmap with 17 validated solutions	
	Set of recommendations and measures including an appealing document	All	Report	-	-	1 set

Baseline data

Previous projects and scientific papers have been taken into account to build upon their results and design the solutions that are being tested in TransformAr. The most important to highlight are:

- MarRisk regional project, where a resilience index for coastal infrastructures was developed. While it offers some clues and orientations about coastal risks in a CC scenario, the project did not focus on shellfish culture.
- León-Mateos et al., 2021, publication in the Marine Policy journal that entails the RI first application in the A Coruña Port, Galicia (Spain), as was explained in section 3.2.1. The RI has never been applied to the mussel sector in Galicia.
- Climefish European project: provided guidelines for how to make climate-enabled management plans to prepare and adapt to climate change while minimizing economic losses and social consequences. Shellfish culture was considered and some of the conclusions lead to the digital-technological approach of the solutions that are being developed in TransformAr. None of them has been tried before in real active culture areas.
- Galician observatory environmental and oceanographic data

For the INTERM, the sedimentological understanding baseline for the sandbanks studied is scarce. No high resolution topography existed for sandbanks harvested by foot. However, and thanks to the meetings organised through the course of the project, we have found previous datasets of intertidal bathymetry surveyed by governmental research institutions of the region that might serve as a baseline for the context of the area bathymetry, and can be included in morphodynamic models grids.

Sediment composition for the selected sandbanks was barely analysed before the start of this project. No studies included or monitored sediment composition at this scale. Only shellfishers guilds provided few samples, not publicly available, per location and year, but with no consistent sampling strategy.

The understanding of the hydrodynamics affecting the selected sandbanks is attained here with direct and temporal measurements of turbidity and current flow direction and magnitude. It is done at specific locations where no baseline data was found after reviewing literature and meeting exchanges. However, there are border scale stations ruled by public organisations in the area, that provide continuous valuable data of sea level, currents, temperature, pressure, etc. (<https://www.meteogalicia.gal/web/home>; <https://www.puertos.es/en-us>)

Morphodynamic simulations are not published for the studied region. There are, however, applications of a similar model set up for the broader scale of the Galician coast aiming to provide insights in the temperature and salinity modifications of the coastal bivalve ecosystems (Des et al., 2021, Des et al., 2020).

For the MRM, there are not previous oceanographic and production data in real time taken from an active mussel raft. It was never tried before in a structure that belong to producers without impacting their daily activities. Time series are being obtained in the TransformAr project since May 2023, which are currently undergoing processing and analysis. They need to be compared to data gathered by scientific or administrative centres to clean them and understand the local effects of the environmental changes in the production.

It's relevant to mention for this **demonstrator the bilateral meetings and workshops held in the initial two years of the project. These sessions gathered information on STH ' perceptions and interests regarding CC and adaptation measures.** Additionally, each solution has maintained continuous contact with producers, engaging them in identifying needs, installing sensors, making enhancements, and providing consultations to assess the sector's resilience

Availability and access of monitored data

This section describes how data will be stored for each solution, whom will have access to it, and how it will be used.

For the RI

The findings from the RI will be directly communicated to the involved STH and shared at scientific conferences or through scientific communications.

For the INTERM

- **Geological and oceanographic** parameters (topography and bathymetry, sediment composition, turbidity, current magnitude and direction) that monitor the sandbank characteristics and morphology at selected locations.

This monitored data is currently stored internally, accessed by the GEOMA TransformAr team. It is under analysis, used for model configuration validation, presentation of results in conferences, and if asked during the knowledge transfer meetings, shared with scientific assistants of involved shellfish guilds. It is also available for TransformAr partners. If scientific publications result from the analysis, data involved will be submitted to open access platforms.

For the MRM

- **The environmental conditions.** The monitored parameters are *position, raft movement, mussel wire weight, water agitation, rain, wind, air temperature, water Temperature (6 depth levels), salinity, air sound, turbidity and intrusion system*. All these parameters are being measured/recorded at a high frequency. However, for the first tests, commercial precision instrumentation has been used to validate the COTS (Commercial off-the-shelf) components. The final monitoring solution must not include the acquisition of expensive oceanographic equipment as traditional CTD or Wave buoys. Instead of that, the solution will focus on the deployment solution based on the integration of COTS
- **Production and management parameters:** maintenance operations control (unfold, landslides, rope extraction, surveillance).

Upon project completion, a user-friendly digital dashboard will be available, providing access to production data exclusively for producers via a website (due to the confidential information that implies). This dashboard will also offer a public view, featuring oceanographic and environmental data for all interested STH.

It is intended that the access and visualization of the data will be tailored for STH and it is essential for the initiative to have an impact on the sector. This access and representation of the data must be accessible for the sector and its workers, facilitating understanding, allowing the relationship and comparison between data to obtain significant conclusions.

2.4. Conclusions

The Galician Climate Change and Energy Strategy 2050 and sectoral workshops outlines the importance of understanding how the variations in oceanographic conditions, changes in rainfall and runoff regime, will threaten the aquaculture sector. In this context, the challenge is to find suitable adaptation tools to ensure the resilience and sustainability, considering both their adequacy and economic viability. In order to address this effectively, it is crucial to monitor the evolution of climate-related risks and provide the sector knowledge through accessible and user-friendly datasets.

Three solutions are being developed in order to provide valuable insights into these challenges: the Intertidal Monitoring - INTERM, Mussel Raft Monitoring - MRM, and Resilience Index - RI.

In general terms it is expected that the demonstrator **innovates** on monitoring, technical and social aspects. It provides a decision-making tool, simplifying complex scientific data into easily understandable metrics while offering a comprehensive assessment of adaptive capacity.

The solutions also present innovations in scientific monitoring filling knowledge gaps, and conducts simulations unprecedented in Galicia's productive sandbanks. Moreover, exhibits innovations in real-time data collection, remote monitoring, predictive modelling, alerts, data storage, energy efficiency, and non-disruptive integration into daily operations, marking significant advancements in the Galician mussel industry. It ensures inclusive stakeholder engagement, reducing biases and involving them in decision-making processes for sectoral improvements beyond the project's duration.

The **impact** of these solutions will be evaluated by the awareness and the perception of risks, the availability and utilisation of tools, in combination with the knowledge increase. Furthermore, the roadmap with consensus and validated solutions will be a key indicator of success, as well as the engagement of relevant actors and STH.

While the increase of understanding in the problem to solve impact is approached through indicators based on data availability improvement, the approach to monitor the social impacts involves a range of tools, including workshops, testimonies, key informant interviews, surveys, reports, and various communication and transfer events. These tools will help demonstrate the achievement of the expected impacts and enable STH to assess the effectiveness of the solutions.

In summary, the Galician demonstrator is making strides in testing innovative solutions to enhance the resilience of shellfish aquaculture and harvesting in the face of CC. The specific objectives of the project, including improved understanding of sea behaviour, stakeholder engagement, digitalization, and decision-making support, all contribute to the overarching goal of transforming and adapting these vital industries in the Galician region to the challenges of CC.

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3.0. Lappeenranta – Developing stormwater management and monitoring

Executive summary

A number of solutions exist to adapt to the consequences of climate change. An overview of existing solutions is provided in the 'Catalogue of solutions' ([Deliverable report 3.2](#)). This report describes firstly the adaptation solutions that are being tested in the city of Lappeenranta, Finland, and secondly how the impact of the solutions will be monitored. Reference is given to the respective task (T) in work package 4. The solutions are:

1) **Nature-based urban stormwater solution (URB)** (T4.3.2): a biofiltration area, that captures and treats runoff and storm water from the surroundings street and sidewalk in the city center of Lappeenranta.

2) **Stormwater monitoring (SWMM)**³ (T4.4.1): The influent to the biofiltration area and groundwater is monitored with real-time sensors for water quantity, and quality, in addition to sampling campaigns for runoff and groundwater. Water flow volumes/surface levels in pipelines as well as stormwater quality are monitored in stormwater conveyance system facilities to identify capacity and quality issues.

3) **Citizen App Finland (CAF)** (T4.1.2): Data on stormwater management, from monitoring and simulations, are brought together in data applications. An existing platform used by the city administration, named Street AI, is being extended for stormwater management. In addition, a new app is being developed for the citizens of Lappeenranta. Citizen app allows users to get up-to-date information e.g. on air quality, weather, stormwater quality, stormwater drainage system flooding and ongoing street works.

4) The fourth solution is a **Choice Experiment survey for citizens** (CEI, T4.5.3): this survey is asking citizens about their willingness to apply runoff and stormwater management measures on private land. The choice experiment is not limited to the citizens of Lappeenranta. The choice experiment reaches out to 1000 citizens across Finland, and 1000 citizens in Norway.

Technical partners supporting city of Lappeenranta are: LUT, UA, NTNU, Verhaert. The tasks of each partner are described in section 3.2.

This intermediary monitoring report defines objectives for these four solutions and describes which impacts are expected and how they are and will be monitored. The objectives are: (i) Reducing pluvial urban flood risk, (ii) Reducing the overall load of the stormwater drain system, (iii) Increasing environmental awareness of emission load to recipient lake and groundwater, and mitigation of the load caused by the runoff, (iv) Increasing knowledge and accessibility of data to all stakeholders via real-time monitoring and novel data, (v) Facilitation improvement of the choice of alternative options, e.g., green infrastructure, (vi) Increase awareness of stakeholders on climate change impacts on local level and region.

³ The Grant Agreement mentions 2 solutions SWM and SWMM, yet both refer to the monitoring of stormwater management solutions. We propose to use just 'SWMM' as the solution (in full: storm water monitoring).

The impacts monitored are (i) Flood Vulnerability (ii) Water Quality (iii) Social Acceptance, and (iv) Economic Costs. The report defines solution sensitive indicators and presents indicators chosen for monitoring. All four solutions have novelty in the city of Lappeenranta. URB is a NBS which is built for the first time in this city, and the biofilter media has a new structure containing biochar and gangue (limestone mining) crushed fraction. Monitoring of URB provides real-time data that is utilized together with laboratory analysis to provide information about the volume flows, water quality and emission load. This requires computational correction and modelling (see Chapter 3.3.) to be integrated into the digital platform of the city. The digital platform is utilized in citizen application (CAF). In addition to the URB, the drainage influent flow is monitored and measured aiming to provide novel information to city planning about the seasonal and precipitation wise variation. Utilization of public cameras for precipitation estimates provides novel tool for street maintenance and real-time warnings. Principle concepts of innovations are presented in this report broadly since the implementation of the solutions is not completed.

3.1. Context

Infographic

Objectives

Objectives of the demonstrator: (i) Urban surface runoff and flood mitigation, mitigation of the risk, (ii) Addressing the conveyance runoff water pipelines capacity issues, (iii) Increasing environmental awareness of emission load to recipient and groundwater, and mitigation of the load caused by the runoff, (iv) Increasing accessibility of data to all stakeholders via real-time monitoring and novel data, (v) Facilitation improvement of the choice of alternative options, e.g., green infrastructure, (vi) Increase awareness of stakeholders on climate change impacts on local level and region.

Table 1 presents problem statements and how they are related to the solutions demonstrated.

Table 1 Problem definitions and objectives in relation to solutions demonstrated.

Problem definition and objectives	URB	SWMM	CAF	CEI
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Increased flood risk due to increased rainfall and temperature in winter and spring: urban surface runoff and flood mitigation, mitigation of the risk 	x	x		x
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Increase of peak events in precipitation: addressing the conveyance runoff water pipelines capacity issues 	x	x		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Environmental assessment of emission load to recipient lake and groundwater caused by runoff and infiltration: increasing awareness, mitigation of the load 	x	x	x	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Adaptation relevant data and information availability to all stakeholders: improvement to present state via real-time monitoring and novel data 	x	x	x	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Facilitation of the choice of alternative options, e.g., green infrastructure: increase awareness of stakeholders 	x	x	x	x
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Climate change impacts in this region: Increase awareness of stakeholders via empirical data and forecasts from reliable sources. 		x	x	

Geographical description

Lappeenranta (61-06°N, 28-19 °E) is a Finnish city with a population of 73000 covering an area of 1,724 km² situated in the region of 'South Karelia' (aka. Etelä-Karjala) on the south-eastern frontier of Finland, 30 kilometres away from the Russian border (Figure 4). The city is located on the shores of Lake Saimaa, which is the biggest lake in Finland and the fourth biggest lake of Europe. The city's main water intake is the lake water, which a decade ago was polluted by the proliferation of algae. Since, water conservation has been a major area of interest for the city. According to the latest national water quality classification ([Finnish Environment Institute, 2019](#)), the water quality of the Western Saimaa is fair to intermediate. The objective is good ecological status.

Figure 4 Lappeenranta's boundaries within South Karelia in relation to the map of Finland

The city centre is located on the First Salpausselkä ridge, which is an ice-marginal formation laid down by the last Ice Age. Salpausselkä is mainly formed of sand and gravel and holds massive reserves of high-quality groundwater.

According to the Köppen climate classification, Finland has a continental subarctic/boreal climate and Lappeenranta has a southern-boreal climate. The city's climate is influenced by Salpausselkä, the lake areas of Saimaa and Laatokka (in Russia) and the Gulf of Finland.

Typical of the city's climate are four distinct seasons, each season lasting approximately three months. In Lappeenranta, winter is longer than summer. Precipitation has an annual average of 614 millimetres of which 40-50 % usually falls as snow. The snow cover typically melts in April and May which can contribute to flooding. In this context it is important to underline that the meltwaters are recognised to consist of large amounts of nutrients and heavy metals. These substances are mainly from prevention of icy roads and yards, and from vehicles, which are more polluting in winter due to corrosion caused by road salt. In addition, the rain or melting snow washes with it pollution from all other impermeable surfaces, such as roofs or construction areas.

Climate vulnerability, impacts and challenges

For Lappeenranta, the Key Community Systems (KCS) that we focus on are water management and urban planning. Lappeenranta demonstrator will be implementing solutions to adapt to CC in these KCS described in more detail below:

I- WATER MANAGEMENT

Climate change impacts on water in Lappeenranta could create new water-related challenges and exacerbate existing ones in light of changing rainfall seasonality, climate variability and extreme weather events. This is likely to have a series of ramifications on a range of economic sectors that depend and rely on water such as tourism, industry, agriculture, among others. Not to mention, water quality could be affected as heavy rainfall could lead to the dilution of polluted water, which makes treating it more

challenging and requires more costly and energy-intensive technologies. Therefore, addressing water issues and ensuring a sound water management is crucial for the city of Lappeenranta.

II- URBAN PLANNING

As the city of Lappeenranta is one of the major urban centres in the Saimaa region, urban planning needs to consider and adapt to climate change. Water from melting snow and flood water bring contaminants (e.g., oils, chemicals, microplastics, as well as organic and solid matters) which are likely to decrease the quality of water in the city and the lake. An adaptive urban planning could be a key to solve these issues and improve the living conditions of Lappeenranta's citizens.

The possible vulnerabilities and challenges caused by climate change in Lappeenranta key community systems was evaluated in the TransformAr *pathways workshop* by the stakeholders. Figure 5 summarises the climate change projections for Lappeenranta region (PIK 2022). It is to be expected that the winters will be milder but wetter, which will cause more load on the urban drainage system. In the wintertime the frozen soil is not so permeable, so flooding is expected to increase. Furthermore, climate change is projected to increase the number of heavy rain events, that can surpass the capacity of the urban drainage system.

According to projections, **Lappeenranta** is likely to deal with

Figure 5 Summary of climate projections for the City of Lappeenranta (Source: PIK presentation during the WS 2)

Based on these climate projections, hazards and vulnerabilities were assessed in the *pathways workshop*. The risk chains that have been developed in the workshop are presented in Figure 6 and Figure 4. The increased rainfall projections and the insufficient capacity of the stormwater pipe network leads to increased flooding risk and more harmful substances in the stormwater.

In light of climate change, some opportunities may arise at the scale of Lappeenranta, including the increase of water availability as well as an increase in forest growth, crop yields and the potential of tourism due to milder weather conditions. This is important to underline as adaptation is not solely about increasing the resilience of the territory in the face of shocks and stresses but also entails profiting from opportunities that are likely to arise (Burch & Harris, 2014).

Figure 6 Risk chain for the sector of Water management for the City of Lappeenranta

Similarly, a risk chain was created for the urban planning KCS and is presented in Figure 7. This assessment gives similar risks, but from a different perspective. Flooding is still seen as one of the main risks with the addition of droughts.

Figure 7 Risk chain for the sector of Urban planning for the City of Lappeenranta

State-of-the-art on adaptation in the demonstrator

Adaptation policy in the demonstrator

Finland's National Strategy (2005), [the National Climate Change Adaption plan 2022](#), Flood Risk Management Act (No. 620/2010), and Land use and Building Decree enacted under the Land use and Building Act (132/1999) form the ground for City of Lappeenranta climate strategy. As summarised in the [Finnish country fiche](#) for the EU adaptation preparedness scoreboard, the NAP stresses that municipalities ensure the integration of climate proofing reviews into the planning of emergency preparedness and security of supplies. The NAP requires the joint regional offices ([ELY-keskus](#)) of the Ministry of Employment and Economy, the Ministry of Environment, the Ministry of Transport and

Communications and the Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry to guide municipalities in boosting climate resilience.

As further outlined in the [Finnish country fiche](#), in 2017, the majority of Finnish municipalities implemented action on climate change adaptation. By the end of 2015, regional flood risk management plans were published for every significant flood risk area (21 areas) and implementation of identified measures is ongoing. The NAP further seeks to integrate adaptation multi-sectorally on a multi-actor basis. Moreover, adaptation is also taken into account in the [Climate Act](#) (which was also approved in 2015). The Climate Act maintains that national authorities need to promote the NAP in their actions, including - but not limited to - land use, buildings and construction, environmental protection and the use and management of water resources. Research and communication are also highlighted as necessary to complement these actions.

The climate [programme of the city of Lappeenranta for 2021-2030](#) forms the basis for the carbon neutrality target by 2030 and its long-term emission reduction targets. The climate programme is developed based on the reporting model of Covenant of Mayors for Climate & Energy (CoM), and as a result the Sustainable Energy and Climate Action Plan (SECAP) is created and reported to the Covenant of Mayors for Climate & Energy reporting platform. The city of Lappeenranta committed to conduct SECAP when joining the Covenant of Mayors in 2016. The risks and vulnerability of climate change as well as adaptation to possible risks were assessed for the climate programme, and the risk and vulnerability assessments were carried out using an Indicator-based Vulnerability Assessment method. Experts from different organisations of the city of Lappeenranta and closely related companies (e.g., energy supply) took part in workshops on risk assessment and vulnerabilities. The assessed adaptation actions are closely connected with the new climate program 2021-2030 and are reported to the Covenant of Mayors platform. The implementation of the climate programme for 2021-2030 is followed yearly through the *Ilmastovahti* website. The implementation and follow-up actions are connected to the [Climate programme of the city of Lappeenranta](#).

The City strategy (LPR2037) sets out its long-term operational and financial objectives According to the City strategy land use planning should aim to ensure that stormwater management considers the status and quality of water bodies where stormwater is discharged. In the strategy it is encouraged to use a wider range of methods for managing stormwater and increasing the use of NBS and on-site solutions. The construction of a new stormwater drainage system should be minimised.

A [stormwater management plan](#) (Ramboll Finland Oy, 2021) was developed for the city of Lappeenranta to prevent problems caused by stormwater, such as flood damage and water pollution, and to maintain the natural water cycle, such as the water retention and groundwater recharge. The aim is also to manage stormwater as cost-effectively as possible. The stormwater management plan underlines the importance of promoting stormwater management consideration at all stages of development and construction (i.e., land use planning, building control and maintenance). The plan directs construction and design and provides guidance on a catchment-by-catchment basis and for each land use type.

The city of Lappeenranta has projects and programmes to increase biodiversity in the urban environment, such as [Meadow network project](#) which, in addition to protecting biodiversity, encourages residents to participate in the design of their living environment, and a [Biodiversity programme 2023-2033](#) which brings together measures to protect nature values and aims to improve the city's practices to become more ecologically sustainable and respond to the global nature challenge.

Table 2. Adaptation governance at the national level

Finland's National Strategy for Adaptation to Climate Change	The National Climate Change Adaptation Plan 2022
<p>Finland's National Strategy for Adaptation to Climate Change adopted in 2005 aims to reinforce and enhance the capacity to adapt to climate change in Finland. The focus of the adaptation strategy is the national level and the approach is sector-based. The Adaptation Strategy gives a detailed account of the impacts of climate change in different sectors and presents measures to be taken until 2080. The main elements of the strategy are also included in the National Energy and Climate Strategy, where the focus is on measures to be launched in the next 5 to 10 years.</p>	<p>The aim of the plan is that the Finnish society has the capacity to manage the risks associated with climate change and adapt to changes in the climate. It identifies the most important tasks needed to promote adaptation nationally, and encourages Finnish society to take action on climate change adaptation in every sector. Monitoring the implementation of the plan is ensured by a multi-stakeholder group, while both local and regional authorities have incorporated adaptation action into their climate strategies. The Act was launched in 2014 and brought the 2005 strategy up to date.</p>

Table 3. Relevant national Finnish policies

Flood Risk Management Act (No. 620/2010)	Land use and Building Decree enacted under the Land use and Building Act (132/1999)
<p>The Act is part of the adaptation strategy and aims to improve the organisation of flood risk management through the reduction of flood risks, as well as through the prevention and mitigation of adverse consequences caused by floods. The Act also coordinates flood risk management and other management plans of river basins, by taking into account requirements related to sustainable use and protection of water resources.</p>	<p>The Act supports the relevant municipal and regional authorities to improve energy efficiency and sustainability of buildings, developments and plans in their jurisdiction. The update of the national governmental land-use guidelines in 2008 includes storms, heavy rains and urban flooding and the risks of major accidents as additional factors to consider during land-use planning processes.</p>

Stormwater management

In the urban areas of Lappeenranta the main management system for stormwater is the stormwater drain, which is located under the streets with inlets from the pavement. In Lappeenranta stormwater and wastewater are drained in separate sewers. Wastewater is discharged to a treatment plant, while most of the stormwater especially from the city centre area is discharged untreated into the water body. Even though stormwater in stormwater pipelines does not contain domestic sewerage, it holds substantial pollution. The stormwater pipes are known to be overloaded, as a consequence of large impermeable surfaces that drain towards the stormwater pipes.

The pipelines should be capable of transmitting accumulated flow caused by climate change, but the capacity of most of the pipelines in Lappeenranta is already full. The infrastructure has been designed for prevailing conditions, not taking into account climate projections. The capacity of the existing drainage is thus not capable of processing increased precipitation in light of climate change which increases flood events and risks. Overflow routes should therefore be well-designed to minimise the damage. Stormwater management should also consider other solutions rather than the mere discharge of precipitation into drains, such as decentralised methods and Nature-based solutions (NBS).

Outside the city centre there are a total of seven constructed wetlands, located on the shores of lake Saimaa, to treat stormwater from some of the catchment areas. Lappeenranta has good experiences with constructed wetlands that treat stormwaters before they enter the lake. However, these are mainly built outside the denser city area, in the suburbs and rural areas, because of the lack of room to implement wetlands in densely built areas. For urban areas these wetlands do not necessarily reduce flooding as such but reduce the pollution load on the lake. The NBS filter the stormwater from the city streets and sidewalks.

In urban areas there are some retention basins, which mainly serve to balance flood peaks during heavy rains and help with capacity problems in the sewerage network. Since the introduction of the Stormwater management plan, private landowners have also been required to delay stormwater run-off before it is discharged to the stormwater sewers. So far, these systems have mainly been installed on public buildings such as schools, large parking lots and for example on apartment building sites.

As Lappeenranta is located in groundwater area, the recharge of stormwaters into aquifers is crucial. Urban planning should thus stress the importance of increasing green areas to limit flood risks, specially that climate change is expected to increase the amount and intensity of rainfall in Europe (JRC Scient Policy Report, 2020).

3.2. Description of solutions in TransformAr

A total of four solutions are demonstrated in the city of Lappeenranta. The solution URB (T4.3.2) is a biofiltration area, where runoff and storm water harvested from street and sidewalk in city centre. The influent on biofiltration area and groundwater is monitored with real-time sensors for water volume flow, and environmental emissions. The information gained is completed with water sampling campaigns that provide direct information about nutrient and heavy metal concentrations. Water flow volumes/surface levels as well as stormwater quality are monitored in additional sites at the old, constructed conveyance system facilities to identify capacity and quality issues. All above mentioned information is gathered together and utilized SWMM (T4.4.1) solution, where data is turned into information via models and figures. This information is utilized by city planners and local authorities via closed, existing city system (Street AI) and by citizens via public citizen application implemented in TransformAr (CAF, T4.1.2). The fourth solution is a choice experiment (CEI, T4.5.3) for the stormwater management system upscaling.

URB (NBS)

URB: Supported by LUT, LAPP will use NBS as part of the urban run-off system as a flood management solution. This will allow the co-design of new integrative Nature-Based Solutions as part of new urban adaptation standards which is jointly developed with city planners, architects, and urban architecture responsible administrators. Plants and greeneries will be used for reducing urban runoff.

In section 4.3 the utilization of constructed wetlands in the city of Lappeenranta has been described. The upstream constructed wetlands have been constructed to reduce the pollution load of the stormwater to the lake Saimaa. For this purpose, the experiences from the wetlands have been excellent. In this project, the NBS solution will demonstrate water retention and filtration in an urban, downstream location. To combine stormwater retention, infiltration and treatment and delay the storm waters way

to the drainage system in a relatively small footprint a nature-based solution is demonstrated. The location of NBS is presented in Figure 8 and plan of this NBS filtration field in Figure 9.

Figure 8. Location of the NBS and Lake Saimaa.

Figure 9 Plan of the Koulukatu NBS demonstration

Water is led through the filtration field from the surrounding streets, yards and roofs. The water that enters the NBS gets slowed down, and depending on the amount, some, or most of it gets adsorbed

through the layers and finally reaches the groundwater. The varied vegetation in the green area utilizes water that is not immediately absorbed through the filter layer. In the case of severe rain, not all water gets adsorbed, and the overflow is directed back to the storm water drainage system, in this case the area functions as a buffering zone to prevent flooding of the drainage system. Any pollution in the incoming water should get filtered out, and for example nutrients utilized by the plants growing in the NBS.

Furthermore, Lappeenranta sits on top of ground water reservoirs (See Section 4.1), so any system that is intended to filter water through it must be designed in such a way that the filtrated water does not contaminate the groundwaters. Filtration fields can fit into a relatively small footprint and take load of the stormwater drainage and pollution load of the lake, where the stormwater is traditionally directed.

Here the nature-based solution (NBS) refers to the demonstration of stormwater adsorption field in the city of Lappeenranta. This solution is closely related to digital solutions, as sensors to monitor the water quality and amount are placed to the NBS. The groundwater after treatment by the NBS is monitored to assess the functionality of the filtration in the NBS. Also, the digital solution of storm water monitoring is connected to this demonstration, as it allows more precise measurement of the amounts of water passing through the NBS and consequently the evaluation of the capacity saved in the stormwater drainage system. This information is crucial when new filtration areas are planned to be able to place them into ideal locations to mitigate flooding of the storm water system and streets. The placement of the sensors in the NBS is indicated in Figure 9.

Creating this kind of green filtration area to existing city scape poses its own challenges. The planning and construction of the demonstration site gives new insight into the process to city planners and practical understanding about the construction process.

Through the digital monitoring and sampling campaign, the functionality of the NBS is evaluated. Combining the information from monitoring with the experience gained from the planning and building helps to locate new places for similar NBS solutions.

NBS increase biodiversity in a densely built-up area that would otherwise have very limited green space (Biodiversity programme). By building NBS in the city centre, methods not previously used in the city are used, stormwater management methods will be diversified (City strategy), and the Stormwater management plan is followed by treating stormwater where it is generated.

SWMM (digital solution)

SWMM: LAPP, supported by LUT, VERHAERT and its Linked Third Party Pegus Digital, will couple a first set of new sensors, measuring water quality, flow and volume within the water pipe and drainage system, to a scalable digital platform. This platform will be developed to TRL level 7 to prove monitoring scalability & impact for Lappeenranta. Analysis of available and generated data of the purification/filtration processes and control processes of the runoff-water management system will be executed by LUT with initial research by VERHAERT on applicable predictive machine learning models.

Figure 10 Different aspects of stormwater monitoring and how they could be connected to each other.

Storm water management and storm water management monitoring are closely connected to the NBS filtration field. One of the main goals is to gather information on the function of the NBS in the form of water quality indicators and amount of water passing through. At the same time this monitoring campaign test the feasibility of implementing similar monitoring in other parts of the storm water drainage system. This is done with sensors attached to drainage system manholes and with openly available video feeds in the city. Together with NTNU the camera feeds are utilized to estimate the precipitation levels with more precise locations. The aim is to produce online measurement data to get a more complete view on storm water pollutant and amounts in the NBS and water flows. Various indicators can then be calculated from this data some for authorities and study purposes. Findings can also be distributed to the public through the citizen app.

A sampling campaign from the NBS demonstration is planned, and those results are utilized in the validation or calibration of the online sensors. Sampling campaigns are aimed to cover reasonable variation from different events and seasons for modelling. The models are validated and updated during the demonstration.

Through monitoring more information on the pollution/nutrient content and amount of storm water is acquired. This information is crucial to evaluate the performance of the NBS demonstration as either stormwater filtration or retention. Monitoring the water flow in the drainage system can reveal potential flooding risks. In locations where there is a known risk of storm water sewer flooding, sensors to measure the variation in water level will be installed. The data will be used in Citizen app to give warnings about water flooding in the street. The risk areas and flooded manholes can be identified using the hydraulic and hydrological model (Figure 11).

Figure 11. Flooded manholes in red color and other manholes in green color, from Hydraulic and hydrological model of the storm water sewer system.

When combined this information helps in the planning of new NBS sites in the city, that can handle elevated rainfall events.

According to the City strategy, the water quality of Lake Saimaa and other water bodies must be protected. By monitoring storm water quality and flow in drainage system it is possible to identify areas that need action and target the necessary measures to those areas.

CAF (Citizen app)

CAF: For the city of Lappeenranta, NTNU, together with LUT, will develop and support the implementation of a citizen application for crowd sensing and real time monitoring of anomalies due to climate change events.

Together with LUT, NTNU, Verhaert and the replicator municipality of Gjøvik, city of Lappeenranta is developing and implementing a citizen application for crowd sensing and real time monitoring of anomalies due to climate change events. The overall objective of Citizen app is to raise awareness of climate change and storm water management and enable feedback from citizens (Figure 12. *Principle of the Citizen app and connections with StreetAI and existing feedback systems in both Lappeenranta and Gjøvik.*).

Figure 12. Principle of the Citizen app and connections with StreetAI and existing feedback systems in both Lappeenranta and Gjøvik.

Citizen app allows users to get up-to-date information on air quality, weather, stormwater quality, stormwater drainage system flooding and ongoing street works, among other things. Until now such information has not been available to citizens, except for weather data. Another important element is giving feedback. Since the city already has an existing feedback system that also allows sending pictures of concerns, the app's feedback will be integrated into the existing system as shown in Figure 12.

The app supports other implementations of the demonstrator by linking NBS and SWMM together and sharing this information with the citizens. The solution is in line with the city strategy where it is stated that cooperation with citizens and other stakeholders is one of the values to be respected.

CEI (Choice experiment)

CEI: Additionally, LAPP will also conduct choice experiments for the stormwater management system (in T4.4) upscaling. The outcome will be models for integrating knowledge on stakeholder preferences for climate adaptation and related services into the design of new policy instruments and business models and the co-design and test policy tools as part of new adaptation standards jointly with stakeholders, through behavioural economic experiments in the different regions. For this specific case, the Gjøvik municipality will have 2 field trips to follow the implementation of such solutions to foresee a potential replication.

Choice experiment is conducted both in Finland and in Norway focusing on stakeholders. The choice experiment provides information about citizens awareness and willingness to pay for NBS solutions. Initially, the survey was to be addressed to investors but due to challenges city of Lappeenranta is facing in implementing stormwater management measures in private land (see 4.3) and overlaps between CEI and other choice experiments implemented in TransformAr, such as T5.3.2, it was decided to focus on citizens, especially private plot owners.

The outcome of the CEI should provide models on stakeholder preferences for climate adaptation and related services, and co-design of policy instruments and business models with stakeholders through integration of their preferences.

According to the city's Stormwater management plan private landowners are required to manage stormwater in their own yards as a primary method of stormwater management before it is discharged to stormwater sewers. So far, these systems, both NBS and underground stormwater storage solutions,

have mainly been installed on public buildings such as schools, large parking lots and for example on apartment building sites. The city has had difficulties in implementing this part of the Stormwater management plan, as the stormwater sewerage network covers almost the entire city, there is no stormwater fee and it has been easier and in principle less expensive for landowners to connect to the stormwater drainage system than to carry out the measures on their own land and at their own expense. The results of CEI are expected to be useful in addressing this challenge.

Description of the expected innovations

Previously four different solutions and how they complement each other and fit the overall strategy of the demonstrator. Each of the solutions is expected to produce some new information or innovation for the demonstrator and then be distributed to a wider audience. As each solution has different expected innovations in different fields, these have been collected Table . In some fields the innovations stretch across different solutions, indicating that combining information from different solutions results in the desired innovation.

Table 4. Expected innovations.

Aspects of innovation and added value	URB	SWMM	CAF	CEI
Technical or technological innovation <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Combining NBS implementation to street renovations Assess performance of NBS to treat storm water Utilization of sensors to monitor storm water Utilization of public cameras to estimate precipitation 	X	X	X	
Innovation on monitoring <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Combining information from laboratory samples and real time measurements to evaluate for example nutrient concentrations in the stormwaters. Flooding and drainage capacity monitoring Utilization of cameras in precipitation estimation 	X	X	X	
Innovation to city planning <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Distributed stormwater management Novel and real-time information from choices, their effects and citizen willingness 	X	X	X	X
Awareness on climate change and regional effects for citizens			X	X

These possible innovations are presented here as quite general concepts, as many of the solutions are not completed yet and how well the expected innovations are acquired is not known. However, all four solutions have novelty for the city of Lappeenranta. For example, the NBS solution is the first to be built and innovations regarding how building should be done and planned have already been gained.

The measurement campaign has the potential to provide plenty of novel innovations. Firstly, monitoring the NBS solution in real time and calibrating the data with laboratory analyzed samples. Secondly following the water volumes in the stormwater drains and combining that data with precipitation estimates gained from public camera imagery creates a new way to monitor the capacity of the drainage system and potentially give warnings about flood risks. Furthermore, the processed data and real time information about water quality can be distributed to the public through citizen application to increase awareness of climate change adaptation.

3.3.Expected impacts

Overview of the expected impacts

The expected impacts of solutions demonstrated are described in Table 5. All four solutions can be expected to have an impact on flood vulnerability, and social acceptance or acceptance in city planning. CAF and CEI can have long-term effects on water quality. However, in CAF and CEI the impact is not measured with indicators due to the nature of the impact. URB with monitoring system, and the influent together with the groundwater will be analyzed. This empirical information can be utilized together with existing water quality of recipient lake and wetlands to evaluate the impacts. Economic assessment and impacts in this frame will be done via empirical cost estimates and comparing to alternative solutions typically applied in Lappeenranta. Tables 5. and 6. describe the expected impacts and the indicators in detail.

Table 5. Expected impacts of the four solutions.

Expected impact	URB	SWMM	CAF	CEI
Flood Vulnerability				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Gathering runoff (stormwater) from streets and leading them to biofiltration will help free capacity from drainage and mitigate flood and drought risks. 	x			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Monitoring volume flows and surface levels provides novel information and warnings. 		x		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Distributed stormwater management mitigate flood risks 	x	x		x
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Realtime estimates for precipitation via cameras provide local estimates and warnings 		x	x	
Water Quality				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Realtime monitoring of URB together with laboratory measurements provides information on runoff and groundwater quality. 		x		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Biofiltering field utilizes nutrients and filters urban emissions 	x			
Acceptance				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> City planning gain novel information to support decision making and planning 	x	x	x	x
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Citizen's awareness of environmental effects of runoff and choices for mitigating the risks and impacts increase 	x		x	x
Economic Costs				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Solution costs are compared to traditional alternatives and reflected to benefits expected. 	x	x	x	x

Selected indicators

The expected impacts of the four solutions will be described with indices and metrics shown in Table 5. The indicators for URB and SWMM are mostly calculated from the monitored water qualities and measured flows, with calibration from the laboratory analyses. In addition prior information and projected information for example on the rain events are utilized to construct the indicators. The CAF

solution is mainly aimed to provide information to citizens of the area, so most of the indicators will be determined from the user engagement.

Table 6. The longlist of indicators. Solution T4.3.2 URB (NBS), T4.4.1 SWMM (NBS and digital solutions), Solution T4.1.2 CAF (Citizen application) and T4.5.3 CEI (Choice experiment) indicators for expected impacts with units.

To assess the effectiveness of implemented solutions and monitor their progress, a tailored set of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) has been defined for each demonstrator. The KPIs provide quantifiable evidence on the technical, environmental, and social performance of the deployed solutions. They are aligned with the overarching TransformAr objectives and reflect the specific context, data availability, and impact logic in each location.

The following tables list the selected KPI for Lappeenranta. Each indicator includes a description, its source or method of measurement, associated solution(s), and thematic relevance (e.g. health, infrastructure, environmental sustainability). The KPIs are categorized by the nature of impact and are designed to support ex post evaluation, policy planning, and community awareness initiatives.

Table 6. Overview of Key Performance Indicators (KPI)

Solution	Expected impact	Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)	Source/Measurement Approach
Nature-Based Stormwater Solution	Reduction in flooding events. Mitigating drought risk.	Reduction in peak runoff levels (%)	Real-time monitoring via sensors
	Improved water quality, increased knowledge of main water quality parameters.	Water quality improvements (pollutant reduction %)	Real-time monitoring via sensors and water sampling campaigns
	Mitigating flood risk.	Increase in stormwat	Real-time monitoring

		er retention capacity	g via sensors
Stormwater Monitoring	Increased knowledge and awareness of key stakeholders. City planning gain novel information to support decision making and planning.	Number of monitoring sensors installed	Sensor deployment tracking
	Improved knowledge of flood risk.	Real-time data accuracy and reliability (%)	Data verification & models
			Data from app
Citizen App	Citizen's engagement	Number of citizen reports submitted	App analytics and surveys
	Citizen's awareness of environmental effects of runoff and choices for mitigating the risks and impacts increase	User engagement metrics (logins, feedback provided)	
	Increased knowledge and awareness	Improvement in communi	

	<p>s of key stakeholders at different levels (public and private sectors, economic categories, citizens, etc.)</p>	<p>ty awareness on flood risk (%)</p>	
<p>Choice Experiment</p>		<p>Norway :1000 respondents Finland: 1013 respondents</p>	<p>Survey analysis and economic modeling</p>
	<p>This research provides valuable insights into how to encourage private investments in stormwater management (SWM) to address urban flooding risks. It will reveal residents' preference of the SWM measures . These findings can help policymakers</p>	<p>Finland exhibits a higher WTP for risk reduction (up to €4,820 for a 75% risk reduction), while Norway shows a stronger preference for runoff reduction (up to €3550 per household for a 50% runoff reduction). Aesthetic improvements are valued more in</p>	

	design more effective incentives and SWM strategies that align with residents' preferences, promoting broader adoption, which will promote the collective actions from citizens and improving urban flood resilience	Finland (€1,257) than in Norway (€615).	
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Note: The KPI table for Lappeenranta includes specific metrics for each solution (URB, SWMM, CAF, CEI), aligned with climate adaptation goals. These include indicators such as reduction in stormwater runoff volume, usage rate of the CAF app, behavioral shifts based on CEI outcomes, and green infrastructure effectiveness. KPIs are measured against baseline conditions established in 2023 and will be assessed periodically through 2025. All indicators were selected for their contribution to measuring combined ecological and community resilience. The originally proposed performance indicator—comparison of flood-related outcomes with and without predictive analytics—was not applicable due to the **absence of an actual flood event during the NBS installation and operation phase**. Consequently, real-world data for direct causal comparison could not be captured within the timeframe of the project.

Baseline data

Generation of official and local knowledge in Lappeenranta region is supported by three main institutes: [The Finnish Meteorological Institute](#), [The Flood Centre of the Finnish Environment Institute](#) and [Finnish Meteorological Institute](#) (established in 2014) and [The Finnish Environment Institute \(SYKE\)](#).³

SYKE is principally in charge of collecting information on floods and their impacts. SYKE also coordinates action for the [Finnish Long-Term Socio-Ecological network](#) (FinLTSER) network which gathers researchers

and scientists working on related socio-ecological issues on platforms representing the major ecosystems such as marine, terrestrial, lake, sub-arctic and urban settings.

SYKE has created a nationwide stormwater flood risk map to help municipalities better identify flood risks from rainwater and meltwater in urban and built-up areas. The map has been updated to reflect the actual situation, including the addition of drains to channel stormwater, for example under roads. The flood risk map shows flood water coverage and depth for two rainfall events; a very heavy rainfall event that statistically occurs once every 100 years and a much less frequent heavy rainfall event.

The city of Lappeenranta has a hydraulic and hydrological model covering the entire stormwater drainage network, including catchment areas and their characteristics. The model allows for an analysis of the current network capacity and calculated overflow and flooding situations, as well as to design treatment methods for stormwater based on the characteristics of the area. The model will be used to assess impact of the solutions on the capacity of the stormwater drainage system. In Figure 13 is presented the baseline data for URB from hydraulic and hydrological model. The amount of storm water and the flowrates are calculated on the basis of the design guide in Stormwater management plan. Precipitation is 260 l/s/ha and duration of rainfall 5 minutes.

Figure 13. Baseline data for URB before implementing the NBS (in green color).

The city of Lappeenranta has access to a cloud-based street and city information system StreetAI which collects, analyses, displays and distributes information about city and traffic environments. StreetAI also has information about e.g. local weather and air temperature, which if needed, can be combined with the measured data and information about run-off and flood waters. The aim is to utilize this existing system for data collection and analysis in TransformAr.

In 2008, the [Group for Adaptation to Climate Change](#) was formed to monitor and promote the implementation of the adaptation strategy. The [Monitoring Group on Climate Change Adaptation](#) was formed in 2015 to continue this work, including governmental officials from the Prime Minister's Office and the relevant ministries, agencies, regional and local actors, research institutes, fire and rescue services, and financial services. The monitoring group implements, follows-up and raises awareness on the NAP, but also seeks to encourage collaboration between relevant actors to promote action on adaptation.

The Climate Act states that the implementation of the NAP is to be monitored and reported to Parliament every electoral term (this reporting is included in the annual climate report as well).

Main databases available

- Recipient water quality: Hertta (SYKE, Finnish Environmental Institute)
- Green Reality Lappeenranta databases for runoff water quality.
- Precipitation, depth of snow, temperature, humidity: Finnish Metrological institute database and monitoring stations.
- City planning data bases for spatial use, and drainage systems

Description of available data to complete the data provided by the project

- Flood Vulnerability: Precipitation timeseries (cm/day) in Meteorological Institute database. City planning database of paved surfaces. Hydrological models for flows of drainage system.
- Water Quality: Water quality in several wetlands monitored 2-4 times annually. Research campaigns with weekly quality and flow estimates. Short real-time quality campaigns. Recipient water body quality sampled by Saimaa water association 4 times annually, and with a real-time station.
- Acceptance: City strategy; Green reality and city planning projects; Public regional events for citizens held in city of Lappeenranta.
- Economic Costs: Investment and maintenance costs for main alternative solutions applied in Lappeenranta.

Approach to monitor impacts

Approaches to monitor the impacts are solution sensitive, and methodologies vary. For example, URB (NBS Koulukatu) impact to Flood Vulnerability is defined via empirical real-time water influent and precipitation in the catchment area. These form the baseline estimation that can be presented as m³/h or as cumulative sum of annually captured runoff volume. The real time precipitation is available at Metrological institute database, or it can be estimated via public cameras. Similarly, information is gained from selected manholes of drainage system. Flow volume and surface height in manholes are measured with sensors. This will provide information for city planning on flood risks, and results will be compared and completed with the existing hydraulic and hydrological models. Monitoring SWMM also provides estimates via video cameras on precipitation. This information can be distributed via CAF to citizens.

However, the main indicator and impact of CAF and CEI are engagements of citizens and city planners that show acceptance of new NBS technologies. Figure 14 illustrates monitoring scheme of solutions to Flood Vulnerability.

Figure 14 Overview of main methods applied in describing solutions impacts to flood vulnerability.

Impacts to water quality are defined in solutions URB and SWMM. Figure 15 visualizes main methods. The fundamental idea is to measure real-time data with limited number sensors. This set of sensors does not include direct measurements for nutrients or pH due to the durability and maintenance costs of the sensors. Instead, these water quality parameters are measured in the laboratory from influent and groundwater samples. Models taking account the flow rate (expected dilution), turbidity and conductivity will be applied to estimate the emission load (kg/a) or improvement (%). Estimation will include comparison of runoff water captured to groundwater filtered through the biofilter field and recipient lake water. The goal is to keep the models as simple as possible. For most of the described analyses different regression models can be applied. The laboratory analyzed samples provide a way to calibrate and

validate

the

models.

Figure 15 Overview of main methods applied in describing solutions impacts to water quality.

Costs impact will be evaluated by comparing alternative solutions typically applied and available in Lappeenranta. For monitoring system and CAF costs-benefits will be related to maintenance and implementation costs.

Availability and access of monitored data

Monitored data from the sensor devices described in 3.2 SWMM as well as data from the water sampling campaigns will be transferred to the cloud-based information system using either LTE or LoRaWAN technology. The sensor vendor's own cloud-based information system will collect the data and analyze it. Both data and analyzed information will then be transferred over the Internet to the StreetAI system used by LAPP, using Application programming interfaces (API) in either Push or Pull manner.

All agreed data and analyzed information will be available for the TransformAr partners from the StreetAI platform through an API. The StreetAI platform is accessible to city employees. From StreetAI selected information is provided to citizens via Citizen app (CAF). From Citizen app feedback and local information from various stakeholders can be uploaded to StreetAI to inform relevant parties in the city organization.

The length of the storage of the sensor data and analyzed information will be defined later in TransformAr.

Upscaling and acceleration of the solutions

All solutions demonstrated by city of Lappeenranta are designed in such a way that enables them to be implemented in an urban environment at different scales. Depending on the area and space available, an NBS, for example, may be for larger or smaller catchment areas. Water quality sensors are currently tested in winter conditions and in situations where there is no water flow in the stormwater drain. After this testing, it will be possible to add sensors at points in the network where it is necessary to study either the quantity or the quality of water in the system. Sensors can be used, for example, to calibrate the hydraulic model of the stormwater sewer network.

3.4. Conclusions

In TransformAr, city of Lappeenranta supported by its technical partners is implementing total of four solutions to adapt to CC impacts. All solutions focus on developing stormwater management from the perspective of two KCS: urban planning and water management. The vulnerabilities and challenges caused by climate change in Lappeenranta KCS have been evaluated in the TransformAr *pathways workshop* by the stakeholders. In Lappeenranta climate change is predicted to increase the number of heavy rains, which may exceed the capacity of the drainage system. The infrastructure has been designed for prevailing conditions, not taking into account climate projections. The capacity of the existing stormwater drainage is thus not capable of processing increased precipitation in light of climate change which increases flood events and risks.

The solutions demonstrated include NBS in city centre and a digital and technological solution for measuring water quality and flow. Citizen app and Choice experiment both concern awareness raising and sharing information with the citizens, as well as aiming to provide novel information to city planning.

The objective of these measures includes mitigating the risk of urban surface runoff and flooding, addressing the conveyance runoff water pipelines capacity issues, increasing awareness of emission load to recipient lake and groundwater, increasing knowledge and accessibility of data to all stakeholders, facilitation improvement of the choice of alternative options, and increasing awareness of stakeholders on climate change impacts on local level and region.

The solutions demonstrated are expected to have an impact on flood vulnerability, social acceptance or acceptance in city planning. CAF and CEI can have long-term effects on water quality. URB with monitoring system, and the influent together with the groundwater will be analyzed. This empirical information can be utilized together with existing water quality of recipient lake and wetlands to evaluate the impacts. Economic assessment and impacts in this frame will be done via empirical cost estimates and comparing to alternative solutions typically applied in Lappeenranta.

All four solutions have novelty for the city of Lappeenranta. Some of the solutions are the first to be built and innovations regarding how building should be done and planned have already been gained. The measurement campaign has the potential to provide plenty of novel innovations. Furthermore, the processed data and real time information about water quality can be distributed to the public through citizen application to increase awareness of climate change adaptation.

The solutions are designed in such a way that enables them to be implemented in an urban environment at different scales. The city of Lappeenranta intends to continue developing these solutions based on the experience gained from TransformAr.

4.0. Oristano – COAST and Smart Gate

Executive summary

In Oristano (Sardinia), TransformAr is actively working on two transformative projects—the Coastal Contract (COAST) and the Nature-Based Solutions (NBS) initiative—aimed at addressing climate change and environmental challenges.

The COAST is a comprehensive governance tool designed for the integrated management of wetlands, aiming to address the fragmentation of local governance, mitigate the natural and anthropogenic impacts and improve ecological conditions. . COAST has been signed in 2021 by 11 Municipalities of the Gulf of Oristano, the Province, the Oristano Reclamation Consortium and the Regional Government. It places a strong focus on social impact by organizing participatory meetings that enhance community knowledge and awareness. These gatherings not only engage diverse segments of the population but also highlight the project's success in promoting sustainability and adaptability. The COAST initiative under TransformAr develop an active and strong community engagement; it employs factsheets to disseminate crucial information extending beyond the project's initial scope and contributing to regional replicability. A key component of COAST is the Local Wetland Observatory (LWO), whose scope is to monitor the wetlands' status and trends and share the knowledge achieved to raise awareness and support decision making processes.

The second solution is the implementation of a SMART GATE and a monitoring system which are part of Nature-Based Solutions (NBS) focused on the restoration of the wetland system of Marceddì and San Giovanni (Sardinia). The NBS enhances understanding of key water quality parameters, supporting long-term assessments and improving water circulation management. The impacts encompass environmental, economic, social, and technological dimensions. This not only bolsters the lagoon's flood regulation capacity, thereby reducing economic losses (in particular for the fishing sector) and minimizing cultural heritage damage but also fosters social synergies among public organizations. Furthermore, the technological advancements introduced by the Smart Gate (SG) system ensure efficiency, precision, and reliability in managing water flow within the lagoon as a prototype replicable within the lagoon and in other areas with similar problems.

The active involvement of local stakeholders, especially public authorities and the fishing sector, from the NBS development to its implementation and management, ensures the solutions' efficacy and efficiency to face the ongoing environmental challenges and improve climate resilience in the region.

4.1. Context

Infographic

Objectives

There is abundant literature predicting the effects of climate change on ecosystems' functions and species' ranges (Junk et al., 2013; Moomaw et al., 2018). However, climate change models are rarely incorporated into restoration and conservation plans because they are not developed at the spatial and temporal scales used by territorial planners and environmental managers (Gitay et al., 2011). Therefore, the aim of TransformAr in Oristano is to demonstrate how the protection and conservation of coastal wetlands, achieved through effective governance and nature-based solutions, can significantly mitigate the impacts of climate change on local communities and the environment.

The specific objectives of the TransformAr's solutions are to:

- inform key stakeholders on the potential role of healthy coastal wetlands in mitigating climate change impacts;
- raise awareness on the efficacy of COAST and LWO to support wetland managers and planners into decision-making processes and developing successful adaptation actions
- improve the scientific knowledge on the status of Marceddì and San Giovanni wetlands for planning opportune mitigation actions in case of critical conditions of the lagoon;
- test a technological and replicable model to increase the water quality and the hydro-geological dynamics and reduce the loss of habitats and species;
- limit areas damaged by both coastal and inland floods, resulting in reduced economic losses and cultural heritage damage;

- create synergies between regional and local administrators for an integrated and coordinated wetland water management.

Geographical description

The coastal area of Oristano (Sardinia, Italy) is a complex and high-density system of rivers, lagoons, and salt marshes. Most of the wetlands are shallow eutrophic water bodies (approximately 0.5-2 m depth), around 7,700 hectares of which (over 60% of Sardinia's wetlands) are protected the Ramsar convention⁴ and the Natura 2000 network⁵. The Gulf of Oristano is characterized by the tight integration between the existing settlement structure and the environment characterized by the system of coastal wetlands. It is a low-density area, characterized by small concentrated urban zones, most of them located in the inland areas, and sprawl urbanization related to fishing cooperatives, agricultural and livestock farms and small touristic villages located along the coast (Satta, 2014).

The population of the 11 municipalities located in the area, around 85 thousand in 2022, is decreasing as people are moving to the main cities of the island or to the north of the country mainly driven by more employment opportunities. The rivers and wetlands are amongst the most fish-rich inland areas of Sardinia, possibly in the entire Mediterranean, and they also hold significant cultural heritage value. In several ponds and lagoons, there are operating fishing cooperatives and some aquaculture production, often derived from traditional practices.

⁴ The “Convention on Wetlands of International Importance especially as Waterfowl Habitat”, signed in Ramsar (Iran) in 1971, which represent the intergovernmental treaty that provides the framework for the conservation and wide use of wetlands and their resources. <https://www.ramsar.org/>

⁵ The network of nature sites nature sites protected by EU legislation. Natura 2000 is the largest coordinated network of protected areas in the world. https://environment.ec.europa.eu/topics/nature-and-biodiversity/natura-2000_en

Figure 16 - General map of the Gulf of Oristano

The southern wetlands of the Gulf are the Marceddi-San Giovanni lagoon compendium, which appears as a deep marine inlet artificially separated from the sea by a fishpond bridge and divided into two different wetlands: the Marceddi lagoon (900 ha), closer to the sea with brackish water, and the internal pond of San Giovanni (700 ha), characterized by freshwater inputs from the rivers Rio Mogoro, Rio Mannu, Rio Sitzerri, and from some artificial canals.

Figure 17 - Zoom on the wetland of the NBS implementation

The surrounding territory is dominated by the agricultural plain of Arborea on the north-east side, an expanse of regular fields bordered by the reclamation infrastructure (canals and roads), while to the west it is surrounded by the mountainous complex of Monte Arcuentu. The fishing activities in the Marceddi-San Giovanni lagoon are managed by the Consortium Coop. Riunite della pesca di Marceddi. The concession, granted by the Autonomous Region of Sardinia under the act rep. 1082/98 dated 07/07/1998, is currently renewed. Covering an area of 2610 ha, the fishing operations involve around 140 operators. Hydraulic interventions carried out in recent decades have significantly altered the original structure of the entire wetland system. These modifications have disrupted the natural water exchange conditions between marine and freshwater environments, leading to changes in the ecological conditions of the area due to sediment discharge into the water and impacting on the ongoing fishing activities.

Figure 18 - Landscape of the Marceddi Wetland

Figure 19 - Landscape of the Marceddi Wetland

Figure 20 - Fishpond bridge that separates Marceddi wetland from the sea

Figure 21 - Extreme flooding event in the area

Climate vulnerability, impacts and challenges

Sardinia is located in the center of the Mediterranean region, and according to EEA (2017), is likely to be impacted by several climate forces that include, among others: sea level rise, an increase of maximum temperatures and heatwaves especially during summer; long drought periods interrupted by heavy and extreme rainfall events leading to severe floods, and extreme storm events causing coastal flooding.

Droughts during summer are often associated with greater water demand from different competing sectors, leading to inter-sectorial conflicts and unsustainable overexploitation of water resources. Consequences of severe droughts have been particularly relevant with risks for limited freshwater supplies and the incurrence of large fires affecting not only forest ecosystems, but also rural/urban interfaces and the increase of coastal erosion risk and desertification. Flooding is a particularly crucial risk not only endangering human life and infrastructures, but also causing soil erosion and the transport of contaminants from industrial, mining and agriculture fields to natural and especially aquatic ecosystems.

Changes in climatic conditions can alter agricultural productivity, in terms of quantity and quality of agricultural products, water supply and the hydrological regime, with implications for water resources availability. Increases in irrigation requirements are expected for the main crops cultivated in Sardinia

because of climate change. Moreover, water demand increases could derive from socio-economic changes (tourism, agri-food, and textile sectors, energy plants, agricultural settlements), urbanization and lifestyle changes, causing a serious concern.

Focusing on the Gulf of Oristano, the coastal area faces a significant threat from inland flooding, especially during extreme rainfall events combined with marine storms. This endangers the population, infrastructure, and the local economic activities.

The Gulf is characterized by its low-lying areas, which make it highly vulnerable to the impacts of rising sea levels, coastal and inland flooding. Despite the high susceptibility of low-lying coastal zones to these hazards, the overall vulnerability of the region is mitigated by the robust ecosystem health and efficient drainage density, enhancing its resilience.

Given the influence of climate change on the Gulf's water system and current patterns, an increase in water temperature in all seasons, a decline of winter salinity, pH levels dropping (acidification), and an increase in the presence of non-native species, among other effects. Looking ahead to the medium to long term (50 to 100 years), there is a likelihood of certain coastal lagoons disappearing due to rising sea levels. These changes will have adverse effects on the local flora and fauna and the distribution of fishing stocks, particularly concerning commercially relevant aquatic organisms. The full extent of these impacts on local socio-economic conditions remains difficult to predict.

The traditional aquaculture activities are and will be significantly impacted by the extreme rainfall events that disrupt the balance between saltwater and freshwater in the lagoons, causing sediment deposits that impede water circulation. The alteration of parameters such as salinity, Ph, dissolved oxygen, turbidity is linked to a change in the state of the ecosystem and a decrease in fish stocks. The alteration of the water quality can increase the presence and proliferation of invasive species which pose a threat to native species and reduce ecosystem services.

The solutions implemented within the TransformAr project focus on three Key Community Systems: Water Systems, Nature Conservation, and fisheries, which are vulnerable to climate impacts and are strictly related and positively influenced by COAST and SG.

The conditions of biodiversity and habitats, already affected by intensive land use activities (agriculture, animal husbandry, industry, and mining), along with the hydraulic efficiency of the wetlands and river dynamics, are severely impacted by climate hazards such as coastal and inland flooding, coastal erosion, wetland and groundwater salinization.

Coastal receptors, including beaches, river mouths, wetlands, terrestrial biological systems, and protected areas, are all affected by habitat degradation, biodiversity loss, and the emergence of alien and invasive species. Moreover, alterations in water quality influence fish stocks, leading to a reduction in fishermen's income. Extended drought periods could lead to increased water demand from wells or, where possible, a request for public water, which would then increase costs for farmers.

Based on this information the Risk components (hazards, exposure, vulnerability) were assessed in the pathways workshop. What have been highlighted by the participants is that the main drivers related to climate change are the increase of temperatures and the changes in precipitation patterns, appearing as a general reduction of the rainy season and a concentration of heavy precipitation in short periods. These drivers are generating impacts such as flooding, drought and storm phenomena that are exposing the communities, territories, and local economic activities to a risk of important economic and environmental losses.

Figure 22 - Risk chain of Oristano demo

State-of-the-art on adaptation in the demonstrator

Adaptation governance at the national level

The [Italian Climate Adaptation Strategy](#) was adopted in June 2015 and targets several sector in its action on adaptation such as: water resources; desertification, soil degradation and drought; hydrogeological risks; biodiversity and ecosystems; health; forestry; agriculture, aquaculture, marine fishery; energy; coastal zones; tourism; urban settlements; and critical infrastructures.

As listed in the [Italian country fiche](#), to develop the NAS, the following background documents were prepared:

- A national climate impact and vulnerability assessment of the national sectors
- An analysis of the European and national policy framework for climate adaptation
- Elements for a strategy document: 'Elementi per una Strategia Nazionale di Adattamento ai Cambiamenti Climatici' (ESNACC). A public consultation process on its contents was closed in January 2014.

The NAS provides guidance on how to address climate change in diverse socio-economic sectors and systems and it aims to: “raise awareness on the impacts of climate change; identify vulnerabilities and adaptation options for relevant natural and socio-economic systems, and describe opportunities that may be associated to climate change; promote participation of stakeholders in defining strategies and sectoral adaptation plans to make later implementation more effective; increase awareness about climate change risks and adaptation through a range of communication activities; specify methods to be used to identify the best options for adaptation actions while highlighting the co-benefits” (Grantham Research institute, 2022).

In 2017 Italy approved the [Piano Nazionale di Adattamento ai Cambiamenti Climatici](#) (PNACC) (National Adaptation Plan - NAP) to support the implementation of the National Adaptation Strategy. The Directorate General for Climate and Energy of the Ministry for the Environment and Energy Security (MASE) developed the NAP (while preparatory work was done by national, regional and local institutions, as well as research centres). and it seeks to guide ministries, regions and local authorities to mainstream adaptation criteria into policymaking.

Adaptation governance at the regional level

Local authorities, regions, and central government, coordinated by the MASE, are expected to implement the NAS through specific adaptation plans. In 2016, the Institute for Environmental Protection and Research (ISPRA, 2016) carried out a survey on the development of climate adaptation strategies (and plans) at the regional level. The results saw that around 50% of regions (e.g., Sardinia, Calabria, Apulia) recognised the importance and multi-sectoral nature of adaptation in their governance models. As summarised in the [Italian country fiche](#), some other regions were reviewing their regulatory measures (e.g., EIA) and planning tools (e.g. EU Structural Funds) to better integrate adaptation (e.g. Abruzzo, Molise), while other regions were promoting adaptation at the local level by supporting cities and municipalities who have joined the Covenant of Mayors for Climate and Energy (CoM), as territorial coordinators (e.g. Lazio, Abruzzo). The Lombardy Region has now approved its Regional Adaptation Strategy, and Sardinia has developed a [Regional Adaptation Strategy to Climate Change \(RASCC\)](#) to (1) assess climate vulnerability and risk, (2) identify adaptation options, and (3) define a governance system for including adaption in regional plans and programmes (Spano et al., 2019) and stimulate tailored responses to specific local needs.

Key elements of the Sardinia RASCC include:

- Identifying the primary weather-induced hazard indicators based on the analysis of current and future climate conditions at a high spatial resolution.
- Assessing territorial adaptability through the development of a methodology and the collection of indicators for calculating the aggregate adaptability capacity index.
- Evaluating the impacts of future climate change on strategic sectors for the Sardinia region, using the latest scientific methodologies, particularly those of the IPCC (AR5, 2014), including the aggregation of specific indicators.
- Selecting priority adaptation strategies by identifying and defining priority actions based on the identified impacts of climate change.
- Identifying governance models for the implementation of adaptation measures.
- Providing detailed indicators and related metadata, collected in the Regional Environmental Information System (SIRA), to support governance decisions in the implementation of adaptation actions.

The regional strategy has been developed based on the five strategic axes of action proposed by the National Strategy for Climate Change Adaptation (SNACC):

- Enhancing current knowledge about climate change and its impacts.
- Describing the territory's vulnerabilities, adaptation options, and any associated opportunities.
- Promoting participation and increasing awareness, including integrating adaptation into sector-specific policies.
- Supporting awareness and information dissemination on adaptation.
- Specifying the tools to be used for identifying the best options for adaptation actions.

The RASCC recognizes *governance* as a key factor in shaping the adaptation process, since effective adaptation to climate change requires new approaches across all regional and local administrative levels and sectors. In line with the European and national strategies, this strategy emphasizes the importance of active involvement of local authorities in promoting adaptation actions and objectives related to climate change, considering the significant variations in impacts and effects on different areas of the region. Highlighting the importance of the development and implementation of new policies dedicated to adaptation to climate change, the strategy suggests preventing environmental risks through the promotion of specific policies for the integrated management of water resources (rivers, wetlands, etc.) at a district or basin scale, also in partnership with private stakeholders.

Indeed, in recent years, climate change adaptation topics have started to permeate environmental planning and policies with increasing awareness and effectiveness. Below is a list of the main regional or local territorial planning and management tools that address climate-related issues and adaptation measures.

SCALE	PLANNING AND MANAGEMENT TOOLS	POLICY AREAS
Region	PAI - Piano Stralcio per l'Assetto Idrogeologico (Hydrogeological Management Plan)	The PAI serves as the primary knowledge, regulatory, and technical-operational tool for planning actions related to soil conservation, defense, and enhancement, as well as the prevention of hydrogeological risks, including the mapping of flood-prone areas. This planning is based on the physical and environmental characteristics of the regional territory.
	PGRA - Piano di Gestione del Rischio di Alluvioni (Flood Risk Management Plan)	The PGRA is the reference document for the management of flood risk, encompassing prevention and protection measures, as well as operational tools and governance mechanisms. Its purpose is to reduce the impacts on human life, the environment, cultural heritage, and economic and social activities
	PGDI - Piano di Gestione del Distretto idrografico (Management Plan of the hydrographic district)	PGDI is the operational and management tool to implement a coherent and sustainable water protection policy
	(SRSvS) - Strategia Regionale per lo Sviluppo Sostenibile (Regional strategy for Sustainable Development)	The strategy assesses various aspects of sustainability in our societies, from health and well-being to quality education, from ensuring decent work and economic growth to combating climate change and identifies specific goals and actions that create measurable impacts.
Local	Management Plan of Natura 2000 sites	Reference document for the site-specific conservation objectives and measures
	COAST – Coastal Contract	A voluntary act of shared commitment to improve the protection and implement an integrated management of the wetlands of the Gulf of Oristano (Ramsar and Natura 2000 sites).
	Piano Di Protezione Civile Per Rischio Idraulico	A practical tool for everyone to be used by who will be directly involved in emergency management
	PAESC - Piano d'Azione per l'Energia Sostenibile e il Clima (Action Plan for Sustainable Energy and Climate)	The program through which local authorities plan their actions to achieve the objectives set by the Covenant of Mayors for Climate and Energy (reduce CO2 emissions, increase energy efficiency and use of renewable energy sources, etc.)

Table 8 - Planning and management tools at Regional and local level related to CC

Adaptation governance at the demonstrator level

Wetland management in Oristano is challenging. The fragmented governmental responsibilities impede the timely implementation of actions. The various types of protected areas, such as RAMSAR, Natura 2000 sites, Important Bird Areas (IBA) and Marine Protected Areas (MPA) are managed by different governance instruments and different public bodies, while in reality they are part of the same coastal system. The need for better coordination and communication among the various levels of governance, the need for more active involvement of local communities and the need for adaptive management led to the coastal contract, as a more unified and flexible governance model.

4.2. Description of solutions in TransformAr

In Oristano, TransformAr will focus on two solutions: a governance solution for improving wetland management, and a NBS to restore and protect the lagoon and enhance the natural role of the wetland.

The Coastal Contract

Healthy and properly managed wetlands act as natural reservoirs that sequester atmospheric CO₂, can serve as natural water retention areas during extreme climatic events. In order to enhance the integrated management of the wetlands in line with the objectives of the RASCC, the 11 Municipalities of the Gulf of Oristano, along with the Province, the Oristano Reclamation Consortium and the Regional Government, have undertaken significant achievement of this process with the signature of the Coastal Contract in 2021. This voluntary agreement aims to improve the ecological condition of water systems by implementing proactive measures. These measures are designed to mitigate the negative impacts of human activities, enhance water quality and circulation, and increase resilience to climate change.

The signatories form the Coordination Group, the institutional body responsible for political decision-making and the strategic direction, which is supported by the Technical Secretariat for the implementation of the Contract.

The Action Plan of the Contract contains projects at different scales and covers the following topics:

- Participatory territorial governance and capacity building;
- Improvement of the ecological status of water systems;
- Protection of biodiversity and natural heritage;
- Landscape requalification and enhancement of cultural heritage;
- Green economy - towards a sustainable and responsible territorial development model;
- Strengthening resilience by addressing climate change;
- Communication and environmental awareness.

Some of the activities outlined in the Action Plan have already secured funding and will be implemented in the coming years, while others are still awaiting financial coverage. Being part of the Action Plan allows for preferential access to new funding opportunities, either through the Region's new financial programming or through new regional and national calls.

Within the **TransformAr project**, MEDSEA is playing a strategic role in scaling up and consolidating the Coastal Contract as an operational tool to promote wetland conservation and adaptation across Oristano Gulf. Several key activities have been carried out under TransformAr to support this goal:

1. Strengthening Participatory Governance

A **structured and inclusive participatory process** has been activated to foster broader and more active engagement from local stakeholders—including public authorities, fishing and farming communities, tourism operators, and civil society. This process aims to ensure that all actors contribute to shaping shared strategies for wetland protection and climate adaptation, reinforcing the legitimacy and ownership of the Contract.

2. Development of the Local Wetland Observatory (LWO)

One of the most significant contributions of TransformAr is the creation of the **Local Wetland Observatory**, a key action foreseen in the Contract's Action Plan. The LWO serves as a scientific and technical hub dedicated to:

- Monitoring the ecological status and trends of wetlands in the Gulf of Oristano;
- Identifying emerging threats and evaluating the effectiveness of conservation and adaptation actions;
- Producing data-driven reports, maps, and factsheets to inform decision-making.

Staffed by a multidisciplinary team with high scientific expertise, the LWO integrates data from both public and private sources and collaborates closely with the Technical Secretariat to ensure that scientific insights directly support the implementation and monitoring of the Contract.

3. Knowledge Sharing and Policy Support

TransformAr has facilitated the dissemination of the LWO's outputs to public institutions, private actors, and local communities, contributing to:

- **Informed policymaking**, thanks to up-to-date scientific data that supports wetland management and climate resilience strategies;
- **Increased stakeholder awareness and engagement**, recognizing wetlands as essential to the area's cultural and ecological identity;
- **Capacity building and advocacy**, enabling communities to co-develop a shared vision for the territory and collaborate on sustainable development opportunities.

Moreover, by supporting the replicability of the Coastal Contract model in other Sardinian coastal areas, TransformAr contributes to scaling up good practices for climate adaptation and wetland protection across the region.

The Smart Gate and Nature-Based Solution

Among the wetlands included in COAST there is the Marceddì lagoon and the San Giovanni pond, which represent a complex and articulated transitional ecosystem between the hydraulic and coastal marine environments, whose functionality is crucial in flood and storm control, climate resilience, and the maintenance of biodiversity.

From an ecological, geomorphological, and sedimentological perspective, the critical issues of the San Giovanni - Marceddì lagoon and pond system, with evident implications for the environment and productivity, can be detailed as follows:

- Disruption of water exchanges to and from the sea (including natural daily tidal flows) and limitations on the distribution towards the open sea of finer sediment fractions and suspended materials due to the construction of the Marceddì bridge. This aspect has led to the deterioration

of water quality in the lagoon and its productivity, as well as widespread problems of poor oxygenation and water turnover between adjacent basins and the sea. (see the 8.2 Baseline data for more detail).

- Progressive silting of the internal basin of San Giovanni resulting from the construction of the embankment and the interception of continental water flows. While representing a crucial condition for the development of fish farming in the lagoon, the clear separation provided by the internal embankment between freshwater areas at the estuary and the rest of the lagoon leads to a gradual reduction in the depth of the estuarine basin, a decrease in flood buffering capacity, and the development of phenomena of anoxia related to limited water exchanges, especially during the summer season. (see the 8.2 Baseline data for more detail).

In an attempt to address the highlighted issues, a NBS is partially under development with multi-financing, including support from the European Regional Development Fund (ERDF) under the 6.5.1 action, managed by the Municipality of Terralba, and the development of a SMART GATE under the TransformAr project.

Figure 23 - Masterplan of ongoing and future interventions

The masterplan (Fig. 23) shows the set of interventions, some of which are already financed, while others are part of a broader configuration still awaiting funding (more details in the map legend).

- Equip the existing embankment within the San Giovanni Pond with an intelligent system of gates, the opening and closing of which can be remotely controlled. . While one gate is being tested within the TransformAr project, the installation of the other gates is planned but currently unfunded and will proceed only if additional funding becomes available. The use of the existing embankment also appears to be functional for flood management and for the utilization of the reservoir for water regulation and storage purposes. The embankment should be easily passable by floods, even for $Tr=50$ years, and the gates will act as overflow thresholds in the case of lower return period events
- Adapt the Marceddì bridge sheet piling to enable effective water connection between the sea and the lagoon. The positioning of the hydrometers, under TransformAr, is therefore aimed at understanding and controlling the hydraulic interaction between inflowing watercourses, sea and the water body, both seasonal and exceptional, functional to the use of the water surface for regulation purposes, and the efficiency of the phyto-depuration capacity of the wetland sector.
- Arrange the internal embankment (closure of gaps) and removal of the existing embankment partitions which do not permit the communication among areas. The internal embankment,

separated from the main basins, could function as a genuine filtering ecosystem by increasing its natural purification capacity. (ERDF funds)

- Creation of buffer zone with rows of trees and shrubs along the inner banks of the pond of San Giovanni and Corru S'Ittiri. (ERDF funds)

Figure 24 - Map of the ongoing projects in the area (ERDF funds)

The TransformAr solution focuses on testing the functionality of the SMART GATE with a remote control and installing a monitoring system into the lagoon with the aim of improving the current challenges with synergic, efficient, and participative managing of lamination lagoon problems, due to climate changes, and fishing practices, due to general faunal pauperization.

The SMART GATE has the aim of regulating the water circulation between the mouth area and San Giovanni Pond, to guarantee the better condition in terms of ecological parameters and control the hydraulic levels. In a state of equilibrium, the SMART GATE will remain closed and will be opened only in the event of hydraulic risk or alteration of the chemical-physical state of the water, thus allowing a flow of freshwater from the mouth areas of various rivers and canals into the pond.

Figure 25 - Positioning of the monitoring stations

The TransformAr solution incorporates the use of hydrometers and multi-parameter sensors to measure various factors such as pH levels, conductivity, redox potential, temperature, dissolved oxygen levels, turbidity, and hydrometric levels. A weather station will be integrated to support civil protection weather warning systems and enhance our understanding of weather conditions during SMART GATE operations. The monitoring instruments, positioned in the most important areas of the lagoon, will be useful to set up the conceptual model which regulate the opening and closing of the SG. The conceptual model will consider variables related to flood risk (hydrometric level) and the ecological state of the lagoon, with a significant emphasis on fishing activities (salinity, pH, temperature, etc.). Thresholds for each parameter will be determined based on an analysis of the initial conditions and the optimal ecological conditions for the species inhabiting the lagoon.

Figure 26 - SMART GATE intervention

The SMART GATE operating model (when, how, in which condition the SMART GATE must be opened or closed) will be tested with a preliminary set up and, following the installation of the monitoring system, must be reviewed and will involve public authorities responsible for water quality, flood risk, and ecological conditions. Furthermore, the fishing sector will be actively engaged in the process to consider their requirements and share scientific insights, fostering a collaborative and mutually beneficial approach.

Figure 27 – Technical scheme of the SMART GATE

Figure 28 - Electric actuator with lever for manual movement

Technical characteristics:

Within TransformAr it will be installed 3 monitoring stations. Each station (a, b, c) is connected to a multi-channel datalogger, which collects, stores, and transmits data to the IT platform that communicates with the SMART GATE.

Here is the list of the monitoring instruments that MEDSEA is planning to install:

a) **monitoring station Marceddi lagoon composed by:**

- Weather station (Timing, Humidity, Wind speed, Wind direction, Rainfall intensity, Rainfall height, Temperature)
- Hydrometer (Piezometric level sensor with Immersion) **(internal)**
- Hydrometer (Piezometric level sensor with Immersion) **(external)**
- Dedicated data logger

b) **monitoring station San Giovanni Pond (SMART GATE area):**

- N.2 - multiparameter sensor (Dissolved oxygen level, Conductivity, pH, ORP, Temperature, turbidity)
- Hydrometer (Piezometric level sensor with Immersion)
- Dedicated data logger

c) monitoring station San Giovanni Pond (mouth area):

- N.1 multiparameter sensor (Dissolved oxygen level, Conductivity, pH, ORP, Temperature, turbidity)
- Hydrometer (Piezometric level sensor with Immersion)
- Dedicated data logger

The instrumentation will be IP68 rated. All instruments will be resistant to the conditions of a marine environment.

The devices will have uplink and downlink features. The remote communication must allow to:

1. Restart the sensors.
2. Change the frequency of acquisition on demand.

The autonomy of the data acquisition unit should be at least 12 months. The sensors will be powered by a solar panel.

The opening and closing of the SMART GATE will be managed remotely through the IT platform in most cases, or physically if required.

Figure 29 - monitoring network and IT platform operation diagram

Description the expected innovation

COAST and SMART GATE introduce innovative approaches to ecosystem management in the wetland areas of Oristano. They emphasize proactive measures and integrated governance, which represents a novel way to address environmental issues. The LWO serves as an innovative tool for real-time monitoring of wetland status and trends. The application of SMART GATE technology to regulate water circulation demonstrates innovation in water resource management within the ecosystem.

The SMART GATE enables efficient and timely responses to changes in hydraulic levels, ecological conditions, and water quality. The remote-control system improves the effectiveness of water regulation and contributes to flood risk management, allowing for precise monitoring and control of the ecosystem with a significant focus on environmental conditions and fishery requirements.

Furthermore, both solutions aim to foster a collaborative approach by involving public authorities responsible for water quality, flood risk, and ecological conditions, along with engagement with the fishing sector. This collaborative approach is innovative as it brings together various stakeholders to collectively address environmental challenges.

4.3. Expected impacts

Overview of the expected impacts and related indicators

Expected impacts in the implementation of the two solutions differ on a territorial scale for COAST and a more local scale for NBS (Marceddì and San Giovanni).

The COAST project generates various impacts across different domains:

Social Impact

The project places a significant emphasis on social impact, aiming to enhance knowledge and awareness within the community. This is achieved through a series of participatory meetings involving stakeholders. The number of these meetings serves as a key indicator of the project's success in engaging different segments of the population.

Technological and Economic Impact

In terms of technology transfer and economic sustainability, the COAST project leverages factsheets to disseminate crucial information. These materials reach a broad audience, including individuals and managers, extending the project's influence beyond its initial scope. This dissemination contributes to the replicability of COAST practices on a regional scale, showcasing the project's technological and economic impact.

Social and Economic Influence on Local Policies

The active involvement of public authorities in the COAST project is a testament to its social influence. This commitment is reflected in the ongoing updates to the Local Wetland Observatory (LWO), demonstrating an economic investment in the monitoring and management of local wetlands. Together, these social and economic factors play a pivotal role in shaping and conditioning local policies.

An additional measure of the project's success is the resilience of the local population. This indicator spans environmental, social, and economic dimensions, reflecting the overall effectiveness of the COAST project in fostering sustainability and adaptability within the community.

Regarding the SG and the overall NBS project for the Marceddì and San Giovanni lagoon, reference is made to environmental, economic, social, and technological impacts.

Environmental Impacts

An important environmental impact of the project is the increased knowledge of key water quality parameters, facilitating a long-term assessment of parameter improvements compared to the initial state. The implementation of Nature-Based Solutions (NBS) contributes to better water circulation management within the lagoon. This enhancement increases the ecosystem's flood regulation capacity, reducing areas damaged by coastal and inland floods and subsequently minimizing economic losses and cultural heritage damage. An additional positive consequence is the potential increase in fish catches both in terms of quantity and quality. It's essential to note that this impact is influenced by external factors, and its evaluation as a secondary indicator is necessary.

Social Impacts

In the implementation of NBS, it is considered important to highlight two aspects regarding social impacts:

Creation of Synergies:

The project fosters synergies among organizations with expertise in water management and climate change. This collaboration enhances the social fabric by bringing together diverse stakeholders to address shared challenges.

Influence on Policies:

NBS influences local policies, such as the COAST and wetland management plans, and extends its impact to the regional level with contributions to the Regional Strategy on Climate Change Adaptation. This showcases the broader societal influence of the project beyond its immediate implementation.

Technological Impacts

The implementation of the Smart Gate (SG) system introduces technological advancements, testing a conceptual model for regulating SG openings and closures. This model relies on reference parameters collected through the monitoring network installed in the lagoon. The technological impact is evaluated based on:

- Efficiency: The response time to hydraulic variations is a key measure of the system's efficiency, ensuring a timely and effective response to dynamic conditions.
- Control Precision: Precision in controlling openings/closures is assessed, emphasizing the importance of accurate water flow management within the lagoon.
- System Reliability: The reliability of the SG system is a critical factor, determining the consistent and dependable operation of the water control system.

The following table summarizes the expected impact and the related indicators:

SOLUTION	EXPECTED IMPACTS	INDICATORS	SOURCE
COAST	1. Increased knowledge and awareness of key stakeholders at different levels (public and private sectors, economic categories, citizens, etc.)	1. Number participatory meetings with stakeholders	List of meetings
		2. Population that became more resilient	Stakeholder map
	2. Replicability on regional scale of the COAST experience	3. People/managers reached by the factsheet to disseminate COAST at regional level	Stakeholder map
	3. Local policies conditioned by the COAST and NBS implementation as best practice	4. Public authorities actively involved in the project	Stakeholder map
		5. Number of reports and factsheets produced and shared by the LWO	LWO and TransformAr webpage

NBS	4. Increased knowledge of main water quality parameters	6. Data collected and analyzed through the monitoring system	IT platform and monitoring system
		7. Fishermen informed on the knowledge acquired	Minutes of the meetings with fishermen and surveys Agreements signed GIS analysis
	5. Improvement of the biodiversity and ecosystem integrity	8. Surface covered by NBS	
	6.Reduction of economic losses and cultural damage		LWO reports
	7. Increased efficiency of the lagoon dynamics in case of flood risk (hydrometric level) and poor ecological state of the lagoon, with a significant emphasis on fishing activities (salinity, pH, temperature...)	9. Enhancement of the water quality	IT platform and monitoring system
		10. Response time to hydraulic variations	IT platform and monitoring system
		11. Accuracy of aperture/closure control	IT platform
		12. System reliability	IT platform

Table 9 - Expected impacts and indicators

Note: KPI 8 – Improvement of Stock Productivity

This indicator, which relies on data from the Regional Department of Agriculture and Agro-Pastoral Reform – Fisheries and Aquaculture Service, could not be evaluated within the current reporting period due to **delays in the implementation timeline of the solution**. Specifically, the interventions impacting aquatic stock conditions (e.g., habitat restoration or water quality improvement) were not in place long enough to generate measurable biological responses in stock productivity.

Definition and Interpretation:

Stock productivity refers to the **reproductive output and biomass increase** of aquatic species in the monitored wetland or coastal ecosystem. It is typically assessed using fishery yield data (e.g., CPUE – catch per unit effort), species growth rates, or population surveys conducted before and after the intervention.

In this case, evaluation would have required a **minimum post-intervention monitoring period of 12–18 months**, covering reproductive and growth cycles. Since this condition was not met, the indicator remains unevaluable at this stage. Future assessments can revisit this KPI once sufficient biological response time has elapsed.

Baseline data⁶

MEDSEA collected some preliminary data in the lagoon (before the implementation period of TransformAr), as preliminary studies for the drafting of the project jointly with the Municipality of Terralba.

The comprehensive baseline data presented below is essential for understanding the rationale behind the development and implementation of Nature Based Solutions (NBS), encompassing various impacts such as enhanced knowledge of water quality parameters, biodiversity and ecosystem integrity improvement, reduction of economic losses and cultural damage, and increased efficiency in lagoon dynamics during flood risks and ecological challenges, particularly focusing on fishing activities.

Bathymetry:

Bathymetric survey, covering an area of approximately 830 hectares:

Maximum depth reached: -3.68 meters below mean sea level (m.m.s.l.).

Minimum depth reached: -0.11 meters below mean sea level (m.m.s.l.).

⁶ Source of data: Analysis within the “Integrated project for the redevelopment of ecological connections of the wetland compendium of S. Giovanni - Marceddì and the pond of Corru S'Ittiri”, managed by the Municipality of Terralba and developed by the project team composed by Criteria srl, Prima Ingegneria and Macro Design Studio.

Figure 30 - Digital Elevation Model (DEM)

Water temperature (°C):

Figure 31 – Water temperature Summer period

Figure 32 – Water temperature Autumn period

pH

Observing the figure below, it can be noted that the pH follows a clear spatial gradient. Specifically, the San Giovanni basin, and even more so the basins near the mouths of watercourses, exhibit significantly higher values (up to pH=9) compared to the mouth area. In the autumn campaign, the values show greater homogeneity.

Figure 33 – PH summer period

Figure 34 – Ph Autumn period

Chlorophyll 'a':

The indicator describes the concentration of chlorophyll "a" in surface waters, allowing for an indirect estimate of phytoplankton biomass, as it provides a measure of the main photosynthetic pigment present in microalgae. It serves as an effective indicator of the system's productivity. The concentration of chlorophyll "a" in water highlights the level of eutrophication in coastal waters. It is of fundamental importance for the application of trophic indices and turbidity indices, assessing the trophic characteristics of the water body and the state of ecosystems. Additionally, it is an excellent indicator for evaluating primary production and the trophic levels of the ecosystem.

Figure 35 – Chlorophyll – Summer period

Figure 36 - Chlorophyll – Autumn period

Turbidity

Figure 37 – Turbidity Summer period

Figure 38 – Turbidity Autumn period

Salinity (PSU):

The parameter of surface salinity shows a clear gradient from the estuarine area toward the mouth of the lagoon. The autumn survey confirmed the salinity gradient, which decreases linearly from the mouth area to the barriers separating the Marceddì and San Giovanni basins. In contrast, a sharp drop is observed, even more pronounced in sectors internal to the embankment near the mouths of watercourses.

Figure 39 – Salinity summer period

Figure 40 – Salinity autumn period

Dissolved oxygen:

The percentage of **dissolved oxygen** plays a crucial role as it is closely related to the water regime and the presence of algae and aquatic macrophytes, as well as the decomposition of organic matter by bacterial communities. This parameter varies between 53% and 137% saturation and generally assumes oversaturation values (O.D.% > 100) in the spring, as a result of the photosynthetic activity of phytoplankton and aquatic plants and algae in general.

Spatial analysis of the data highlights a spatial trend between the estuarine area and the mouth area of the lagoon. The autumnal period shows greater homogeneity in dissolved oxygen values, with a decrease observed only near the mouth of the Rio Mogoro.

Figure 41 – Dissolved oxygen summer period

Figure 42 – Dissolved oxygen autumn period

Fish productivity

The historical catch records from Consortium Coop. Riunite della pesca di Marceddì (2015-2017) are averagely 9,000 kg of fish, 136,000 kg of mollusks, and 65 kg of crustaceans per year. The targeted species include sea bream, mullets, sea bass, clams, and heart clams. Bivalve mollusks are the most extensively caught species within these two water mirrors. Notably, the lagoon is also monitored for invasive alien species, such as *Mnemiopsis leidyi* and *Callinectes sapidus*.

The Fishing consortium must communicate the data about type and number of fishing species to the Regional Department of Agriculture and Agro-Pastoral Reform - Fisheries and Aquaculture Service.

The data available are related to the following years 2015-2016-2017, but MEDSEA will request also data from 2018 to 2022 to have a deep knowledge of the trend.

Approach to monitor impacts

COAST aims to actively engage public and private stakeholders, citizens, and various economic categories. Monitoring occurs through:

- Continuous Dialogue through periodic meetings, workshops, and discussion forums to foster dialogue and participation.
- Participation Indicators: Measurement of engagement through participation in COAST-related events.
- Awareness Surveys: Periodic surveys to assess stakeholders' understanding of COAST principles.

The impact of the NBS will be evaluated considering, as reference for comparison, the condition of the lagoon registered in August 2021 when the first set of parameters were collected.

Overall, the impact of the NBS will be monitored through a combination of real-time data collection, analysis, and ongoing assessment to ensure that it effectively addresses the issues related to climate change and fishing in the lagoon.

The positioning of the SMART GATE and the monitoring system is expected between January and April 2024. A first test of the model and review of parameters setting (subsequently the 1st internal

monitoring/evaluation of the data) is expected in August 2024. A monitoring and evaluation of the implementation will be planned every 4 months, and a report will be provided with a deeper analysis of the NBSs performance over the previous months. These reports can include:

- Overview of data trends and significant events.
- Assessment of whether predefined parameters and thresholds were met.
- Any maintenance or technical issues encountered and their resolution.
- Comparisons to baseline data and long-term goals.
- Recommendations for adjustments or improvements based on monitoring results.

Availability and access of monitored data

All the instruments listed above will have features that enable them to transmit data remotely. They will all provide acquired data associated with date and time. The acquired data will be able to be transmitted remotely, real time preferably, will be accessible by software that also allows remote configuration and includes various telemetry functions including intelligent alarm systems. An internal memory for devices to recover data in case of no connection with the cloud is foreseen.

The data collection platform must be accessible both by public authorities and general public, with the possibility to visualize raw data or elaborated data depends on the type of user.

4.4. Conclusions

The TransformAr project in Oristano has highlighted two innovative solutions to address environmental and climatic challenges in the region: COAST and SMART GATE.

The COAST solution aims to enhance knowledge and awareness among key stakeholders, measured through participatory meetings, the replicability of COAST on a regional scale, dissemination through factsheets, and the influence of COAST on local policies. The Local Wetland Observatory plays a pivotal role, with regular updates to monitor the status of wetlands.

On the other hand, the SMART GATE, as part of a NBS, focuses on improving water quality, biodiversity, and ecosystem integrity. It anticipates a reduction in economic losses, an enhancement of fishery resource productivity, and optimized efficiency of lagoon dynamics, especially concerning flood risk and the ecological health of the lagoon. These impacts are quantifiable through a series of indicators, including water quality, response time to hydraulic changes, and the accuracy of the SMART GATE system.

In summary, the solutions proposed in the TransformAr project offer a combined approach of governance and technology to ensure a sustainable future for the wetlands of Oristano, with expected impacts that could significantly influence climate resilience and ecosystem conservation.

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5.0 Westcountry Region: Improving the agricultural-riparian interface in nutrient sensitive catchments in South West England

Executive summary

The Westcountry region demonstrator seeks to address the problems of diffuse water pollution and habitat loss relating to intensive agriculture, exacerbated by increasing rainfall and periods of drought caused by a changing climate. Westcountry Rivers Trust (WRT) are testing emerging ecosystem services markets as a mechanism to pay landowners to reinstate wetlands and riparian buffers along river corridors in three ecologically designated catchments where nutrient pollution has been identified as a serious problem. Outcomes are monitored using metrics relating to the broad range of benefits strategic habitat reinstatement can deliver. The benefits of flood mitigation, drought resilience, improved water quality and increased habitat deliver the cross sectoral climate adaptation identified through stakeholder workshops. WRT use a range of site-specific indicators to define appropriate baseline and assess the environmental and wider outcomes, with an emphasis on those valued in ecosystem markets: Water quality and biodiversity. The infographic of the Westcountry demonstrator is depicted below.

5.1. Context

Infographic

Objectives

Climate risks and impacts in the Westcountry region include pollution, flooding, drought, and reduced development. Although climate change adaptation capacity is developing well within all sectors, the ability to integrate cross-sectoral delivery is still lagging.

Following discussion with stakeholders in the agricultural, water industry and conservation sectors, the following risks were identified:

- Water resource issues linked to climate change: seasonal flood and drought, impacting agricultural outputs and riparian habitat.
- Reduced water quality due to sediment and nutrient loss from agriculture, amplified by low dilution rates from drought and soil run off from heavy rain, affecting sensitive habitats, fisheries, recreation and human health.
- Planning hiatus due to poor water quality from excess nutrients, designated under Habitat Regulations until mitigation for sewage increases from new development can be provided.

The objectives are to deliver **nature-based solutions** in the form of riparian buffers, floodplain wetlands and ponds that will capture sediment and reduce nutrient loading in rivers and increase water storage capacity and riparian habitat in the target catchments.

To improve sustainability and uptake of these solutions amongst landowners, compensation for long-term sacrifice of agricultural use along river corridors is needed. WRT will test the mechanisms of Phosphate credits and Biodiversity Net Gain (BNG) credits, where housing developers pay landowners for long-term (30-80yrs) delivery of ecosystem services, releasing new development in the catchment.

Geography of the Westcountry

The demonstrator sites are all located in the south-west of England (*Figure 1*). Each site falls within a catchment designated as either a Special Area of Conservation (SAC) (Camel (*Figure 2*) and Axe) or Ramsar site (Somerset Levels (*Figure 3*) and Moors), where water quality and quantity issues have been identified. The catchments each have different topography, soil type and agricultural systems, meaning that different approaches to NBS are needed for each area.

Figure 43 Map of the South west of England showing project river catchments

Figure 44 View of the River Camel in Cornwall (SAC)

Figure 45 View of the River Tone in Somerset (Ramsar)

Climate vulnerability, impacts and challenges

The Westcountry is likely to witness drier summers and an increase in the frequency of extreme weather events, such as droughts (Southwest Water 2021). High energy rainfall events can also cause mobilization of sediment and nutrients leading to water quality issues.

The Meteorological Office highlights detailed impacts for the Southwest (Met Office UKCP) including:

- More frequent intense rainfall and wind-driven rain causing river and surface water flooding.
- Warmer wetter winters causing problems with crop management.
- Hotter drier summers causing problems for water quality and supply.
- Increase in extreme weather and disruptive events such as flooding, droughts, landslides or heatwaves interrupting or limiting access to vital services and impacting on people's physical and mental health.
- Sea level rise affecting the viability of coastal communities and coastal infrastructure through flooding and erosion.

These projections were supported by the modelling carried out by PIK for the Westcountry stakeholder workshops in spring 2022 for Work package 2. (Figures 4-7 below)

Figure 46 Summary of climate projections for the Westcountry (Source: PIK presentation for Workshop 2 WP3) using ISIMIP 3b DATA

Figure 47 Modelled precipitation change shows drier summers and wetter winters

Figure 48 Modelling shows reduced river flows in summer and autumn

Figure 49 Modelling shows increased runoff during late summer to winter, but with high uncertainty due to coarse hydrological models

Adaptation within the demonstrator

In 2021 Natural England, the UK government's statutory advisor for the natural environment, imposed a stop to all development in designated river catchments where water quality was failing targets due to nutrient enrichment. These catchments are now subject to Nutrient Neutrality (NN) planning rules. Locally, this means any new development must mitigate additional phosphates entering waterbodies via additional load on the sewage system. Mitigation can be either on the development site itself, or off-site, delivered through land use change elsewhere within the catchment. Off-site mitigation usually means reduced inputs from agriculture or work to improve sewage treatment by water companies.

- The Conservation of Habitats and Species Regulations 2017 translates the European Habitats Directive into UK law. It sets out measures for protection of natural habitats and wild fauna and flora. This is the legal basis for the Nutrient Neutrality ruling.

Currently, nutrient neutrality policy is focused on land use change within the catchment area, using a calculator that assesses phosphate reductions based on nutrient export coefficients from different land uses. For example, changing from dairy farmland to woodland will deliver $0.47\text{kg Ha}^{-1}\text{ yr}^{-1}$ phosphate mitigation. This approach does not recognize the enhanced benefits which could be achieved by focusing land use change along the river corridor. It identifies only constructed wetlands as a form of additional

treatment. Initially, WRT intended to develop Integrated Constructed Wetlands (ICW) on farms. However, there are difficulties with adapting this solution to diffuse pollution, with intermittent and variable inflows impacting on effectiveness. Alongside this, WRT identified issues around compliance with existing agricultural regulations (Environment Agency UK) and due to the high costs of land purchase when phosphate credits were not available at the outset. Therefore, alternative solutions such as wetland riparian buffers have been prioritised.

Current evidence on the effectiveness of natural process led NBS to deliver multiple benefits is limited (Robotham et al, 2022). Through TransformAr WRT want to increase the evidence base for the benefits of NBS, including buffer strips and habitat restoration, within the region. Strategic implementation of this type of NBS would deliver multiple co-benefits addressing the other risks identified in the Environment Act (2021) including habitat loss, recreation and sediment loss to waterbodies.

- Environment Act 2021: Aims to improve air and water quality, tackle waste, increase recycling, halt the decline of species, and improve the country's natural environment to make it more resilient to climate shocks. This environment act does not directly target adaptation, however ensuring the protection and the development of the natural environment increases the ability of the territory to overcome climate-related stresses (e.g., natural buffer zones, increased permeability, etc.).

The desire to increase the evidence base for innovative NBS in the Westcountry demonstrator region and to deliver multiple co-benefits realised over long lead times are well aligned with the overarching objectives of the Climate Change Act (2008). Within the CCA there is a legal requirement to develop a National Adaption Programme (NAP) with objectives relating to climate adaptation and time-scaled proposals and policies to meet those objectives. The NAP sets out four overarching objectives to address the greatest risks and opportunities arising due to climate change:

- Increasing awareness;
- Increasing resilience to current extremes;
- Taking timely action for long-lead time measures;
- Addressing major evidence gaps

Despite the policy relevance and growing interest in NBS, the knowledge base is lacking evidence for lowland catchments typical of those in the south of England (Lockwood et al., 2022). There is also uncertainty over the sustainability of water storage in such features, where rapid sediment deposition could diminish storage capacity over time (Lane, 2017). Thus more evidence is required to support the delivery of wider benefits from NBS which underpin agri-environmental policies such as the UK Government's Environmental Land Management Scheme (ELMS), outlined in the Agriculture Act (2020). Alongside the Green Finance Strategy (2023) this could provide farmers with financial incentives for adopting NFM and other NBS, thereby increasing uptake more widely (Bark et al., 2021).

5.2. Description of solutions in TransformAr

Overview of the solutions

WRT are developing several NBS across three river catchments: The Camel, the Axe and the Tone. Some use familiar methods, and others are more experimental, for example using ponds and willow beds to

harvest phosphates. The ambition was to test a range of solutions across different parameters. The NBS primarily deal with diffuse agricultural pollution prior to the point of entry to the main water course. The project looks specifically at funding streams to pay for both the initial (capital) cost of delivery and the long-term maintenance and compensation to the landowner for loss of agricultural productive land (revenue). The creation of this type of farm Sustainable Drainage System (SuDS) is not expensive, but landowners are unwilling to sign up in the numbers needed to have a significant effect without fair payment. Nutrient Neutrality provides an opportunity to leverage investment from developers to pay for strategic nutrient mitigation on farms.

There are currently 10 NBS sites across the three catchments at different stages of delivery for TransformAR. These include farm ponds (*Figure 8*), floodplain wetland habitat restoration, sediment traps, and filtration or buffer strips. These types of solutions were also highlighted by stakeholders as part of the adaption pathways co-creation workshops.

They can be created individually or be combined and used in treatment trains according to the specific site conditions and pollution load. One aspect WRT are testing is what level of maintenance is required at a minimum to keep the intervention functioning as designed. The landowners involved often do not have the time or resources to carry out regular or complex maintenance activities. WRT are also testing better ways to identify suitable strategic sites, using a combination of GIS analysis, site survey and chemical analysis of water and soils. Ultimately, the deciding factor is landowner willingness to take part.

Figure 50 Sediment being removed as part of restoration of farm pond for TransformAr

This work complements existing WRT projects, primarily funded by the regional water company (Southwest Water) and National and Local Government, encouraging good environmental practice amongst farmers to reduce pollution at source. This includes the Devon and Cornwall Soils Alliance which offers one-to-one advice on soil and crop management to reduce risk of soil runoff. The Southwest Water [Upstream Thinking](#) project also provides grants to farmers in drinking water catchments to upgrade farm infrastructure such as roofs and tracks. Increasingly, this project is introducing green infrastructure such as cross slope hedging, woodland planting and leaky dams in streams and ditches. Southwest Water is also now funding farm advice on nutrient budgets in the Camel and Axe catchments due to the Nutrient Neutrality issue.

These projects support farmers in staying compliant with Government regulations around water quality and chemical use, such as Farming Rules for Water. Sourcing additional funding from the private sector is increasingly important as agricultural support payments are reduced following Brexit and the withdrawal from the Common Agricultural Policy. To this end, WRT are collaborating with Cornwall Council on identifying BNG and NBS sites to be included in their Local Investment in Nature Cornwall (LINC) project. Relating to climate change adaptation, WRT are working on behalf of Devon County Council to deliver Natural Flood Management NBS for their Devon Resilience Innovation Project (DRIP).

Riparian buffers with wetland restoration

Riparian buffers are bankside strips along watercourses where agricultural activities are reduced or excluded. This is commonly done by constructing fencing to keep livestock off, or seeding grass at the edge of arable fields. The primary purpose is to protect rivers from direct impacts such as poaching by cattle and bank destabilisation, as well as nutrient input from fertilisers and dung. Studies (Vought et al 1995) have shown efficacy of buffers in removing nutrients increases with width, due to the rougher surface of vegetation capturing sediment and increasing infiltration due to root action and reduced compaction. This effect increases steeply to about 6m width and levels off at around 20m. The type of vegetation, soil properties, local climate and topography also play a role in buffer effectiveness. The adjacent land use will affect the level of nutrients entering the buffer. Buffer strips also provide space for riparian vegetation and woodland, which is considered an essential component of the river ecosystem. Currently, river condition assessments for BNG consider 10m width either side of the channel to be part of the river. WRT have found that fencing a narrow buffer (1-2m) where nutrient levels have already been elevated by agricultural management results in dense growth of brambles (*Rubus*) and nettles (*Urtica dioecia*). This limits opportunities for more varied natural vegetation to emerge. Another issue is the increasing colonisation by Invasive Non Native Species such as Himalayan Balsam (*Impatiens glandulifera*), particularly associated with increased light levels from riparian management. It is therefore considered beneficial to continue low levels of conservation grazing in these buffers in many cases. This requires a wider buffer to be practical. Examples of trial sites include Slaughterbridge Farm, Penvose campsite and Yarty Farm in the Camel catchment.

Ponds and SuDS capturing sediment

Introducing features to capture and manage overland flow helps treat nutrient pollution as well as flood risk. These need to be sited in a location near a source and on a pathway of likely flows during heavy rainfall. Typically, a sediment trap is a depression excavated for capturing soil run off, whereas a longer treatment train including swales, ponds and wetlands would be required for effective water quality improvements. Studies show that functional ponds (that stay wet) hold high levels of sediment at the bottom of the pond (Gilbert et al 2014). There is also evidence that this can capture carbon, contributing to climate change mitigation. There is a risk however that if the pond is not maintained and dries out, or banks fail, the nutrient rich sediment will be released back into surface waters, reversing these benefits. Similarly, if sediment builds up, seasonal changes in temperature and water volume can cause phosphates to be released into a soluble state which will escape through overflows or outlets. Therefore, it is essential that these features are regularly maintained, with sediment being removed from the system, to remain effective. Sediment can be spread on adjacent low risk land (level and away from watercourses), where they will contribute to soil and crop nutrient levels and become a useful resource.

Maintenance activities should use straightforward techniques and equipment so that they can be carried out sustainably by the landowner.

Additional benefits from ponds and scrapes and other SuDS features include increased habitat for invertebrates, birds, amphibians and wetland plants. They improve infiltration rates and hold water for longer, reducing flood risks and improving drought resilience. High levels of nutrients entering the system will reduce the biodiversity benefits, as will overzealous maintenance activity, so a pragmatic balance needs to be found between delivering different benefits. Sites using this approach include Wambrook farm, Penvose campsite, Worthyvale Manor, Snowdon Hill and Harpford Bridge Farm.

Floodplain reconnection

A once common feature of our agricultural landscapes are floodplain meadows, which remain wet for long periods of time after inundation from adjacent watercourses. Floodplains have been disconnected from river channels in many places. The channel has become more incised through repeated dredging to facilitate faster flows of water. There are often floodbanks, either designed, or informal from dredged material, preventing water overflowing onto the floodplain. In addition, field drains are commonly dug into riverside fields to make them accessible for grazing all year round. Reconnecting the floodplain encourages interchange of water, sediment and nutrients between the channel and the floodplain, which becomes a wetland environment, supporting managing flood risk, climate regulation, habitat provision, groundwater recharge and amenity. This can involve blocking drains; excavating scrapes to retain longer term pockets of water; introducing material such as wood or stone to the river channel to partially obstruct it or make it shallower and push high flows into the floodplain. Introducing more diverse vegetation, either planted or by natural regeneration, can also slow flows and increase infiltration and sediment capture, as it increases the roughness (runoff coefficient) of the surface over which flood water flows, slowing it down and increasing infiltration and sediment capture.

Floodplain reconnection is being trialled at sites including Tregooden Farm, Chubbs Farm and Rooke Farm.

Description of the expected innovation

Innovation in site selection

The nature-based solutions identified as part of adaption pathways co-creation workshops can be implemented individually or combined and used in treatment trains according to the specific site conditions and pollution load. WRT are developing and testing new ways to identify suitable strategic sites, using a combination of GIS (Geographic Information Systems) analysis, site surveys, and a chemical analysis of water and soils. The strategic identification of the most appropriate NBS sites is always constrained by landowner willingness to take part and eligibility to enter into payment schemes. WRT's reputation as a 'trusted broker' working with landowners to reduce their impacts on water quality enables engagement with landowners towards the best possible outcomes.

Our advisors have long worked in the affected catchments and are knowledgeable about problem areas from observation over years of engagement. Following initial conversations with landowners about potential land use options, we also needed to establish the value of the change in terms of Phosphate credits. Cornwall Council and Royal Haskoning DHV have developed a 'phosphate budget calculator,' based on advice provided by Natural England, for developers to use to measure their impact and offsetting required. The mitigation tab can also be used to quantify mitigation being offered by landowners for credits.

The whole spreadsheet can be found at the link [here](#) A worked example below uses screenshots to illustrate the process.

This tool consists of seven main worksheets:

- Stage 1 - Identifies the additional nutrients as a result of changes in the population
- Stage 2 - Calculates the nutrient load from current land use
- Stage 3 - Calculates the nutrient load from future land uses
- Stage 4 - Calculates the total change in nutrient loading as a result of the proposed development
- Mitigation - current - Calculates the required solutions to achieve nutrient neutrality under current wastewater permit limits
- Mitigation - post 2025 - Calculates the required solutions to achieve nutrient neutrality under AMP7 wastewater permit limits

For the purpose of evaluating P credits, we can skip to stage 5 – mitigation. A box at the top shows the Total Phosphate budget to be mitigated. In this case it would be zero.

Mitigation Spreadsheet from Phosphate Budget Calculator:

The screenshot displays two side-by-side forms for identifying current land use of mitigation areas. The left form is for 'On-site mitigation' and the right is for 'Off-site mitigation'. Both forms include a dropdown menu for mitigation type (No/Yes), a note about implementation, and a table for identifying current land use with columns for Value, Unit, and a dropdown for selection. The 'On-site mitigation' form shows a 'mitigation land runoff coefficient' of 0.00, while the 'Off-site mitigation' form shows 0.49. Blue arrows point to the dropdown menus in the 'Specific land use of on-site mitigation area' and 'Specific land use of off-site mitigation area' sections, with text explaining their purpose.

On-site mitigation:

- On-site mitigation: No
- Note: If the mitigation is to be implemented on-site then the user should select "Yes" in the list above. If off-site mitigation is to be implemented instead, then the user should select "No" above.
- Identify current land use of on-site mitigation area
- Average land use of the on-site mitigation area: NaN, No, Kg/ha/year
- Specific land use of on-site mitigation area:

High density urban	No	Kg/ha/year
Medium density urban	No	Kg/ha/year
Low density urban	No	Kg/ha/year
Commercial / Industrial	No	Kg/ha/year
Urban open space	No	Kg/ha/year
Dairy	No	Kg/ha/year
Lowland grazing	No	Kg/ha/year
Mixed	No	Kg/ha/year
Poultry	No	Kg/ha/year
Pigs	No	Kg/ha/year
Horticulture	No	Kg/ha/year
Cereals	No	Kg/ha/year
General Arable	No	Kg/ha/year
LFA	No	Kg/ha/year
Allotments and city farms	No	Kg/ha/year
Woodland (e.g. conifer, mixed, broad-leaved)	No	Kg/ha/year
Greenspace	No	Kg/ha/year
shrub / heathland / bracken / bog	No	Kg/ha/year
Water	No	Kg/ha/year
- On-site mitigation land runoff coefficient: 0.00

Off-site mitigation:

- Off-site mitigation: Yes
- Note: If the mitigation is to be implemented off-site then the user should select "Yes" in the list above. If on-site mitigation is to be implemented instead, then the user should select "No" above.
- Identify current land use of off-site mitigation area
- Select the soil drainage type: Freely draining
- Specific land use of off-site mitigation area:

High density urban	No	Kg/ha/year
Medium density urban	No	Kg/ha/year
Low density urban	No	Kg/ha/year
Commercial / Industrial	No	Kg/ha/year
Urban open space	No	Kg/ha/year
Dairy	Yes	Kg/ha/year
Lowland grazing	No	Kg/ha/year
Mixed	No	Kg/ha/year
Poultry	No	Kg/ha/year
Pigs	No	Kg/ha/year
Horticulture	No	Kg/ha/year
Cereals	No	Kg/ha/year
General Arable	No	Kg/ha/year
LFA	No	Kg/ha/year
Allotments and city farms	No	Kg/ha/year
Woodland (e.g. conifer, mixed, broad-leaved)	No	Kg/ha/year
Greenspace	No	Kg/ha/year
shrub / heathland / bracken / bog	No	Kg/ha/year
Water	No	Kg/ha/year
- Off-site mitigation land runoff coefficient: 0.49

mitigation land runoff coefficient: 0.49

Annotations:

- Blue arrow pointing to the 'Specific land use of on-site mitigation area' dropdowns: "This side is for mitigation on the development site."
- Blue arrow pointing to the 'Specific land use of off-site mitigation area' dropdowns: "Select current land use and soil type"

Figure 51 Mitigation spreadsheet from Phosphate budget calculator

Land run-off coefficients are calculated from the typical annual rainfall (1500mm/yr) the soil/surface type – free draining to impermeable. The type of land use is then included as a factor to get the final number. A slightly different calculation is performed for urban land use based on density of development.

Land Use	1500 mm/yr		
	Free draining	Impermeable (Drained for Arable)	Impermeable (Drained for Arable + Grassland)
Dairy	0.49	0.39	0.39
Lowland grazing	0.36	0.59	0.48
Mixed Livestock	0.51	0.51	0.51
Poultry	0.58	0.57	0.57
Pig	0.34	2.10	0.34
Horticulture	0.51	0.52	0.52
Cereals	0.61	0.63	0.63
General Arable	0.46	1.58	1.02
LFA	0.29	0.38	0.31

Figure 52 Data table of agricultural coefficients

Value of land use change in KG/year of Phosphate removed from the catchment:

5. Identify proposed land uses for mitigation	Value	Unit	Value	
Constructed wetland	1.000	hectares	8.49	kg/year
Urban open Space	1.000	hectares	0.49	kg/year
Water	1.000	hectares	0.49	kg/year
Woodland	1.000	hectares	0.47	kg/year
Heathland / Bog	1.000	hectares	0.47	kg/year
Meadow/semi-natural grassland/greenspace	1.000	hectares	0.47	kg/year
Sum total area needed to be created	6.000	hectares	-10.88	Kg/year

Note: This section allows the user to input the required area for the various land uses to be created, with the equivalent TP and TN to be offset in order for the development to be nutrient neutral. The same applies as above regarding on-site mitigation.

Figure 53 Testing different land use change options

It can be seen from this example that only constructed wetland shows a significant difference in output compared to more traditional land use options. Based on this, a landowner is unlikely to select a woodland option, due to the expense of establishing woodland and the permanent nature of the change. A meadow option has very nearly the same score, is reversible and requires minimal initial investment.

5. Identify proposed land uses for mitigation	Value	Unit	Value	
Constructed wetland	1.000	hectares	8.51	kg/year
Urban open Space	1.000	hectares	0.51	kg/year
Water	1.000	hectares	0.51	kg/year
Woodland	1.000	hectares	0.49	kg/year
Heathland / Bog	1.000	hectares	0.49	kg/year
Meadow/semi-natural grassland/greenspace	1.000	hectares	0.49	kg/year
Sum total area needed to be created	6.000	hectares	-11.00	Kg/year

Note: This section allows the user to input the required area for the various land uses to be created, with the equivalent TP and TN to be offset in order for the development to be nutrient neutral. The same applies as above regarding on-site mitigation.

Figure 54 Output when the original land use is changed to horticulture

The calculator is described as for guidance purposes only due to the limitations and assumptions of the model. It only considers changes of broad habitat and not particular sites or circumstances. Nor does it acknowledge the nuances of different farming styles, even within the same sector, on outputs of phosphates and particularly soil compaction.

For WRT the most troubling aspect is the lack of location specific guidance. It is not required that these land use changes should be on high-risk pathways to the SAC river. And the mitigation options do not define locally suitable habitat types, so the implication is that any generic approach could be acceptable in any location.

WRT intends to influence land managers using WRT's own evidence from TransformAr to redress this gap in information.

Target locations have been identified using GIS mapping to determine where there is a higher risk of run off due to steepness of topography and soil type, and also where wetland is more likely to develop (Figure 13).

Figure 55 Wetland opportunity mapping for the River Allen, part of the Camel catchment.

Solution modelling: Farmscoper

“Farmscoper is a decision support tool that can be used to assess diffuse agricultural pollutant loads on a farm and quantify the impacts of farm mitigation methods on these pollutants.

The farm systems within the tool can be customised to reflect management and environmental conditions representative of farming across England and Wales. The tool contains over 100 mitigation methods, including many of those in the latest Defra Mitigation Method User Guide.

FARMSCOPER was originally developed under Defra project [WQ0106](#). It was expanded under Defra Project [SCF0104](#) to include additional pollutants and two new workbooks – one providing greater detail on the costs of mitigation method implementation, the other allowing the tool to be applied at catchment to national scale.

Under Environment Agency funding, the catchment scale data has been updated to 2015, with data now included for a range of smaller spatial scales. The latest version (v5) now includes up to date climate,

agricultural survey and farm management data. The updated greenhouse gas (GHG) calculations closely match the latest UK Agricultural Ammonia and GHG inventory.” <https://adas.co.uk/services/farmscoper/>

By running the existing the situation of a farm, or parcel of land against a mitigation scenario, it is therefore possible to calculate predicted P reductions. An example is provided below.

Axe example calculation

Area: 1.2ha (3 ac) taken out of dairy production.

Proposed plan: Land use change for several smaller fields with combined area of 1.2 ha (3 ac), changed from dairy grazing into no livestock.

Farmscoper output for dairy land use is: 0.8kg

Farmscoper Create
09/08/2023

File Information
Create File: FARMSCOPERS
Climate: 900 - 1200 mm
Soil Type: Impermeable - Drained for Arable
Farm Area: 1.2 ha

	Nitrate (kg)	Phosphorus (kg)	Sediment (kg)	Ammonia (kg)	Methane (kg)	Nitrous Oxide (kg)	Pesticides (units)	FIOs (10 ⁻⁹ cfu)	Soil Carbon (t)	Energy Use (kg CO ₂)	Production (t)
Arable	0.00	0.00	0.0	0.00	0.0	0.00	0.00	0.0	0.0	0	0
Grass	52.95	0.50	101.6	13.76	112.3	2.50	0.00	75.3	156.0	198	0
Rough	0.00	0.00	0.0	0.00	0.0	0.00	0.00	0.0	0.0	0	0
Other	2.77	0.29	0.0	28.97	259.6	6.68	0.00	61.6	0.0	94.0	0
Total	55.72	0.80	101.6	42.74	371.9	9.18	0.00	136.9	156.0	1.138	4.896

Report Units
 Total Loss
 Loss Per ha

Compact or Expand Report

Grassland	ha
Permanent Pasture	1
Rotational Grassland	0
Rough Grazing	0

Manure Values	kg N
Dairy FYM	129
Beef Slurry	9

Livestock	Count
Dairy	
Cows and Heifers	2
Heifers in Calf (2 years +)	0
Heifers in Calf (< 2 years)	1

By changing the land use to no livestock the Farmscoper output becomes: 0.17kg

Farmscoper Create
09/08/2023

File Information
Create File: FARMSCOPERS
Climate: 900 - 1200 mm
Soil Type: Impermeable - Drained for Arable
Farm Area: 1.2 ha

	Nitrate (kg)	Phosphorus (kg)	Sediment (kg)	Ammonia (kg)	Methane (kg)	Nitrous Oxide (kg)	Pesticides (units)	FIOs (10 ⁻⁹ cfu)	Soil Carbon (t)	Energy Use (kg CO ₂)	Production (t)
Arable	0.00	0.00	0.0	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.0	0.0	0.0
Grass	4.59	0.17	101.6	0.00	0.00	0.09	0.00	0.00	156.0	136.6	0
Rough	0.00	0.00	0.0	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.0	0.0	0.0
Other	0.00	0.00	0.0	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.0	0.0	0.0
Total	4.59	0.17	101.6	0.00	0.00	0.09	0.00	0.00	156.0	136.6	0

Report Units
 Total Loss
 Loss Per ha

Compact or Expand Report

Grassland	ha
Permanent Pasture	1
Rotational Grassland	0
Rough Grazing	0

Manure Values	kg N
Dairy FYM	0
Beef Slurry	0

Livestock	Count
Dairy	
Cows and Heifers	0
Heifers in Calf (2 years +)	0
Heifers in Calf (< 2 years)	0

Based upon the above figures (0.8 – 0.17kg P) this equates to an annual saving of 0.63 Kg P/year (0.53 kg P/ha/year).

Limitations of capability and use

The scale at which Farmscoper is employed is potentially a very significant limitation. Farmscoper was developed as a policy tool for answering questions at *landscape* scale, but which was able to utilise and produce data at farm level. The input requirements were based around data that would be available at such scales, and which the models used to predict the pollutant losses would be sensitive to. Due to the time required for model simulations, Farmscoper relies upon a database of previously calculated pollutant losses to generate a 'baseline' pollutant load. In order to generate this database and develop the baseline, and to characterise the impacts of certain mitigation methods, it was necessary to make a number of assumptions about farming practice, such as the timing of fertiliser applications. These assumptions were generally based on national surveys of farm practice data, and thus reflect typical behaviour across the landscape, rather than the behaviour for any specific farm.

The source models used to populate the pollutant loss database (i.e. to create the baseline) were applied at 1km² resolution across England and Wales, using local data on soils, slopes, field connectivity, rainfall etc. and the results aggregated for the 3 soil types and 6 climate zones available within Farmscoper. The predicted losses thus represent a typical environmental situation (for the soil type and climate zone selected) and cannot perfectly replicate the specific conditions that may be found in a field or even across a farm."

Farmscoper also has no ability to account for pollutant sources which occur off-farm, i.e., from upstream/higher in the catchment. This misses the opportunity for one farm to act as the buffer/mitigation for another farm/ another source. In this situation on-the-ground testing needs to be employed to both predict and acknowledge any P reduction.

Farmscoper is now hosted on the ADAS website: <https://adas.co.uk/services/farmscoper/>

Innovation in monitoring and evaluation of co-benefits.

WRT are developing monitoring techniques that are appropriate for the solution and that can be utilised more widely. Monitoring nutrient capture and influx is more challenging at sites where there are inconsistent flows in water impacting nutrient concentrations. Therefore, options including nutrient testing of soil and sediment will also be undertaken. Where needed, modelling of phosphate capture can also be used to validate and verify solutions. Due to the wider roll out of these solutions, monitoring needs to be appropriate and cost effective to ensure the credit scheme is viable.

For habitat improvements the Biodiversity Net Gain (BNG) 4.0 metric <https://publications.naturalengland.org.uk/publication/6049804846366720> can be used to establish a baseline and determine the improvements in habitat after implementation. BNG can also potentially be stacked with nutrient neutrality and offer an additional market to the landowner.

The use of Citizen Science is an innovative way to generate a broad understanding of water quality across catchments and allows for high risk or priority areas to be identified, which can then be targeted for solutions implementation.

Innovation in contracts and financing mechanisms.

Each catchment and area that is involved in nutrient neutrality has a separate market system, as there are differing local authorities, developer demand levels and capitalisation models. For the Axe catchment, a digital solution is being developed to create an online nutrient trading platform. The Natural Capital Marketplace (NCM) is hosted by a registered charity; the UNESCO North Devon Biosphere Foundation (Biosphere Foundation). The platform can be viewed here: <https://app.naturalcapital.market/>

WRT are involved in an Environment Agency nutrient neutrality project on the Axe in which the Biosphere Foundation are a partner and are offering to deliver their contribution to develop the nutrient market on NCM at cost. The platform has the advantage that it offers landowners options to create Carbon Credits and Biodiversity Net Gain income in addition to nutrient credits (where there is additionality on site or elsewhere on the holding). It also offers developers a single market for their Nutrient Credit, Biodiversity offset and Carbon offset needs. Importantly the new nutrient market will integrate all the learning from existing trading schemes, within the UK and internationally, supported by NE National Teams and the newly formed Nutrient Programme Team in the EA. A key element of this work is demonstrating the benefit of any Natural Capital product and nutrient credits will be no different. This is termed Monitoring, Reporting and Verification (MRV). The North Devon Biosphere offers to design the MRV element of the nutrient trading model at cost using their Smart Biosphere programme illustrated here:

<https://biospherefcic.maps.arcgis.com/apps/webappviewer3d/index.html?id=768524c5399e463490f3af18c748bd98>

5.3. Expected impacts

Overview of the expected impacts

Achieving Nutrient Neutrality

The primary objective of Nutrient Neutrality is to make the issue of nutrient pollution in designated catchments no worse. The wider environmental objectives in this project are to deliver the best outcomes for nature and the region's rivers, by working strategically to restore river corridors and surrounding catchment function and provide a range of environmental co-benefits. To achieve this, multiple landowners need to be supported to implement a range of NBS to reduce soil and slurry entering watercourses; to reduce the nutrients introduced to farming systems and re-use nutrients more efficiently. In appropriate locations, NBS can also attenuate surface water flows and increase infiltration across the system. This reduces the volume of surface water entering the combined sewerage system and reduces pollution from overflow spills. These primarily environmental impacts will be captured through a range of quantitative and qualitative monitoring metrics and data. Each solution provides a range of primary and secondary impacts, depending on the design and location of solutions. The primary focus is to reduce phosphate pollution these solutions, particularly where funded as part of the nutrient credit scheme. Co-benefits include:

- "Slowing the flow' reducing localised flooding;
- Improvements in habitat and biodiversity value;
- Carbon capture, depending on the intervention type;
- Wider water quality improvements through capturing sediments and other pollutants;

Together these environmental improvements help to build resilience within catchments.

Economic Development in the Catchment

Through TransformAr new nutrient credit markets are being developed which can provide an additional income for landowners and farmers.

In the Camel catchment WRT are working with the local planning authority to create a nutrient credit scheme (Figure 14). Here WRT are liaising directly with farmers and landowners and with the local planning authority, who are capitalising the scheme, through CIL (Community Infrastructure Levy) funds. A key element in the formation of credits, is to find an investor who is willing to capitalise the credit through upfront investment, this can then be recovered when the credit is sold to the end user.

Figure 56 Schematic and flow pathway in the Camel catchment for nutrient creation.

Bilateral marketing of nutrients is becoming commonplace and in recent years online platforms have been used to attract and contract with multiple providers such as farmers. This can reduce cost and alleviate market blockers. Some of the existing platforms include those in Somerset, Avon and Solent catchments hosted by ENTRADE;

<https://www.entrade.co.uk/our-markets/>

In the Axe catchment, the nutrient credit model is slightly different as it will be using the Natural Capital Marketplace (outlined in Section 5.2.3) as a platform to market nutrient credits, alongside other credits that are available. In the Axe, the route for capitalisation is less clear, however there is potential for this role to be undertaken by the regional water company. A schematic of the current scheme in the Axe catchment is shown in Figure 15 below.

Figure 57 Flow diagram for the creation of nutrient credits

WRT are working with the North Devon Biosphere Foundation who are developing the nutrient market on NCM.

By facilitating development these credit schemes support a stable local economy, with affordable homes prioritised for local populations.

Tourism is the biggest economic sector in the region and estimated to support one in five jobs in Cornwall (Local Government Association 2019). The sector is dependent on the beautiful natural environment in the region, including coastal, countryside and moorland scenery. The local economy therefore requires careful stewarding of natural assets, and there is a reputational risk from pollution of both inland and coastal bathing waters.

Raising Climate Awareness and Resilience through Landowner and Community Engagement

WRT has an established history of acting as an ethical and trusted broker for the delivery of payments for ecosystem services. For almost 15 years WRT have worked with the regional water company to act as a broker with landowners and communities (Figure 16), though initiatives such as Upstream Thinking. <https://wrt.org.uk/project/upstream-thinking/>

Figure 58 Ethical Broker example with Water company South West Water and WRT

WRT have adopted this ethical broker position regarding Nutrient Neutrality in the Westcountry Region, to ensure that there is strategic delivery of interventions and actions. Without this, developers may pay to fallow productive farmland, in unsuitable locations, which will not have the greatest benefit for nutrient reduction for the catchment and may impact on food security. New markets are often unregulated, therefore it is important to design the best solutions and offset schemes where possible, to provide a broader range of benefits including climate change adaptation. Through the broker role, WRT will work with investors, regulators, communities and catchment partnerships to develop solutions that provide the greatest benefit overall.

Figure 17 below, highlights how an ecosystem services approach can be used to as an alternative to the traditional agricultural production model.

<https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/payments-for-ecosystem-services-pes-best-practice-guide>

Figure 59 Payments for Ecosystem Services

UK DEFRA (Department for Environment, Farming and Rural Affairs) guidance on establishing and setting up PES schemes and the need to understand the current business model and value of verification is shown in Figure 18.

Figure 60 Illustration from UK DEFRA guide to development of PES scheme

WRT has used PES methodology, particularly with water quality issues, to pay or incentivise landowners to change practices or minimise impacts on water quality. Investment from Water companies to fund these improvements is now part of the investment business plan for each funding cycle and has been adopted much of the UK, with Rivers Trusts often acting as the broker, due to their existing relationships with landowners.

Through WRT’s wider stakeholder involvement there have been examples of community groups opposing new developments in their catchments due to environmental concerns, including opposing the concept of nutrient neutrality outright. Engaging with community groups and developing an active programme of Citizen Science in the selected catchments enables greater community awareness of the benefits of NBS. This includes the wider co-benefits this approach can achieve above the simplistic land-fallowing often favoured by developers. These societal impacts can be evaluated through the public attendance at workshops and monitoring social media posts.

It is expected that many of the benefits and impacts from innovative NBS delivery and novel new nutrient trading schemes will be fully realised after the timescales of the project. WRT will continue to build its longstanding work delivering NBS and seek future funding both to evaluate the legacy of the project and implement the evidence-based outcomes more widely.

Selected indicators

There are three main areas where a successful nutrient neutrality scheme would have positive impacts. These are: Environmental improvements within the selected sensitive catchments; Economic benefits both to communities from unlocking development and providing alternative income for farmers and land managers; And finally social benefits of increasing engagement and understanding of rivers and ecosystems, including threats and resilience.

Environmental improvements

Expected impacts:

Should the land use change be sited strategically in areas adjacent to river corridors, there will be the greatest direct benefit to the environment. The aim of the scheme is to reduce nutrients, primarily phosphates, entering rivers and affecting water quality. The WRT interventions rely on increased hydraulic residence time improving nutrient retention in the riparian zone, where vegetation improves in situ denitrification and phosphate removal rates. Water quality is subject to spot sampling across the affected catchments by citizen scientists (CSI) and WRT staff. It may be hard to demonstrate a direct link with interventions at this scale on catchment water quality over this project timespan, but up and downstream sampling of intervention sites has commenced.

There are also co-benefits to habitats and species from this approach which WRT will monitor through habitat surveys (species richness) and drone footage (habitat extent). Riverfly and fisheries surveys will provide information about the quality of in-river habitat. WRT will also monitor ecological function through soil analysis at intervention sites. Samples will be visually assessed for health based on structure, infiltration rates and samples will be sent to a lab for soil organic matter and nutrient content analysis.

Economic Development in the Catchment

Expected impacts:

The initiation of a trading scheme allowing housing development to proceed by mitigating additional sewerage through land use offsets will overcome the planning hiatus in the affected catchments. New housing is needed for local people who provide a workforce for sustainable economic growth in a region where holiday homes and tourism are a dominant economic sector. Studies (Lichfields, 2018) show that each £1m investment in housing development supports around 19.9 direct jobs, and 15.6 indirect jobs, as the construction industry has an indirect and induced employment multiplier of 2.23 (Lichfields, 2022).

This impact is more complex to assess but the value of P offsets obtained can be expressed as housing units. The value of capitalisation in (£) and value of credits traded can also be used. Also, the number of landowners and investors/developers brought in as part of the scheme. A set of metrics around this can be established as a way of indicating the impact. There will be wider economic benefits including the protection of tourism and recreational value.

Economic benefits to farmers in payments for ecosystem services will be measured in the financial value of BNG and P Credits obtained. WRT are providing support with nutrient budgets on farms, leading to financial savings from more efficient use of fertilisers. In addition the land use change and interventions on floodplains will help retain nutrient rich sediments which are a valuable resource to farmers but a pollutant in rivers. Depth or volume of sediments captured at intervention sites will be measured, along with the nutrient content via lab analysis.

Landowner and Community Engagement

Expected impacts:

This will focus on increasing wider community awareness and understanding of river systems and threats, promoting the benefits of water use awareness and drought resilience.

The success of community engagement activities is monitored and evaluated through quantitative, qualitative and narrative approaches. Metrics can include sign-ups to the Westcountry Citizen Science scheme, numbers of active volunteers and retention and numbers of volunteer surveys. Attendance at participatory research events and workshops offered by WRT and the motivations for this and the

outcomes and actions from those workshops. Higher-level engagement through community groups working with WRT to develop new Citizen Science methodologies and development of co-funding streams to drive environmental outcomes (water quality and resources) which have been identified as important by the community, including landowners and farmers, is also indicative of increased awareness of, and action for, climate resilience.

Baseline data

Environmental Indicators

In the UK there is no central database of all water quality data thus any existing available baseline data must be extracted from a variety of sources subject to availability and access. Natural England base calculations of phosphate loadings in priority Nutrient Naturality catchments using data available in the Environment Agency Water Quality Archive (WIMS) database (Wood et al 2022).

Ideally at least five years of site-specific baseline data is required prior to the delivery of NBS interventions to properly evaluate the impacts on diffuse pollution in a catchment and funding timescales rarely allow for a truly empirical approach to generating baseline data. To augment the currently available data sets a programme of monthly spot monitoring was established in 2022 in both the Axe and Camel catchments which encompasses a range of water quality parameters depending on the specific study site. These include: temperature, pH, conductivity, dissolved oxygen, conductivity, turbidity, nitrate and ammonium, dissolved organic matter (CDOM), optical brightening agents and tryptophan. Please see the Axe Scorecard in the Appendix for initial outputs from this sampling.

Sites are chosen carefully using GIS mapping and local knowledge to monitor the main rivers and their tributaries and to capture inputs from diffuse and point source pollution. This approach will build a strong data set of baseline data across the catchments and help to identify potential sites for NBS interventions. The data is stored in the Cartographer integrated monitoring, mapping, and data interpretation platform and downloaded for additional analysis and reporting.

In addition, WRT has collected the first set of electrofishing and botanical survey results on selected sites. This data will help to ascertain whether we have achieved BNG within the demonstrator sites, as well as improvements in habitat and water quality.

Economic Indicators

Due to the novelty of nutrient credit schemes in the UK, there is no current methodology for assessing the total economic impact generated. Baseline data on the economic impact of the affected activities (housing development, tourism, etc) is also highly diffuse. Therefore, a range of sources & methods must be used to assess the total value generated.

The most direct economic impact will be land value change, which can be used to ascertain the total value of credits to landowners. Baseline data for current capital flows/HA within demonstrator sites can be found using the [NEVO modelling](#) tool. Developed by the University of Exeter, this publicly available model enables analysis of existing land use and value/ha/year, spatially resolved to 2km². Whilst NEVO doesn't currently offer land use conversion values to account for water-quality related NBS, when compared to the ultimate value of credits traded, it will be possible to ascertain the value of land use change. In addition, baseline data on existing nutrient budgets can be obtained from landowners to understand the additional financial benefits of NBS, as safely re-using nutrient-rich sediments captured by interventions

reduces the amount of investment needed in fertilizers, enhancing the cost-effectiveness of land use conversion.

The housing and development sector is most significantly affected by the creation of nutrient credits, however “due to the scale and complexity of the house building industry, there is no single source of data that provides comprehensive information about its day-to-day economic activity and operations” (Lichfields, 2018). Baseline data for the current economic value of housing within the demonstrator site catchments must therefore be extracted from a variety of sources. Baseline data on the estimated economic value of Housing Association homes in the region can be found using the National Housing Federation’s Local Economic Impact Calculator. This tool provides both baseline data on the Gross Value Added (GVA) of social housing, aggregated by region, as well as future projections based on predicted housing developments. As there will be some social housing implicated in the development released by nutrient credits, once exact numbers are known, the tool can be used to provide information about the contribution of those properties to the local economy.

However, social housing only contributes 15% of the total economic value of housing in the UK, with private development contributing 85% (Lichfields, 2018). Baseline data on the economic value of existing private developments is not currently available regionally, however, combining the housing development and employment targets outlined in Local Plans (e.g the Cornwall Local Plan, 2021) with available metrics on job creation, tax revenue and local infrastructure, it will be possible to calculate the value generated by new housing developments in relation to their contribution to existing targets.

Type	Output (£ billions)	Total
New Housing		
Public Housing	£5.5	15%
Private Housing	£32.4	85%
Total New Housing	£38.0	100%

Figure 19, table showing national value of public or ‘social’ housing vs. Private housing to the economy, Lichfields 2018.

Baseline metrics for the projected number of jobs created & supported by housing development; tax revenue generated; and the contribution of private development to community infrastructure are available from Lichfields 2018 study, *The Economic Footprint of Housebuilding in England and Wales*.

Finally, in order to assess the value of each individual credit, baseline data on the capital fronted by investors to complete the works can be acquired, for future comparison with the ultimate value of credits traded.

Social Engagement Indicators

An active programme of Citizen Science monitoring across the Axe and Camel catchments provides high spatial density but low specification monitoring of water quality parameters including phosphate, turbidity, total dissolved solids and temperature. This opportunity will be extended to the Tone catchment when more NBS sites become available. As well as adding valuable baseline data over a wide geographical area, engagement with Citizen Scientists and local ecologically-focused community groups

increases awareness of the issues and promotes general and social acceptance of NBS as a pathway to climate resilience.

Baseline data on the number of volunteers engaged with WRT prior to the commencement of the TransformAr project is available internally, as well as data on numbers of participants who have undertaken additional training. This information can be compared to numbers following the TransformAr project, to ascertain whether the project has contributed a meaningful increase in stakeholder awareness & understanding of climate resilience. In addition, it's possible to survey participants before & after workshops to baseline understanding of climate adaptation & resilience before and after involvement with TransformAr.

Approach to monitor impacts

Detailed monthly spot monitoring plans have been developed for the Camel (23 sites) and Axe (28 sites) catchments, although the exact number of monitoring sites may be refined as further sites for NBS are identified and agreed with landowners. Monitoring and data collection commenced in 2022 in the Camel and Axe catchments and is ongoing. Monthly monitoring data are uploaded into the Cartographer platform for detailed analysis. There are currently around 20 sites in the Camel catchment and 30 sites in the Axe catchment under active Citizen Science monitoring due to high engagement with community environmental groups in these areas. The frequency and consistency of Citizen Science monitoring is more challenging to maintain due to the voluntary nature of this work but nevertheless this provides a useful auxiliary data set due to the high spatial density of the data that can be achieved by hyper-local volunteer monitoring.

During a longitudinal study, multiple data points will be collected at each site for total reactive phosphate and a range of additional water quality metrics. Data sets are analysed annually to create an annual catchment report and scorecard for individual parameters and overall water quality. Over time, these annual reports provide valuable information on catchment health and any changes (improvements) in water quality that may arise.

Availability and access of monitored data

Environmental monitoring and Citizen Science data is available on the WRT website where it can be viewed in the Cartographer app or downloaded manually. A data access policy and platform for Citizen Science water quality data is currently under development by the UK national Rivers Trust as part of the Catchment Systems Thinking Cooperative and it is anticipated that all WRT data will be made available to that platform once live.

5.4. Conclusions

Westcountry Rivers Trust are engaging with landowners, environmental agencies, citizen scientists and planners in the three river catchments affected by the Nutrient Neutrality policy. Stakeholder engagement has been carried out with agricultural, water business and ecological KCS which highlighted risks and potential solutions related to climate change in these locations. The proposed solutions are low maintenance NBS and habitat enhancements in the river corridor, which bring a range of climate adaptation co-benefits. WRT are testing emerging ecosystem service trading mechanisms to provide funding to encourage landowners to accept these solutions. WRT are refining site selection techniques using a combination of GIS and analysis of water quality and soils. WRT are monitoring the wide-ranging co-benefits from the NBS alongside their primary purpose of nutrient pollution reduction to build a case for wider acceptance and valuation by regulators of these strategic solutions.

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Mapping data:

Publisher	Dataset	Data Attribution	Figure number
Cranfield University	Natmap Soils	Soil data © Cranfield University (NSRI) and for the Controller of HMSO 2021.	9
	Detailed River Network	Accessed via the CaBA Data Package.	-
Environment Agency	Flood Zone 2 and 3	© Environment Agency copyright and/or database right 2018. All rights reserved. Some features of this map are based on digital spatial data from the Centre for Ecology & Hydrology, © NERC (CEH). © Crown copyright and database rights 2018 Ordnance Survey 100024198	9
	Source Protection Zones	Contains public sector information licensed under the Open Government Licence v3.0.	-
Natural England	Priority Habitat Inventory	© Natural England copyright. Contains Ordnance Survey data © Crown copyright and database right 2021.	-

	SSSI Units	© Natural England copyright. Contains Ordnance Survey data © Crown copyright and database right 2021.	-
Ordnance Survey	OS Terrain50	Contains public sector information licensed under the Open Government Licence v3.0.	9
	OS VectorMap District	Contains Ordnance Survey data © Crown copyright and database right 2020.	-
Rural Payment Agency	Customer and Land Anonymised Database	Extract from Rural Payments Agency Customer and Land Database (CLAD) – Information warning: This dataset has not been updated since 2015. Contains Environment Agency information © Environment Agency and/or database right	-

Climate change impacts are here and now. The impacts on people, prosperity and planet are already pervasive but unevenly distributed, as stated in the new EU Blueprint strategy (European Commission-EC, 2019). To reduce climate-related risks, the EC and the IPCC agree that transformational adaptation is essential. The TransformAr project aims to develop and demonstrate products and services to launch and accelerate large-scale and disruptive adaptive process for transformational adaptation in vulnerable regions and communities across Europe.

The 6 TransformAr lighthouse demonstrators face a common challenge: water-related risks and impacts of climate change. Based on existing successful initiatives, the project will develop, test and demonstrate solutions and pathways, integrated in Innovation Packages, in 6 territories.

Transformational pathways, including an integrated risk assessment approach are co-developed by means of 9 Transformational Adaptive Blocks. A set of 22 tested actionable adaptive solutions are tested and demonstrated, ranging from nature-based solutions, innovative technologies, financing, insurance and governance models, awareness and behavioral change solutions.

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